

THE AESTHETICS OF THE YORÙBÁ VIDEO FILM

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ABSTRACT

The video film is a new phenomenon in Yorùbá studies. In spite of its prolific production, it has not enjoyed much critical attention which it deserved from scholars. In this work, therefore, attention is focused on the aesthetic evaluation of the Yorùbá video film.

The aesthetic and the semiotic theories have been employed for this study. The two theories are adopted for the following reasons. Aesthetics as a theory is relevant to various arts such as the literary, plastic and the visual. The video as a presentational art, also incorporates these other arts that we have mentioned above. Hence, the relevance of the application of the aesthetic theory to it. Secondly, since the content of the video film is communicated by a combination of several system of signs such as words, gestures, costumes, lighting, sound etc., it follows that its analysis is amenable to semiotic study. The dialectical relationship between the two theories has helped to illuminate and lay bare the literary and the technical devices and/or qualities that are present in the Yorùbá video film.

Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. Our primary sources comprise thirty Yorùba video films selected on generic basis such as folkloric, comic, crime, religious and love. Secondary sources include interviews of some Yorùba video film producers and directors at shooting locations. We have also visited the Nigerian Film Institute, Jos to learn the processes of film making. Lastly, we have made use of relevant film and critical texts.

Our findings fall under the two approaches that we have adopted for our analyses— the literary and the technical.

Under the literary, we have found out that the plot of the Yorùbá video film is usually straightforward and reflects incidents depicting the reality of everyday life and experiences. Furthermore, the Yorùbá video film has focused on the family more than any other social institution. The gender and social roles of the husband, wife, father, mother, brother, sister, child, in-laws and so on are the concern of the medium. We have also found out that the themes of the Yorùbá video film are carefully selected and are in consonance with the producers' creation of

their characters. In the Yorùbá video film, there is a dramatisation of the Yorùbá worldview.

Technical devices such as camera movement, camera angle, sound, lighting etc. are employed in the Yorùbá video film for special effects. These devices are presented for us to admire the dexterity at which the Yorùbá video film producers have mastered the film art.

Of the technical devices considered, two of them have not been perfected by the Yorùbá video film producers. These are: optical trickery (especially in the handling of the supernatural) and the synchronisation of image with sound. This constitutes an aesthetic defect in such films where they occur despite their interesting plot and other literary qualities.

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to:

- i. The Lord Almighty, the ALPHA and OMEGA;
- ii. To my Parents, The Ven. and Mrs. Joseph Olátundé Àlà mú and
- iii. to my wonderful children: Olúwatóbi, Olúwatóba, Babátólá and Olúwatómi and my beloved wife, Eunice.

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Jesu, what didst thou find in me
That you have dealt so lovingly?
How great the joy that thou has brought,
So far exceeding hope or thought!
Jesu, my Lord, I thee adore,
O make me love thee more and more

(Sir J. Barnby, 1838 – 96).

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by Ọlágòkè Ọlúgbéngá ÀLÀMÚ
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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0. Why The Yorubá Video Film?

By Yorùbá video film, we mean dramatic features recorded on video cassettes, which at times are exhibited in cinema halls with the aid of projectors.

The video film is a new phenomenon in Yorùbá studies. It emerged in the early 1990's, as an off shoot of the celluloid film whose production had stopped abruptly as a result of the huge capital required for its production. This was the period of economic recession in Nigeria. Consequently, the video became an alternative vent for the creative ability of the Yorùbá theatre practitioners who abandoned the theatre and embraced the medium with great enthusiasm because they found it more lucrative.

In spite of its prolific production, the Yorùbá video film has not enjoyed much critical attention from scholars. Existing work on the Yorùbá film has been, largely, on the celluloid. This work is therefore

aimed at filling this gap by attempting an aesthetic evaluation of the Yorùbá video film.

1.1 Aims

This study is aimed at attempting an aesthetic evaluation of the Yorùbá video film. Aesthetics as a theory, is relevant to various arts such as the literary, plastic and the visual. Its concern is multidimensional. Among other concerns, aesthetics probes into the impact which a work of art has made on the reader or the target audience; the predominant or over-powering emotion it has invoked; the atmosphere it evokes; its strengths and shortcomings and the standard of artistic perfection which the work has attained.

The video as a representational art also incorporates other arts just like aesthetics. Hence, the relevance of the application of the aesthetic theory to the medium.

1.2 Methodology and Scope

Our discussion of the aesthetics of the Yorùbá video film is done through a combination of theories. While the techniques of literary

appreciation are used to evaluate the video film as dramatic text, the technical processes or procedures that have given birth to the film images are considered to evaluate the quality of these images and to lay bare the aesthetics of the video film text.

We have also applied the semiotic theory in order to be able to see the literary and technical components of the Yorùbá video film as signs. The interstructural relations between these signs are investigated. Thus, this study has two prongs viz, the literary and the technical. But the forte is in the latter which introduces us to a new approach in Yorùba film study.

To achieve a meaningful evaluation of the aesthetics of the Yorùbá video film therefore, 30 Yorùbá video films, selected on generic basis such as the folkloric, comic, crime, religious and love have been selected (see Annex 1). An indepth analysis of these video films has been done towards arriving at a definite description of the aesthetics of the Yorùbá video film.

We have also discussed with and interviewed some Yorùbá video film producers and directors at shooting locations and consulted

relevant literature on film and literary criticism. Finally, our visit to the Nigerian Film Institute, Jos and the National Film and Video Censorship Board (NFVCB), Lagos have familiarised us with the processes of film production and the administration of the film industry in Nigeria respectively.

The achievement of this work is that it is the first to look at the Yorùbá video film. We have also established that the literary as well as technical qualities of the Yorùbá video film must be taken into consideration in order to define the aesthetics of the Yorùbá video film as they mutually reinforce the standard of artistic perfection of the medium. This study, with its two prongs viz, the literary and technical, has introduced a new approach into Yorùbá film study as previous emphasis has mainly been on the literary. The study which is a pioneering work, therefore, serves as a springboard for further studies in Yorùbá film research.

1.3 AN OVERVIEW OF THE YORÙBÁ VIDEO FILM INDUSTRY

This section considers the Yorùbá video film industry. Issues such as the emergence and the management of the industry, the interrelationship of the Yorùbá theatre and film and the functions of the film producer are taken into consideration to provide an indepth study of the Yorùbá video film industry.

Under management, constraints facing the industry in the areas of censorship, piracy and marketing are highlighted. The efforts of the various stakeholders in this industry at combating these problems and their contributions to its growth are also discussed. Our discussion on the Yorùbá theatre and film focuses on the similarities and dissimilarities in the practice of the two media, while the functions of the Yorùbá film producers and directors as well are also given attention in the last segment of the chapter.

1.3.1 **The Emergence and the Management of the Nigerian Video Film Industry**

Literary scholars such as Adédèjì (1971), Èbùn Clark (1978), Ògúndèjì (1988) have written that the Yorùbá dramatic tradition and movement from where the Yorùbá film industry takes its roots, was pioneered by Hubert Ogunde. This is why the theatre movement has been labelled by Ogundeji (1988) as the Ogunde Dramatic Tradition. At the early period of its development, the live stage was the only known available medium where the works of these theatre practitioners were performed. But after a period of time, following the introduction of the radio in 1945 and the television in 1959 in Nigeria, their plays were recorded on these media (Clark 1979; Olusola 1981). The involvement of the theatre practitioners in celluloid film making started in 1976, with the production of *Àjàní Ògún*. (Alàmú 1991; Adélékè 1995). The eventual shift from the stage to the film must have been occasioned, mainly, by the limitations of the medium. The film with its superior technology and production techniques now offers the theatre practitioners an alternative to the inhibitions of the stage.

But by early 1990's the production of the celluloid film stopped abruptly as a result of the economic recession in the country at that time which made it very expensive to produce¹. Consequently, the video became an alternative vent for the creative ability of Nigerian theatre practitioners.

When the Video Cassette Recorder (VCR) was introduced, many Nigerians embraced and purchased it with great enthusiasm. To them, it was an alternative to the television production which prior to this time was the only popular form of entertainment enjoyed in the intimacy of their homes. During this period, video film from the West such as *The Sound of Music* and the James Bond series namely *The Spy Who Loved Me*, *Octopus*, *Goldfinger* among others were prominent in almost every home that had the VCR. Later, foreign musicals, the Indian and the Chinese films followed.

With the realisation of meaningful profits from the video venture, Nigerians took to its production. Among the early popular video films is *Living in Bondage* (1992) produced by Kenneth Nnebue's NEK Video Link. The film condemns the money making syndrome through rituals,

a social evil plaguing the Nigerian society at that period. Within a short period the film became so popular that it sold 200,000 copies within two weeks.²

The prospect of the video film production soon attracted television producers, directors and artists. Some of the early experiences at the Nigerian Television Authority (NTA) were the different soap operas such as *Family Ties* and *Behind The Cloud*.

The manner in which the video film was embraced was phenomenal such that nowadays video film are produced almost on weekly basis in Nigeria. The reason for this is not far-fetched. Firstly, the video is cheap to produce and is lucrative. Secondly, it hardly calls for foreign participation in the areas of production and post-production processes. Thirdly, its diffusion technique permits it to reach thousands or millions of people at once in the intimacy of their homes.

With a strong and virile theatre tradition, and because of the theatre's very relatedness both in theory and practice to the cineart, the transition of the Yorùbá theatre practitioners from the theatre to the

film was less stressful.³ Of all the ethnic groups in Nigeria, the Yorùbá was the first to embrace the video with great enthusiasm.

The first Yorùbá video film was *Igí Dá* (1990) by Kólá Qlátúnde. It was closely followed by Oşo Dáramólá's *Ajá Dúdú* (1990) and Eḅun Olóyède's *Òde Ọsán* (1991). To date, as earlier mentioned, there are about 350 Yorùbá video films (See Annex 2). The films, by and large, promote Yorùbá culture and tradition and polemise pseudo-modernism or foreign culture. They deal with various issues like greed, avarice, pride, infidelity, crime, love, hate and occultism, to mention a few. The moral lesson of these films has always been the triumph of good over evil.

The untiring efforts of the Yorùbá video film producers in promoting the Yorùbá culture and language through this medium have encouraged other ethnic nationalities in Nigeria in realising the potentials of the medium in promoting their respective cultures. Consequently, films in other indigenous languages gradually flooded the market. The Igbo video films are the most prominent after the Yorùbá.

Among the popular ones are *Ikuku* (1993), *Omeṅukọ* (1994), *Echidimme* (1996), and *Nneka* (1996)

The path for Hausa video production was recently set in 1998 by Yusuff Mohammed with the production of *Adawo Lafiya*. Mohammed in an interview in the *Guardian* (2 July, 1998 : 52) claimed that his involvement in the production of Hausa video is essentially to fill the vacuum created by the absence of any in the market and to challenge the domination of the Yorùbá, English and to some extent Igbo movies. He acknowledged the fact that though a few productions have also been made by producers from the non-major ethnic groups in the few years when the production of video took a great leap in the country, none had come in the Hausa language, a major language in Nigeria.

There are a few video films in the non-major Nigerian languages. These include Joe Dundun's *Ugbeyin* (Retribution) in Itsekiri which was produced in 1998. In Èdo, there are two. They are *Ewemade* (What is expected to fail did not) and *Evbakoe* (What you sow you reap). Both films were also produced in 1998 by Utetenegiabi Ọmọ-Osagie. The films have strong, folkloric influence

1.3.2 Film Censorship

To safeguard the video film industry, the Federal Government set up the National Film and Video Censorship Board (NFVCB). The functions of this Board include :

- (i) the encouragement of the production of films in Nigeria
- (ii) to censor or screen films before exhibition

The censorship of films does not promote free enterprise. Many a times, films are screened by the NFVCB before exhibition and marketing. The Board also brings its influence to bear on what otherwise are good films but which they consider as offensive. A case in point is Jidé Kosóko's *Àmíná Eléha* which has to take a new title of *Ìyàwó Alhaji* because the NFVCB considered the former title as 'unhealthy' for Islamic religion⁴.

Ìyàwó Alhaji is the story of a strong-willed and immoral woman who is imprisoned for killing her husband after he has caught her with a boy in their matrimonial home. On her release from jail, however, an

Alhaji who is unaware of her past, marries her, and places her in purdah. Hiding under this cloak, she commits adultery. Her past behaviour soon re-echoes as she injects animosity into her family. She later plots to kill the Alhaji. The Alhaji however is saved by a prophet who exposes her misdemeanour.

What determines the action of the Censor Board in taking decisions includes the themes of the film (which is legitimate) and, unfortunately, religious pressure groups and government's undue interference. There are some subjects which the Board expects every film-maker to steer away from such as religious and/or 'sensitive' political issues. Government's insistence that film-makers should not touch such subjects defines the nature of censorship in Nigeria. The government has always used censorship as a weapon of State control thereby infringing on the right of its citizen to freedom of expression. Lane, quoted in Ekwuazi (1987 : 97), further captures the nature of film censorship in Nigeria:

The real menace of censorship is the insidious and cunning way it is being used as a device to prevent the expression of any opinions contrary

to the various powers and interests which seek to run and control the people, the country, the government and other things that is of importance to them at the time. It is these big interests that are among the strongest supporters of censorship, for they shrewdly recognise in the movie the strongest public weapon ever created that could be used against them.

In 1997, the then Minister for Information and Culture, Dr. Walter Ofonagoro was reported to have enjoined the NFVCB to reduce drastically or clampdown the exhibition and production of pornographic and violent video movies.⁵ He revealed that between 30,000-40,000 various foreign cassettes that were in circulation had not been registered, censored or even classified by the NFVCB and that these illegally imported video films could lead to international litigations against Nigeria by the owners or countries of origin for copyright infringement. A 21-day ultimatum was issued by the Minister to the NFVCB and other relevant bodies to halt the marketing of such films.

Various reactions followed the Minister's pronouncement. The Association of Movie Producers (AMP), the umbrella body for the

producers of English language films, for instance, raised a lot of issues. It commented that there were no criteria to producers on what the censorship board referred to as pornographic and violent films. The body also wondered how the Minister's ultimatum would work when film practitioners were still in the dark as to how such films would be ejected from the markets. The ultimatum given by the Minister, according to AMP was suggestive of the fact that the Censor's Board has not been effective in carrying out its functions. It also wondered why a society in which violence reigned should not be appropriately depicted?

In our own view, we believe that government's involvement in the film business should not be total so as to sustain the industry and allow it compete favourably with those of other countries. The view of the AMP that clamping down on films through censorship may not augur well for the development of the film industry in Nigeria is mostly welcome. Perhaps, the American film industry is the best in the world because of its autonomy and the freedom it enjoys in touching nearly all aspects of human endeavour and condition. Since one of the functions of the NFVCB is to classify the films and announce the right age bracket that is

qualified to watch such films based on the moralistic viewpoint, it should face its primary role through efficient control of all imported and locally produced films in Nigeria. Furthermore, it is only natural that film just like any other work of art portrays the society from which it emanates. Romance, love and sex are issues which result from human interaction in any society. It is therefore not out of place for any work of art to focus its attention on these issues.

In the same vein, there cannot be any crime film if the society is crime free. It is necessary for film producers to widen their scope and touch 'negative' issues of human existence such as war, hatred, lust, violence, etc. In spite of their appearance in films in Nigeria, these so called 'negative' issues have not been allowed in those films to triumph over what is good. The commercial nature of the film to appeal to the largest number of people by selling them emotions such as laughter, fear, violence, love, sex, etc. attests to the dimension of these issues in Nigerian films. The film needs these issues to perform its functional values as communicator, socializer and culture transmitter.

1.3.2 PIRACY

The issue of piracy has bedevilled the film industry in Nigeria for a very long period. Films by the Nigerian producers in general and the Yorùbá film producers in particular have been appropriated and reproduced by pirates without authority for their own profit. For instance, Moses Oláiyá Adéjùmọ (Baba Sàlá) revealed in an interview that he nearly committed suicide when his film *Orun Mo'oru* was pirated in 1988 at a time he had a balance of N500,000 (Five hundred thousand naira) to pay the bank out of a total loan of N1,000,000 (One million naira) he secured for the film project.⁶

To stem this tide and unauthorised rentage of their works to the public, the Association of Movie Producers (AMP) recently launched a battle against priates on the one hand and the video club owners on the other. To this end, the body met with the Video Club Owners Association of Nigeria (VCOAN), the Nigerian Film and Video Censors Board (NFVCB) and the Nigeria Copyright Commission (NCC) to discuss how to solve the issue of piracy.

The AMP in its argument noted that:

The vibrancy of the Nigerian movies market is largely affected by inadequate or weak marketing outlet. At an average of a movie released per week, the only known market is through outright sale via marketers concentrated in Idumota and Onitsha, leading to a glut and holding up many unfinished works from release. There is also the problem of piracy by video clubs.

(The Guardian July 16, 1998, p.13)

With this scenario, the body in their proposal thought of integrating the video club operators into the mainstream of the industry by entering into an agreement with them. The AMP propounds that the right of the video club operators to hire out the works of producers will only be through the sale of 'territorial rights' in line with the video club territories as structured by the body.

Under this arrangement, the video club operator is expected to buy his or her territorial right through a registration fee payable to the AMP, and a yearly video hiring right paid annually to the producer of the film he is interested in hiring out to people within his or her assigned

area. The video club operator after this registration, will be the only one recognized as having the right to hire out the movie in question directly to the public or sub-let to other smaller video clubs within his assigned or designated territory. It will also be the responsibility of the video club operator granted this right to guard against any probable infringement on his or her assigned territory by other operators.

The fee payable by the video operator as an annual hiring right, according to the AMP, will be agreed on between the operators and the producers. It will be subjected to an annual review. This proposal made it the responsibility of the operator to devise ways and means of recouping the amount that must have been paid through an effective hiring out of the movie to the public or sub-letting to smaller video clubs.

For effective patronage, the producer under this arrangement will be required to advertise the video clubs where his works could be hired while printing the posters and bills of his film. The producer may also resort to using the electronic media for publicity.

Any video club operator granted this right, according to the proposal, will receive over 10 master tapes of the film with the inscription 'video club operator' from the producer. According to the terms, it is only these tapes that are to be hired. In a situation where the operator asked for more, he will be made to pay for them.

The sole responsibility of fixing the maximum amount each producer must charge, the proposal says, will be that of the AMP. For the purpose of designated territory, each local government in Lagos State (where there is a high concentration of producers and video club operators) is considered as a video club designated territory, while all other states of the federation including Abuja, the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) will constitute a single territory.

At a tripartite meeting of the AMP, VCOAN and the ANTP in December, 1998, the VCOAN agreed to some of the issues raised in the proposal and rejected others. Under the proposed arrangement, the association agreed that its members will rent or hire duly certified copies from the producers for hire by the public. To ensure compliance, it directed all its state chapters to enforce this law through their various

Enforcement and Compliance Committee. All operators of video shops nationwide were urged to register with the association for licence. For effective implementation, the VCOAN in the communique further directed the AMP and ANTP among other things to ensure that :

- a. producers, marketers and video club operators work as a team with honest intentions.
- b. each of the three relevant bodies plays its vital roles to ensure the development of the film industry.
- c. for mass appeal, producers should ensure that their films have quality scripts, sound recording and good packaging in quality tapes
- d. new films should first be exhibited in cinema houses for one month, released to video clubs for one month before sending them to the open market.

For smooth operation, the association also set up various committees with assigned roles. The various committees with their roles include the following :

- a) The Rental, Procurement and Distribution Committee to negotiate, procure rental video copies and distribute nationwide to registered members of the association.
- b) The Membership Development, Enforcement and Compliance Committee to embark on membership drive, education and enforcement of orders
- c) The Disciplinary Committee to apply disciplinary measures and deal with defaulters within the registered members of the association.

When the Copyright (Video Rental) Regulations of 7 September, 1999 were promulgated by the Nigerian Copyright Commission (NCC), it took into consideration some of the proposals of the AMP enumerated above. The following are the contents of the regulation :

- a) all persons engaged in the business of rental, leasing, hiring, loaning or otherwise distributing cinematography works, to the public for commercial purposes shall apply, in the prescribed forms, to the Nigerian

Copyright Commission for accreditation to carry on such business.

- b) notwithstanding anything in these regulations to the contrary, no person shall be so accredited unless he has complied with the National Film and Video Censors Board Decree and all other requirements as may be prescribed by law.
- c) upon being accredited, a rental outlet shall be given a certificate of accreditation by the Nigerian Copyright Commission and such accreditation shall be renewable annually. The Commission shall maintain a register of all outlets approved and accredited under these regulations to carry on the business of video rental.
- d) every accredited rental outlet shall keep such books and make periodic returns as may be required and in the manner prescribed by the Nigerian Copyright Commission.

- e) every copyright owner shall make available to the accredited rental outlets specially packaged copies of his cinematography film in library jackets or any other format as may be prescribed by the Commission to be designated as rental copies for the purpose of licensing the rental outlets to commercially distribute same to the public. No work shall be offered or used for rental except it is in the specially packaged library jacket or any other prescribed format. The Nigerian Copyright Commission may, as it deems necessary, require the use of anti-piracy device in or on copies of works that are intended for rental.
- f) every accredited rental outlet shall make an undertaking not to produce or otherwise engage in any form of copyright infringement or abuses. Failure to honour any undertaking so given may lead to forfeiture of licence.
- g) the fees to be paid in relation to any transaction under these Regulations shall be as prescribed from time to time by the Nigerian Copyright Commission.

- h) 'Cinematography film' in these regulations shall have the same meaning as used in the Copyright Act and includes works in video, electronic or other format.

With these regulations, it is the opinion of the NCC that the accreditation of rental outlets throughout Nigeria will enable it to monitor the activities of the video clubs and curb piracy. But the regulation is silent on how the NCC, which is located in Lagos, will effectively monitor these video clubs that are spread across the nation. Furthermore, the section of the regulation which tries to enforce the rentage of only specially packaged certified copies of video films to the public may be superficial unless there is honest intention between the producers, marketers and video club operators. Many marketers and video club operators in Nigeria as we have observed, are at the present so much involved in pirating films thereby sabotaging the efforts of the producers.

1.3.4 **Distribution/Marketing**

The distribution and marketing procedures of films in Nigeria have been part of the problems affecting the growth of the industry.

Distributors many atimes, do not adhere to agreements and thus cheat the producers. In some situations, only 30% of the gate proceeds (if the film is exhibited) are offered by the distributors to the producers. The producers therefore see this percentage as too narrow a margin for profit and feel that the distributors make victims of them.

In the film industry, many marketers are now encroaching on production⁷. Because they lack the expertise and experience which recognised producers possess, mediocrity has now set in. At another level, some of these marketers embark on the illegal duplication (dubbing) of major films released by producers with the result that they wipe off or reduce the profit which would have accrued to the producers. Some of these marketers after dubbing, even print jackets for these films and sell them. They then turn round to tell the producers that the original ones are not selling.

In order to stop these unethical practices and ensure that its members concentrate on marketing, the Nigerian Video Cassettes Recorders Dealers Association (NVCRDA), which used to be the umbrella body of marketers, on the 8 December, 1998 in Lagos resolved to change its name to the Nigerian Video Marketing Association (NVMA). At the meeting, the association agreed that its duty was to ensure marketing good movies. By this action, the Marketers' Association intended to discourage their much criticised incursion into film production, scriptwriting and directing.

The incursion of marketers into film production and control of the industry probably arose from the fact that most marketers fund film projects. Many producers run to them (marketers) to finance their projects. Consequently, this situation has fuelled the tussle between the producers and the marketers over who should control the industry. The attitude of the marketers has probably been the case of the payer of the piper wanting to dictate the tune.

On the other hand, market watchers have argued in different fora that if the Nigerian film industry must grow, proper understanding and

specialisation of roles were desirable. At a forum organised by the Movement for Cultural Awareness(MOCA) in Lagos on 23 July, 1998, participants were of the view that marketers should leave off production and concentrate on market strategies on how to recoup their investments. It was agreed at the forum that for improved film quality, production should be left in the hands of the professionals.

MOCA also observed that some marketers turned producers concentrated on scripts which highlighted premordial rituals, violence, vulgarity and lewdness because they sold. This was so, it reasoned, because many viewers mistook the rituals for Yorùbá culture, and enjoyed pornographic materials. In addition, it was observed by the association that most of the video films were unscripted and where scripts existed, they were pedantic and the dialogue in them was unrealistic and unnatural. MOCA also submitted that language in film had been wilfully corrupted by non-professionals and professionals as well. A re-awakening, a re-direction, according to the association in this regard, would therefore be necessary.

To stem the tide of marketers' encroachment into production, we are of the view that government and banks should provide market-oriented funding for films which internationally is a feature of video production. The entertainment tax on film which government has been collecting over the years should also be enough to start a film fund for the growth of the industry.

1.4. **The Yorùbá Theatre and Film : Continuities and Discontinuities**

By the late 1970's, the Yorùbá theatre practitioners had felt that stage performance was unprofitable because of poor patronage. They considered the film medium which had started to enjoy good patronage from the same audience who used to patronise the theatre as more commercially viable, so they veered into it. Consequently, therefore, the Yorùbá film industry can be described as an extension of its theatre.

But, we may ask ourselves, what advantage does the film medium have over stage performance? First, the film offers the theatre practitioners an alternative to the inhibitions of the stage. Second, the power of the film medium, so greatly increased by technical innovations

and scientific discoveries, opens up new, hitherto unsuspected dimensions of reality which thrill and entice the theatre practitioners. Finally, the fact that the film medium avails the theatre practitioners the opportunity to record their works for posterity and its ubiquitous nature which made it possible for a finished product to be exhibited at the same time in different cinema halls were also great attraction.

Going by the accounts of various scholars such as Adédèjì (1972), Clark (1980), Jéyifo (1984) and Ògúndejì (1988) on the nature of the Yorùbá theatre industry on the one hand, and from our own assessment of the mode of operation of the Yorùbá film industry on the other, we have observed that while some administrative practices have been transferred by the theatre practitioners into the film medium, some have also been discontinued owing to the demands in the practice of the film medium. These various modes of operation that are adapted or discontinued in the film medium will now be highlighted.

1.4.1. Administration and Artistic Direction

The prevalent tradition in the Yoruba theatre practice according to Jeyifo (1984 :87) was that the organisational structure of the theatre companies was shaped to give absolute powers to the leader-founder of the troupe. All issues concerning administration, finance and management were the prerogative of the leader-founder. He may employ, seek, fix remuneration as they were most expedient to him.

One of the problems faced by the leader-founders of the theatre companies was how to stabilise the troupe and retain its members, as poor remuneration, often made members of these troupes to drift into other professions or occupations. Many of the theatre companies were unviable production outfits which most times found it difficult to meet the welfare requirements of their members. The members therefore resorted to other trades or took up acting on part-time basis.

Unlike in the theatre days, where the artistic direction of production and administration were completely dominated by the leader-founder, there is devolution of power and authority in the film industry. Though, today many of the leader-founders are still film

producers, there are other offices which are handled by professionals employed on *ad hoc* basis. These include the director, the art director, production manager, continuity, cameraman, floor mixer to mention a few. Professionalism in the film has also seriously suppressed the idea of giving lead roles to the leader-founder. He may only be assigned this role where his talents and capabilities are suitable. Where this is not so, the director can invite another actor to act that role.

One detrimental factor to film production which the theatre practitioners have transferred to the medium from the stage is that majority of their productions are still basically unscripted.⁸ They remain, by and large, improvised plays whose dialogues are still made up by the actors during production. The few scripted ones are largely adaptations from Yorùbá literary texts, like *Kòṣeégbé* and *Ó Le Kú I & II* which are adaptations of Akinwùmí Ìsòlá's play and novel respectively. The script is crucial for production because it supplies the words the actors need and also provide elaborate stage directions.

1.4.2 Recruitment of Female Artistes

One of the difficulties faced by the theatre companies was the recruitment of female artistes. The prevailing general opinion about female artistes at the period, was that they were 'wayward'. Cultural bigotry or prejudices prevented women from pursuing career opportunities on stage. The culture only assigned domestic roles to them. These considerations were the major causes of the dearth of female artistes. To solve this problem therefore, the leader-founders resorted to marrying as many of their female artistes as they could afford.

Through a new orientation on the perception of the role of women in national development, women are now found in professions that they were hardly found before. A lot of women are now involved in film acting. They include Péjú Ògúnmọ́lá, Ìyábò Ògúnṣọ́lá, Rachael Oniga, Monsurat Omídinà among others.

1.4.3 Professionalism and Fraternisation

Jeyifo (1984) and Ògúndèjì (1988) have described professional theatre groups and actors as those who lived solely on theatre. In other words, it is these scholars' contention that such groups or actors do not practise other professions than theatre. Ògúndèjì further observed that apart from the criterion given above, other factors such as intensive training, high skill and institutionalisation determine professionalism. Perhaps, Ògúndèjì's criteria in assessing the operation of the theatre companies might lead us to ask whether the Yorùbá actors in the theatre groups were really professionals?

It is our belief that professionalism is quite different from taking up a profession. A profession, to our own understanding, is not professionalized until it is institutionalised and its practice standardised. Before the advent of the film medium, there was no legislation guiding the practice of the theatre profession. What existed was enterprise where the troupe leaders are pre-eminent. The artistic direction, finance and the general administration of the group rested solely on the

troupe leaders. Where they were challenged, the expulsion of such 'recalcitrant' members at times was sure.

The Association of Nigerian Theatre Practitioners (ANTP) to which most of these troupes belong did not come into existence until the late '70's. Initially when it came, it failed to adequately address issues such as conventions and techniques of theatre practice, organisation, welfare and legislation which are issues that are crucial for the professionalization of the theatre practice.

The emergence of the film has obviously transformed the image of the Yorùbá theatre practitioners. There exists today a pervasive pride among the actors of the theatre movement. This was achieved through several factors.

First, acting for film in Nigeria is highly professionalized. Various supervisory bodies exist for regulating acting for film. Such bodies include the Association of Movie producers (AMP) and the Association of Nigerian Theatre Practitioners (ANTP). Secondly, the considerable commercial success of the film has shot up the remuneration of actors. Actors can now negotiate their earnings based on their roles in

productions. A lead role in a film can fetch an actor as much as N100,000 or more. Nowadays, there is indeed self and job satisfaction among actors. This was lacking during the theatre era. Some of the actors now display affluence with their visible lifestyle reflecting comfort. Examples of these actors include Jídé Kòsókó, Báýḡ Sàlámi (Ọga Bello), Muyideen Arómírẹ́ (Àlàdé), Léré Páimọ, Fẹmi Adéyẹmọ, etc.

One other vital feature of the film practice which was not maximally utilised during the theatre era is fraternisation. Cooperation exists today among the theatre artists that make up the film production outfits. Actors from other groups are now invited to feature in the production of others. The large cast that is needed for film production has really helped in stabilizing this practice as no group is self-sufficient in the area of personnel needed for any major production.

1.4.4 The Yoruba Audience

In Nigeria, the film, like the theatre, is so prominent among the Yorùbá today as a form of entertainment. Ìsọlá (1981 : 400) for instance has noted that the Yorùbá people are great theatre goers.

Their flair for the stage, according to him, allows about a hundred theatre groups to thrive among them. Jeyifo (1984 :13) corroborating Ìṣṣòlá gives reasons for the commercial viability of the Yorùbá theatre among the Yorùbá:

Demographically, the existence of about twelve million speakers of the language and their being concentrated in one of the most urbanised areas of Africa is a massively important factor for the commercial viability of the Yorùbá theatre.

The Yorùbá audience has loyally followed the Yorùbá theatre practitioners from the stage to the film. According to Ekwuazi (1987 :80), the audience which patronized the theatre primarily for its visual effects has now shifted to the film. The element of reality achieved through the film won for it a large audience who loved the novelty of seeing real things in motion.

Adélékè (1995 :75-9) also observes that the film has become the most popular medium of performance. Writing on the typology of the film audience, he identifies three types of film audience among the

Yorùbá, namely : the lay audience, the average audience and the super-audience. Giving the characteristics of each class, he observes that the lay audience has 'simple linguistic knowledge and can only grasp the surface of the linguistic utterance'. The average audience, according to Adéléké 'has a good knowledge of the language, and can differentiate between a good film and a bad one' while the super-audience as a result of 'its adroitness in linguistic experience can critically appraise the story of the play'.

From Adéléké's observation, we can infer that the Yorùbá audience is not monolithic. The three types of audience above have been identified based on their level of literacy or linguistic competence. But in spite of this literacy difference between these three classes, one can say with confidence that the Yorùbá film audience in general appreciate the aesthetic appeal and entertainment value of the Yorùbá film. This is the reason why they patronise the medium in their thousands.

1.5 The Yorùbá Film Producer/Director

We have identified three categories of Yorùbá film producers. They are : first, those who came to the film via the theatre; second, those who are professionals in film production and have no stage connection and third, the film enthusiasts. While members of the first group have troupes with which they produce their films, members of the two other groups recruit their personnel on an *ad hoc* basis because they do not have standing troupes. Producers in the second category produce best quality films. This is so because these producers have received training in film production. Their works manifest a more nuanced awareness of the medium's mode of signification (Ekwuazi 1987 :30). Qlá Balógun, Àlàbi Hundenyin and Túndé Kèláni best represent this group.

The Producers who belong to the first category namely those who have come through the theatre include Hubert Ogunde, Moses Qlályá Adéjùmò (Baba Sàlá), Oyin Adéjòbí, Adébáyò Sàlámi (Qgá Bellò), Jidé Kòsókò, Léré Páimò (Eḍa) among others. They have adapted some of their successful stage plays for the film.⁹

In the third category are producers who have neither training in film production nor have any stage experience. Rather their love for the medium and the commercial viability of the film have given them the impetus to go into film production. Such producers include Moshood Abíólá (Professor Peller), Şólá Şóbòwálé, Ládùn Ojorá, Fred Aiyegbeni (D'Rovans), etc. Producers in this category finance their productions.

The conventional and primary role of producers is to get fund to finance a film. Sometimes, armed with a good story, he can make contact with a distribution company which when convinced can provide the fund for the film. A writer is usually hired to provide the screenplay paying attention to the structure of the story. The screenplay is the most important item in film making. Film directors believe that it is very difficult to make a bad film out of a good script and impossible to make a good film out of a bad script. When the screenplay has been finally approved by the distribution company, the producer is then asked to submit a budget.

Many factors are taken into account by producers in preparing a film budget. The most important factor is the making of a film schedule. Issues considered in preparing this schedule include the following : how much the lead actors will cost and how to condense the number of weeks to shoot their parts (producers save money by engaging the actors for the shortest possible time); what location will be needed; in what order will the story be shot.

Film schedules are made in consultation with the director and production manager who usually help in breaking down the shooting plan into pre-production, production and post-production stages. The producer also makes his budget for the following personnel : the camera operator, the lighting cameraman, the continuity personnel, the sound crew or mixer, the editing staff and the wardrobe mistress. Allowances also have to be made in the budget for a music composer, rental of props, film and laboratory charges for shooting and editing equipment, special effects, power consumption, location allowances, travel and transport and other facilities.

In terms of technical and literary experience, the director has greater authority and control over production than the producer. The director is responsible for casting, filming and supervising the editing of the film to make sure the film conveys the ideas which he has in mind. On the other hand, however, the producer finds the story, works with the writer on the screenplay, obtains the actors, chooses the director and gets the finance.

In the Yorùbá film industry, there are usually disagreements between the producers and the directors. Quite often producers who belong to the category of those who came to the film through the theatre often disagree with the directors because they fail to respect the division of function between them. Producers who look for fund for the production of the film many atimes try to impose their views on the directors.¹⁰ In such a situation, the directors complain that they are not given a free hand to perform their functions. Contrary to the usual practice in film-making, Yorùba producers nowadays double as directors. Where this is not so, they double as actors. The result of which has not favoured quality production.

In this chapter, we have discussed the developmental stages of the Nigerian video film industry in general and the Yorùba video film industry in particular. We have also provided an insight into the nature of the Yorùba video film industry which to a large extent sprang up from a virile theatre tradition. The Yorùbá theatre, as we have observed, prepared the ground for the emergence of the Yorùba film. In the next chapter, however, we shall go ahead to discuss the theoretical framework for this work which will form the pivot of our analysis of the aesthetics of the Yorùba video film production in the subsequent chapters.

NOTES

1. In 1987, Hubert Ogunde in an interview revealed to me that the post-production of *Àyànmọ* cost him about N4.5m which was a huge amount at that time
2. See *This Day* Vol.4, April 11, 1998 p.19.
3. A discussion on the Yorùbá theatre and film is done in 1.2.
4. When the film was first previewed, a 'Special Committee Against the Defamation of Islam comprising the 'Muslim Students' Society' and 'Women in Purdah' expresses its dissatisfaction over the title of the film and most especially its portrayal of women in purdah which it claims is embarrassing and may discourage young ladies from entering into it. Consequently, the NFVCB asked the producer to change the title of the film.
5. See *The Guardian* 16 January, 1997 p 32.
6. Moses Qlâiya Adéjùmọ (Baba Sàlá) revealed this to me in an interview at Ibadan on 5 February, 1988.
7. Some marketers now finance production of the video film and also market them. These marketers are concentrated in Onitsha and Lagos. They include the Infinity Merchants Limited, NEK Ventures and Gaboski Ventures. These former marketing companies have

now metamorphosed into video production outfits adopting names such as Infinity Merchant Films, NEK Video Film and Gaboski Film respectively.

8. This is my own observation after visits to some film locations.
9. Oyin Adéjòbí for instance adapted *Èkùró Qlójà* and *Orogún Adédigba* which were stage plays initially for film. Hubert Ògúnde also adapted *Aiyé* and *Jáiyésimi* for film.
10. Balógun (1987:83) also reported that Moses Qláiyá Adéjùmò (Baba Sàlá) decided to forego Qlá Balógun's directorial expertise because of disagreement and decided to direct and produce his second film, *Ààrẹ Àgbayé* which has technical shortcomings.

CHAPTER TWO

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND: ISSUES IN THE AESTHETIC AND SEMIOTIC THEORIES

2.0 INTRODUCTION

Two theories are employed for this study. They are: the Aesthetic and the Semiotic theories. The two theories are adopted and / or adapted for the following reasons:

- a. aesthetics as a theory, is relevant to various arts such as the literary, plastic and the visual. The video as a presentational art, also incorporates these other arts that we have mentioned above. Hence, the relevance of the application of the aesthetic theory to it.
- b. any analysis of the aesthetic inventiveness of the film-makers is affected not only by the aggregate of new options of expression which are provided the film makers through innovation in technology (technical processes) but also by how meaning is derived from film.
- c. since the content of the video film is communicated by a combination of several systems of signs (words, gestures, costumes, lighting, sound

etc), it follows that its analysis is amenable to semiotic study. The semiotic theory is therefore applied in order to be able to see the literary and technical components of the Yorùbá video film as signs. With this theory, the interstructural relations between these signs are investigated.

- d. Semioticians such as Ferdinand De Saussure, Charles Pierce, Roland Barthes, Umberto Eco among others, by and large, agree that the boundary of semiotics is coterminous with that of aesthetics among other disciplines. Terence Hawkes (1977 :124) corroborates :

The field of semiotics is of course enormous, ranging from the study of the communicative behaviour of animals (zoosemiotics) to the analysis of such signifying systems as human body communication (kinesics and proxemics), olfactory signs (the 'code of scent'), aesthetic theory and rhetoric.

For these reasons, therefore, and in order to achieve intensity of treatment and clarity of focus, the semiotic and the aesthetic theories have been found invaluable for this work.

2.1 What Is Aesthetics?

The word 'aesthetics' is derived from the Greek word *aesthesis*, meaning perception. It was introduced by the 18th century German philosopher, Alexander Baumgarten to denote what he conceived as the realm of poetry, a realm of concrete knowledge in which content is communicated in sensory form. The term was subsequently applied to the philosophical study of all the arts and manifestation of natural beauty. Aesthetics is therefore, conceived with understanding beauty, particularly as it is manifested in art, and with its evaluation.

In the nineteenth century, the aesthetic theory came under serious criticism. Gwilt, for instance, referred to the theory as 'a silly pedantic term' and 'one of the useless additions to nomenclature in the arts' (Saw and Osborne 1960 :8). Hamilton admitted his own preference for the word *apolaustic* from the Greek word *apolauein*, that is, to enjoy (Charlton 1972 :5). His preference for this term was based on the fact that emphasis had switched from the cognitive aspect of appreciation to the emotional which he assumed to be a sufficient criterion of beauty.

In the second half of the nineteenth century, the word 'aesthetics' came to be associated with the extravagant affectations and artistic dandyism

which were cultivated under the influence of the French art for art's sake doctrines and by the end of the century, it had ceased to be a merely technical term in philosophy and was finally adopted into the 'general' language. Scholars now relate artistic with aesthetics by concluding that 'to be truly artistic, a work must also be aesthetic. In this vein, the word 'beautiful' became subordinate to 'aesthetics'.

Aesthetics has its roots in nearly all the disciplines-philosophy, psychology, linguistics, arts, sociology, architecture, theology, culture, etc. This is why its study and application are complex as a result of its limitless boundary coupled with its consideration of attitude, beliefs, prejudices and human experiences. Furthermore, the concept of 'good' and 'beauty' which are the concern of aesthetics are not exactly the same in all places at all times (Faniola 1990 :206). They vary from one race to another and from one culture to another.

For the purpose of this work, however, we shall give enough consideration to the various contributions of aesthetics to the arts employing where necessary its manifestation in other disciplines where they are crucial for our discourse.

2.1.1 The Aesthetics of Art

Art here connotes two related but different concepts which include the literary and the visual (performance/film). Music which is another category of art is subsumed under these two categories.¹ Any meaningful discussion of the aesthetics of the Yorùbá video film, we presume, must take into consideration these concepts of art which are indispensable for the medium. For clarity of focus, our discussion of the aesthetics of art shall therefore be done under these two categories of art.

Naturally, any work that is regarded as art subsumes a recognition of its aesthetic undercurrent. Oḃáfẹ́mi (1994 :30) posits some criteria for aesthetic evaluation by asking a number of questions which he considers crucial for judgement on a literary work :

What is the writer's intention? How successfully has he conveyed this intention? What impact has the literary piece made? What atmosphere does it convey? Any extra-textual information? What are the text's shortcomings and strengths?

Ngara (1982 : 29) also describes a good literary work as :

A synthesis of reality, subject matter, theme, views and ideas on the one hand, and narrative structure, character and linguistic format on the other.

A consideration of the views of Obafehinmi and Ngara above suggests that the principle of aesthetics is beyond the 'beautiful' or the 'visual' and textual information. Instinctive behaviour and response, temperamental or physiological peculiarity, idiosyncratic tendencies, sociolinguistic factors or ideological perspectives and cultural background are some of the 'extra-textual' factors that are present in aesthetic evaluation.

Psychological aesthetics for instance, is centred on knowing what is in a work of art that releases or evokes the aesthetic response. An interesting argument about what men want, what they like to get and what they try to avoid has been put forward by psychologists who have described with some detail and precision the perceptual content of what they call 'releaser mechanisms in instinctive behaviour' (Mace 1962 :8). Psychologists believe that it is the 'sign stimulus' that releases an instinctive response. Sometimes, the releasing precept, they observed, has an innate basis. For instance, they

argued that the young chick is innately predisposed to follow the hen. Related to the 'releasing precept' is what they referred to as the 'goal precept' which informs the organism when it has got what it needs or wants.

Also, Marxists like Eagleton and Mukarovsky in their discussions of 'aesthetic value' have subordinated literature to the society. They have established what they refer to as 'the social or extra-literary bearings of art and literature'. The argument of these Marxists concern what they call the 'aesthetic function in a work of art which they think has an 'ever-shifting boundary' and not a 'water tight category'. For instance Mukarovsky in Selden(1985 :20) further describes this concept by saying that :

The same object can possess several functions : a church may be both a place of worship and a work of art; a stone may be a door-stop, missile, building material, and an object of artistic appreciation. Fashions are especially complex signs and may possess social, political, erotic and aesthetic functions. The same variability of function can be seen in literary products.

In a similar view, Macherey (1970 :50) also states that the study of art must be a dual one. He opines that art is ideological form and an aesthetic process. Eagleton (1976 :166-167) is also of the opinion that 'the histories of

'value' are a sub-sector of the histories of literary-ideological receptive practices'. The literary text, according to Eagleton, is a text for ideology, selected, deemed readable and deciphered by certain ideological-governed conventions of critical receptivity to which the text itself contributes. These conventions which are embedded in culture, education and which represent a conjuncture of 'general' ideological discourses, according to Eagleton, determine the literary aesthetics.

A work of art has some relevance to the human experience which has endangered it. Ideology and social structures in spite of their complexities are reflected in any literary work. Consequently, to endow an object with the dignity of aesthetic value is a social act inseparable from prevailing ideologies. The position of Selden (1985 :21) that the dominant class in any historical era will have an important influence on definitions of art, and where new trends arise will normally wish to incorporate them into its ideological world must have taken into consideration the extra-literary or social bearing of literature which Marxists believe is necessary for the discussion of 'aesthetic value'.

African works of art cannot be divorced from the very peculiar circumstances of their creators and their primary audience. Consequently, it is important to view aesthetic values within the cultural background from which

a work of art emanates rather than employing conventional norms and values. The cultural artistry of the African nation in general and of the Yorùbá society in particular is quite different from that of the West. For instance, while Europeans find aesthetic value in the bawdy (aesthetics of the bawdy), the Yorùbá view it as immoral and therefore absurd. On the other hand, while the seizing of a man by the whirlwind may seem unacceptable to a European, it is admissible in the Yorùbá world view. It may be difficult to understand the aesthetics of a work of art in Yorùbá, for instance, without understanding and appreciating the Yorùbá world view. The particularity and/or peculiarity of the society which produces a work of art should be taken into consideration before passing any aesthetic judgement. This kind of consideration made Charlton(1972 :125) while writing on the particularity and assessing *King Lear* and the Hispano-Suiza to conclude that :

If *Lear* is a good play because it consists of the speeches and actions which make it *Lear*, the 1921 Hispano-Suiza is a good car because it consists of the structural features which define the 1921 Hispano-Suiza.

Writing on the decolonization of the Nigerian film also, Olúṣolá in Ekwuazi (1987 :37) takes into consideration the peculiarities of culture as an important factor for aesthetic evaluation :

In some cultures, it is considered sincere and trustworthy when a person looks you right in the eyes. In other culture it is rude and impertinent to 'catch somebody's eye' during conversation. In some cultures, people express themselves non-verbally by the mimicry of the face. In others, people talk with their body.... Such circumstances are of striking relevance to the film language in those cultures.

To distil an aesthetic based primarily on the Yorùbá culture, it is our belief that rather than make foreign standards our determining factor, aestheticism should be domesticated. Foreign standard should only serve as valuable guides where relevant.

The Yorùbá concept of 'aesthetics' is discernible from the various words, phrases and other expressions that are used in describing 'the beautiful: Adépégba (1996) is an indepth study of the concept of art among the Yorùbá. He observes that 'unlike other African Languages which are said to have had no separate word for 'beauty' and 'being good', Yorùbá has *ewá*

which specifically means 'beauty' and *dídára* which means 'being good' and which may be used interchangeably with *ẹwá* (beauty)'. Other Yorùbá words that are synonymous with the concept of aesthetics according to Adépegba include *sísunwọ̀n* which is also interchangeably used for 'beauty' and 'being good' and when used for 'goodness' connotes some added value; *ọ̀nà* is also a word for art and craft and can also be used for 'designs' patterns or 'forms'; *àrà* is also the word for creativity. These synonyms of 'beauty' are suggestive of the view that the Yorùbá are certainly one of the most prolific art-producers in the world. Her various arts are 'highly artistic and skilfully produced to meet the people's day-to-day aesthetic canons'. (Adepegba 1996 :73).

Perhaps, the views of the Yorùbá about the aesthetically beautiful are encapsulated in their perception of 'a beautiful woman' and the *gẹ̀lẹ̀dẹ̀* dance in the following saying respectively:

- i. B́ obìnrin bá dára tán, wọ̀n a digi oko, wọ̀n a ní ó sunwọ̀n bí ère

When a woman is extremely beautiful she becomes a piece of wood from the forest. People say she is as beautiful as a carved image.

(ii) Ojú tó rí gèlèdè ó rí òpín ìran

The eye that has witnessed the *gèlèdè* dance has seen
the acme of all spectacles

gèlèdè dance is devoted to the adoration of the *àjé* (witches) in order to achieve harmony in a Yorùbá society which harbours the supernatural beings. The intricate dance and music (performance) of *gèlèdè*, the beautiful dress of its artist and the masques are intended to be admired or appreciated. The idealisation of forms of both the *gèlèdè* masque and a carved image is motivated by the desire of the Yoruba for beauty.

The concept of 'originality as creativity' is crucial for the aesthetic appraisal of any work of art. It suggests a more viable account of art appreciation and also tends to justify its contribution to aesthetic value.

For the production of a creative work, the author proceeds from a myriad of possibilities to a very few, perhaps only one. When he draws or keeps one line some of these possibilities are eliminated. A producer who aspires to be original operates within a narrower range of possibilities. The

dynamism of this sort of development in art therefore constitutes a problem for the aspiring artist or producer. In response to this pressure, his work may be in part derivative, but also in some way original. The way in which he successfully meets the challenge to produce unique work constitutes part of his creativity.

Hoaglund (1976: 52) argues that artists who produce great works make art difficult for the generation of artists that succeed them. He further observes that 'it is not mere chance that the number of composers who wrote symphonies by the dozen fell drastically after Beethoven'. Beethoven, he concludes, must have written masterpiece symphonies that make it difficult for his followers to either surpass him or at least meet his standard. Consequently, Hoaglund views derivation as an important aspect of creativity.

No adequate aesthetics can ignore either derivative creativity or original creativity and no adequate account of these types of creativity can ignore dynamic development in art. An aspect of creativity that is crucial for aesthetic value is that which advances beyond existing development of style. Perhaps, in the Yorùbá film industry, this view makes producers like Túndé Kelani, Túndé Alabi-Húndenyin, Olá Balógun among others stand out as great producers. The dynamic development of the style of these producers brings

out their unique aesthetic qualities and represent a departure from those of their predecessors and contemporaries. There is no doubt that the creativity of an artist or producer should be predicated on the aesthetic qualities and uniqueness of one or more of his works. The aesthetic value of the works of these producers is based on our perception and evaluation of some of their productions. (see chapter 4).

For creativity in film production, technology is indispensable. Film, being a complex medium, requires technical innovations to enhance recording, shooting and revealing abilities. Technical innovations and scientific discoveries open up for film new, hitherto unsuspected dimension of reality – capturing objects from unusual angles or combining phenomena never before seen together. All these are tapped by producers to enhance their creativity and originality.

Critics like Theodore Green, S. Alexander, Katherine Gilbert and B. Jessup have argued that, apart from the strictly aesthetic standard (which we have discussed above) which makes a work of art beautiful, there is also the need for important content which is additionally needed for greatness beyond excellence. In this vein, these critics identify the 'serious content' view as the

traditional or orthodox view of great art. Greene (1940 :375-6) writing on the issue of greatness in art submits that :

Two compositions may be similar in artistic quality or degree of perfection... but the content of one may be slight, that of the other, rich in human import.... The standard of artistic perfection is primarily aesthetic or infra-philosophic, while the standard of truth and greatness are primarily supra-aesthetic or philosophic in character.

Alexander (1963 :138-9) further corroborates Greene's view by asserting that :

In art there are... two standards : there is the strictly aesthetic standard. Is the work beautiful or not? Has it attained beauty and there is the question : Is it great or small?

He concludes by submitting that there are thus in works of art a scale of beauty and a scale of greatness. Greatness and smallness, he concludes 'depend upon the subject matter'.

Jessup (1962: 26) also maintains that the 'serious content' view has held an unbroken, though not unchallenged or untroubled, ascendancy ever, since Socrates laid down and Plato enlarged and systematised the position that 'that man is a fool who judges the beautiful by any other standard than that of the good'. He (Jessup) further gives an indepth analysis of the distinction between 'good art' and 'great art'. He is of the opinion that the basic assumptions in considering 'great art' a division in the class of 'good art' which the 'serious content' view is trying to express are that :

- i) every work of art is a physical thing, a perceptual object, which is an organisation or composition of sensuous materials.
- ii) relative to artistic creation; the sensuous materials may be either.
 - a. merely sensuous materials, such as pigment, sound, wood, stone, textural appearance or feel etc. or
 - b. meaningful or expressive sensuous material i.e. material which represents, states, suggests or symbolises.

Jessup goes on to explain that of the two kinds of materials, the merely sensuous may be called 'neutral' in the sense that its value in artistic use or intention is purely sensuous, while the 'meaningful' or 'expressive' material is

'human' in the sense that it has come to be, through 'association, convention, likeness, or intention, a reflection, or an icon or a symbol of some interest or value other than the look, the feel or the sound of the physical material itself'. He later submits that artistically, to treat a material neutrally is to keep strictly to its immediate physical qualities, to treat it humanly is to take it in the shapes and meanings which the categories of experience other than the aesthetic have already given it. Jessup interpreted human materials as things rather than masses, actions rather than movements, plans and purposes rather than configurations and patterns.

Walter Pater in Jessup (1962 :28) also distinguishes between 'good' art and 'great' art. He argues that the distinction between great art and good art is not in their form but their matter. A good art, according to him, becomes great if it is further devoted to:

the increase of men's happiness, to the redemption of the oppressed, or the enlargement of our sympathies ... or if it presents truth to ennoble and fortify us.

The foregoing has revealed arguments about what constitute 'good art' and 'great art'. We can deduce that while 'great art' reflects aesthetic standard and human materials such as values, moral rules, symbolic qualification etc, the 'good art' reflects strictly the aesthetic standard.

We think the distinction between 'good art' and 'great art' is pedantic and consequently a problem of nomenclature. 'Goodness' or 'greatness' in the literal sense are complementary. Greatness is goodness *par excellence*. This view is reflected in the way the Yorùbá will describe an object that is extremely good :

Èyí ti lọ wàjù, ó peléke

This is too good, it is great

The synonyms the two terms share such as 'desirable', 'suitable', 'excellent', 'beneficial', 'pleasant', propitious, etc. lend credence to their complementariness. Since they therefore share the same qualities, it is our belief that the characteristics of 'greatness' are those of 'goodness'. The features that make a work of art good are also responsible for its greatness and vice versa. Before a work of art can be adjudged as great, it must have been aesthetically beautiful. Though the 'serious content' is necessary for art,

but it is necessary only because it affords a richer material for aesthetic use than merely neutral material or trivial content. The greatness of art also need not be in terms of the intrinsic value of serious content, but rather in terms of something resulting from its use aesthetically. There should be a meaningful distinction between 'serious content' constituting 'great art' and 'serious content' making for great art. The presence of 'serious content' in a work of art is not enough to adjudge it as great. Rather what should constitute its greatness is the device employed to make the 'serious content' appealing.

2.1.2 Literary Aesthetics

The aesthetic appeal of a literary work is hinged on the author's handling of language, character and the narrative technique.

In a linguistic description of a literary text, the selection of materials to be described is highly related to the interest of the reader or critic (Adébòwálé 1993: 56). Ìṣòlá (1978 :217-8) also explains the problem that a critic who wants to examine a writer's use of language may encounter and suggests a better approach:

The language of any novel is not easy to discuss mainly because there are too many examples to choose from. The best a critic can do, therefore, is to look for those patterns of language use that are peculiar to the work and discuss these. Even then one's approach necessarily has to be selective.

There are some stylistic devices that are prominent while considering the general features of language use in a literary work. These include proverbs, imagery, parallelism, humour, metaphor, and allegory. These features form an integral part of the artist's use of language. The aesthetic appeal of the writer's language determines the writer's power of persuasion. A writer has to keep his audience interested, and one way in which he does so is by using rhetoric. Whatever his technique, the writer's style is evaluated in terms of the appropriateness and effectiveness of his choice of linguistic features.

The language of a character or an author can be an index of easy identification. Olabode (1981:44) argues that such identification:

... may be based on the aggregate frequency of certain linguistic items peculiar to each of them or in the similarity of theme.

Irele (1975 :101) for instance attempts to explain this concept of individuality in Fágúnwà's style. His comments on Fágúnwà use of language which he describes as 'the most striking feature in his (Fágúnwà's) art' reflect the significance of his resourceful exploitation of the Yorùbá language:

He possessed the Yorùbá language to a high degree and employed it with consummate mastery. The tone of his language ... is that of oral narrative. This not only gives to his writing an immediate freshness but, reinforced by the use of imagery, contributes to what Wọlé Şóyinká has called Fágúnwà's 'vivid sense of events'.

The peculiarity of Fágúnwà's style facilitates an easy identification of his works much so that fiction writers who take after him such as. Ògúndélé, Omóyájowó, Fátànmí, etc have been labelled by Ògúnşínà (1976 :128) as 'novelists of the Fágúnwà tradition'. These novelists according to Ògúnşínà 'all draw inspiration from Fágúnwà's success, admire his pattern and consequently, and in varying degrees, adopt it in their writings'.

Similarly, writing on Fálétí's use of language, Ọlátúnjí (1982 :80) identifies 'the frequent use of semantically correspondent words which often occur with a repeated sentence structure, euphemism and historical and

institutional materials' as some of his most striking devices. Fágúnwà's use of these devices in. *Èdà Kò Láròpin*, his earliest work, according to Qlátúnjì adumbrates those of his later poetry.

When we come to the film, language is made up of various codes such as the montage, image, sound, narrative and style. In the film, the concept of language, as we shall also see later, is expanded beyond the spoken or written word. It is made up of the combination of some or all of the codes mentioned above. The sound (dialogue, music or any auditory material) in a film, for instance, is synchronized with the image for the audience to conceptualise the message in the film. While the technical devices are primarily employed for visual effects, the dialogue or speech of the characters are relayed through language.

In the works of the Yorùbá film producers, the concept of individuality in their style also holds true. For instance, while Ogunde's films are largely folkloric, those of Moses Qláiyá Adéjùmò (Baba Sàlá) are comic. The frequency of certain linguistic features, similar thematic considerations and characterization make the identification of their films possible.

The language of *Aiyé*, *Jáiyásimi* and *Áyànmò* by Ogunde is at two levels namely : the cultic and the ordinary. The cultic language is used by *Ọṣẹṣẹtura*, the patriarch and the devotees of Orunmila while the other citizen employ the ordinary language. The language of Moses Ọláiyá Adéjùmò (Baba Sàlá) films such as *Ọrun Móoru*, *Mọṣebólátán*, *Ọbèṣé Gbóná* is essentially comic. Since the purpose of Moses Ọláiyá Adéjùmò's 'slapstick' films is to create humour and keep the audience reeling with laughter, comic elements have become a permanent feature of his language. Some other Yorùbá film producers or artistes have their own peculiarities which their audience enjoy and which they expect in each production.

To get at the meaning of a literary piece, savour its beauty and appreciate its poetics, the critic has to pay attention to the language of the work. The relationship between literature, language and linguistics has been mutually beneficial as the application of linguistic principles in the analysis and the study of literary language illuminates the text. The application and examination of linguistic rules in the analysis of literary language according to Theo Vincent(1990 :139) 'look at language in literature synchronically and use utterances and speech acts as texts'. Persuasive language evokes a more

realistic effect on the audience and determines the aesthetic success of the work.

Stylistics seems to have had less to say about drama and film than about prose and poetry with which it has been principally concerned. It would appear there are reasons why this has been so. A performance (film or drama) exists in two ways – as a literary text and as a spectacle on the stage. The two manifestations are quite different and require different analytical approaches. When stylistics focuses on drama or film, it is invariably concerned with the dramatic text or the screen script respectively which is static and unchanging. The text affords the stylistician the opportunity to turn back the pages of the literary texts to a previous scene for comprehension and detailed analysis of the language of discourse.

On the other hand, the live performance is transient. A speech not properly heard cannot be heard again on that occasion. Though, the introduction of the video film allows us the privilege of reviewing speeches for its content and its delivery, nevertheless from a linguistic perspective it is easier to analyse it as a written text, than as a performance.

The techniques of narrative are also crucial for the aesthetic appraisal of a literary work. A basic interest of narrative technique or narratology lies in

the way the narrator fashions a 'story' into the organized form of a 'plot'. Narrative techniques include in their scope a systematic treatment of plot, characterization, point of view, style, stream of consciousness, flashback, suspense etc. Today, narrative techniques are applicable to all genres that use plots.

Among the basic terms of analysis in the realist aesthetics are plot, character, setting, theme, moral aim and verisimilitude. For realist critics, a novel should have a good construction, starting with a coherent plot. Onega and Landa (1996 :2) submit that :

The realist novel, ... should be a psycho-social study, one that reveals new truths about human feelings and relationships. Such a novel has a theme and is linked to a well-defined moral intention, an authorial stance towards that theme, which is easily identified, whether it is conveyed by direct or indirect means. It is this moral intention that makes realism something more than an attempt at copying nature.

Since the artistic shape of the film surpasses literary narrative techniques, it is therefore necessary to employ its technical properties in distinguishing film

narration from that of fiction. This is what will be our focus in the next section.

2.1.3 Film Aesthetics

Here, we shall reconcile film devices and semiotics for the purposes of aesthetic evaluation of film. We shall therefore focus on the aesthetics of film derived from our consideration of the techniques of film production and semiotics. We shall consider the various film devices, that are integral to film narration and are employed for dramatic effects. Since film also makes use of images and speech for narration, it clearly shows that it is not just a subsection of the literary theory, but rather of a general semiotic theory. Film narrative can therefore also be constructed using an ample of semiotic media such as written or spoken language, visual images, gestures and acting, as well as a combination of these. The roots of film technique draw their very existence and wealth from semiotics.

2.1.3.1 Film Devices

Film devices are those artistic contrivances in film narrative that are employed to achieve a particular effect. These devices are determined or effected through the manipulation of the camera by a photographer who is trained for this specific technical process in film making. To achieve his aim, the photographer also relies on the artistic direction of the film director. Some of these film devices include camera movement, camera angle, sound, superimposition, lighting and editing.

The specific properties of film such as its unique ability through the camera to record as well as reveal visible, or potentially visible, physical reality have been identified by critics of the medium. There was a general notion and agreement that film reproduces nature with a fidelity equal to nature itself. But it is not out of place to ask if the camera reproduces and penetrates nature without distortion—a view to which some film critics object. They argued that film does not exhaust itself in recording reality as the artist may use the medium in shaping given materials. Many photographers have aimed and are aiming at pictures which would delineate beauty instead of merely representing truth. Kracauer (1960 :6) opines that with notable exceptions the 'artist-photographers' follow a tendency which he referred to as

'formative' since it sprang from their urge to compose beautiful pictures rather than to capture nature in the raw. The creativity of these artists, as we observed, invariably manifests itself in photographers that reflect valued styles and preferences.

The view of the artist – photographers is that photography need not be limited to reproduction. They reason that photography is a medium which offers the creative artist as many opportunities as does painting or literature – provided he does not let himself be inhibited by the camera's peculiar affinities but uses every 'dodge', 'trick' and 'conjunction' to elicit beauty from the photographic raw material. Such concern with art led the artist-photographers to deliberately prefer pictorial beauty to camera exploration of the reality for artistic effect.

The controversy between the realists and their artists raged on in the second half of the nineteenth century with no clear cut solution reached. But this controversy rested upon a belief common to both schools of thought – that photographs are copies of nature. Kracauer (1960) had also claimed that though they all accept this common belief, opinions always clash when it comes to appraising the aesthetic significance of reproductions which light itself seemed to have produced. Stale as these notions have become, the two

divergent tendencies from which they draw their strength continue to assert themselves.

Contemporary photographers have been overwhelmed by the power of the film medium, so greatly increased by technical innovations and scientific discoveries, to open up new hitherto unsuspected dimensions of reality. The camera today captures 'objects from unusual angles or combinations of phenomena never before seen together; the fabulous disclosures of high speed, micro- and macro-photography; the penetration obtained by means of infrared emulsions and so on. Modern photography has not only considerably enlarged our vision, but, in doing so, has also adjusted it to man's situation in a technological age. The camera has influenced art in that through various techniques, it has called forth our subjective experiences, our personal visions, and the dynamics of our imagination. Andres Feininger in Kracauer (1960 :7) has submitted that 'the goal of film as an art medium is not the achievement of highest possible likeness of the depicted subject, but the creation of an abstract work of art, featuring composition instead of documentation'.

In their desire to highlight the artistic potentialities of the medium, photographers usually draw attention to their selectivity, which, indeed, may

account for films that are suggestive of their personal vision and rich in aesthetic gratification (Kracauer 1960 :8).

So far we have looked at the aesthetic theory and the possibility of its application to the study of film. Now, we want to look at the second theory employed for this work, that is, semiotics.

2.1.4. Semiotics

Semiotics or semiology has been defined as 'the science of signs'. It is a science dedicated to the study of the production of meaning in the society (Eliot 1980 :1). In the words of Silverman (1983 :3) semiotics :

involves the study of signification, but signification cannot be isolated from the human subject who uses it and is defined by means of it, or from the cultural system which generates it.

Semiotics studies all cultural processes of communication made possible by a basic system of signification and it can therefore be said to be concerned with the process of signification and communication.

The process of communication and the system of signification are dialectically related (Ògúndèjì 1988 :10). Every work of art has a communicative function. This is also true of the signifiatory process. In the visual art (film or theatre), the communicative and signifiatory processes are more complex as there is multiplicity of signs in them. Dialogue (word) is only one of the signifying elements in the representational arts. The content of a theatrical or film production is communicated through the simultaneous exploitation of several systems of signs (words, gestures, costumes, decor, lighting, music, sound effect, etc.).

The privileged status enjoyed by language within the semiotic theory has provoked some film critics to stress the image rather than the sound track, and to locate cinematic syntax at the level of shot-to-shot relationship instead of at the level of dialogue. The greatest value of semiotics according to Silverman (1983 :5) is the scheme it has given us for understanding the relationship between visual and linguistic signification, and the equilibrium which the scheme establishes between the two registers.

2.1.4.1 **Signification**

Signification can best be described as the process of sign formation. In signification, the sign is a relational entity, a composite of two parts that

signify not only through those features that make each of them slightly different from any other two parts, but their association with each other (Silverman 1983 :6). Ferdinand De Saussure names these two parts of the sign as the 'signifier' and the 'signified'.⁴ While 'signifier' refers to a meaningful form, 'signified' designates the concept which that form evokes.

Within the linguistic system, Saussure refers to the 'sound-image' as the signifier, that is the image of one of these sounds which we shape within our minds when we think, whereas the signified according to him would be the meaning which that sound image generates. Such conventional relationship between the 'signifier' and the 'signified' is said to be 'arbitrary' because the connection between them is 'unmotivated'.

But Ògúndèjì (1988 :29) has argued that the idea of 'motivated' or 'unarbitrary' sign on the one hand and 'unmotivated' or 'arbitrary' on the other, or their respective conventions as the case may be, are not mutually exclusive though they seem to be. Citing Giraud (1971 :27), Ògúndèjì argues that the so-called unmotivated signs, in some cases, are originally motivated. They become unmotivated as their motivation must have been lost in history. (See P. 82 – 83).

Saussure refers to the relationship which a sign entertains with the other signs that surround it within a concrete signifying instance as 'syntagmatic'.

Though, in discourse, the various words within a sentence enjoy a syntagmatic relationship with each other, as do the shots in a film, a sign's value is determined not only by its syntagmatic association but also by its paradigmatic relationship with others. Reiterating this view Silverman (1983 :11) also opines that the value of a sign :

... depends in part on those features that distinguish it from the other signs within its system, particularly those it most resembles, and in part on those features that distinguish it from the other signs adjacent to it in discourse.

Pierce's semiotic scheme differs from that of Saussure because of 'its attentiveness to the referent, and its relevance to two interlocking triads'.⁵ The proposal of Pierce shows a complex classification of signs in terms of the different relationship manifested between 'signans/signifier' and 'signatum/signified' (Hawkes 1977 :126). According to Pierce, a sign is something which stands to somebody for something in some respect or capacity; it is anything which determines something else (its interpretant) to refer to an object to which itself refers (its object); it stands for something (its object); it stands for something to somebody (its interpretant) and finally it stands for something to somebody in some respect (its ground). These terms

refer to the means by which the sign signifies and the relationship between them determines the precise nature of the process of semiotics.

According to Pierce in Hawkes (1977 :127), the relationship between the object, sign, and ground brings forth three kinds of 'triadic' structures in whose terms the fourth element, the interpretant, perceives. These structures include:

- a. triadic relations of comparison or logical possibilities based on the kind of sign.
- b. triadic relations of performance involving actual entities in the real world, based on the kind of ground.
- c. triadic relations of thought based on the kind of object.

Because of its centrality to our experience of the real world and for simplicity's sake, most interpreters of Pierce's scheme have so far tended to limit their attention to the application of his second triadic relationship. This triadic relationship seems to be the one which human consciousness can interpret and accommodate and it consists of three signification methods namely the iconic signification, indexical signification and the symbolic signification.

2.1.4.1.1 Iconic Signification

The iconic sign resembles its conceptual object in certain ways. According to Hawkes (1977 :128), it manifests a similarity or fitness of resemblance proposed by the sign to be acknowledged by the receiver. Ògúndèjì (1988 :31) defines an icon as :

... a sign which refers to the object that it denotes merely by virtue of characters of its own and which it possesses... Anything whatever, be it quality, existent individual or law, is an icon of anything, in so far as it is like that thing and used as a sign of it.

Thus, photographs, paintings, sculptures, and film images are iconic. The film image has an iconic relationship with its subject. Here, the relationship between the signifier and the signified is direct and apparent.

2.1.4.1.2 Indexical Signification

The indexical sign is defined by Pierce as:

a real thing or fact which is a sign of its object by virtue of being connected with it as a matter of

fact and by also forcibly intruding upon the mind, quite regardless of its being interpreted as a sign (Silverman 1983 :19).

According to Ògúndèjì (1988 :35), indexicalization is central in the signification process because the very nature of the signifier in referring to the signified is indexical in all significations. Hawkes (1977 :129) gives some instance of indexical sign : a knock on the door is an index of someone's presence, and the sound of a car's horn is a sign of the car's presence. Smoke is an index of fire.

In films, 'familiar noises' are indexical. Though they may be used synchronically with the images which accompany them, their sources are still known to us. Examples of familiar noises include the bark of a dog, the ululation of birds, the chimes of the church bell, etc. 'Familiar noises' in films call forth inner images of its source.

In the Yorùbá society, the presence of an *oba's ọpá àṣẹ* (the king's staff of authority) at a social ceremony is an index of the *oba's* consent to the activities (Ògúndèjì 1988 :36). Other domains where indexical signification operates are in symptoms and in the theatrical and dramatic arts. Lyons quoted in Ògúndèjì (1988: 36) opines that the states or situations indicated by

symptoms can be 'an emotional state (fear, anger, sexual arousal, etc.), a state of health, a state of intoxication or whatever will be described as symptomatic of that state'. In the theatrical and dramatic arts, indexical sign can be seen in the linear structures, especially the plot, which is no doubt based on causality and sequentiality.

2.1.4.1.3 Symbolic Signification

The symbol designates a sign whose relation to its conceptual object is entirely arbitrary (unmotivated). A symbol is defined as:

a sign which refers to the object that it denotes by virtue of a law, usually an association of general ideas, which operates to cause the symbol to be interpreted as referring to that object (Silverman 1983 :20).

In symbolic signification, the major systematic manifestation of signs occurs in language. The linguistic sign is a pertinent example of unmotivated (arbitrary) signification. For instance, the utterance of the word 'tree' is a symbol of the tree because there is no inherent, necessary 'tree-like' quality in the signifier. The relationship of the signifier to an actual tree therefore

'remains fundamentally arbitrary sustained only by the structure of the language in which it occurs' (Hawkes 1977:129).

As pointed out earlier, Ògúndèjì (1988:37) has argued that most of the signs usually regarded as unmotivated and conventional might have originally been motivated in history or have a kind of indirect and hidden motivation that can only be contextually explained. For example, he opines that in the Yorùbá *àrokò* sign system, the sending of the *èsúrú* (yellow yam), to a person facing an unpleasant situation is derived from a type of word play signification in Yorùbá rhetoric. 'The syllable /*sú*/ of *èsúrú* which is similar in form to the verb *sú* (to be tired of/exasperated) he says serves as the motivating factor conferring the symbolic meaning of something that can effectuate the meaning *sú* on *èsúrú*. He concludes that the symbolism involved in the above example is metaphorically motivated based on 'certain cultural conventional similarities that are not physically apparent but are logically derived'.

Ògúndèjì's argument above is quite plausible. We have observed that in the Yorùbá society, for instance, hermetic symbols nurse an intimate bond between them (signifier) and their intentions (signified). In this process, the symbolic signs have double references where the first points analogically to the second.

In the Yorùbá world view, the practice of homeopathic and contagious magic involves the use of symbols which are metonymically motivated ('meto-symbolization').⁶ According to Qlátúnjì (1985 :275), in homeopathic magic, an object can transmit some aspects of its nature to other bodies. To back his claim, he gives an example of an iron rod or granite (signifier), because of its hard nature used to make a child's limb stronger (signified) if included in a bath concoction for the child. Honey according to him signifies sweetness. When it does so, honey is the signifier while the sweetness (abundant life) is the signified.⁷ In the film, *Òbúkọ Dúdú*, Adérùpọkò's use of the he-goat to charm Kunle to have sexual intercourse with his stepmother is also symbolically motivated. It is derived from a Yorùbá saying:

'Wérewèrè ní ǐṣ'òbúkọ.'

Lasciviousness is the lot of the he-goat

In contagious magic, however, objects once related to each other retain their connection though they may be separated. This belief accounts for the use of one's clothing item, hair strand and nail paring in charming them.

2.1.4.1.4 The Co-existence of Signs

The three types of signs discussed above at times can co-exist in a hierarchy in which one of them will inevitably have dominance over the other (Hawkes 1977 :129). Thus we can have symbolic icons, iconic symbols, etc. It is the context that usually determines the dominant mode.

Hawkes (1977) in analysing the mode of signification found in a traffic signal, for instance, argues that the traffic signal combines an indexical sign at the same time with a symbolic sign. According to him, while the red light is a symbol of 'danger', it is at the same time an index that the driver should 'stop'. The green light according to Hawkes is binarily opposed to the red in the traffic signalling system. It is a conventional symbol of 'no danger' and an index that the driver can 'move'. In this context, Hawkes concludes, the indexical sign is dominant over the symbolic.

The co-existence of these signs in their hierarchical form can also be found in the semiotic analysis of the film as presented below.

2.1.5 Film Semiotics

While the relation of linguistic signifiers to their signified is primarily conventional, with elements of iconicity and indexicality, the signifiers of the technical devices of film such as camera movement, sound, editing, lighting, etc are characterized by a preponderance of indexical or iconic properties.

Camera movement (panning, tilting, long shot, mid-shot; close-up) is characterised by indexical signifiers. Panning, for instance, is an index of establishing clearly the special relationship of two or more subjects. For instance, in a scene showing a man who is amused by an object or spectacle which draws his attention, the camera will first bring the man into focus before panning to establish his object of amusement. The long shot (LS) is an index of showing a character or an object as part of a general scene. At times, it is used to establish a location. The use of the close-up is indexical in drawing the attention of the audience to any detail of the scene – be it a nuance of facial expression, a significant hand movement or the action of some mechanism. However, when these types of camera movement simulate movement which is depicted within the narrative of the film, they are also iconic.

Sound-track, excluding music, is primarily iconic, simulating the ululation of a bird, the barking of a dog, the horn of a car, the opening and

closing of a door, etc. However, because these sounds quite often alert us to unsuspected or as yet unseen occurrences and objects, they also participate in indexicality.

Film editing supplies indexical signifiers. Editing involves 'cross-cutting from one event to another which coerces the viewer's attention, as do the fade-in, fade-out and dissolve' (Silverman 1983 :23). But when editing focuses on the gaze of certain characters within the narrative of the film it becomes iconic as well, depicting what is seen by a particular pair of eyes.

The signifiers created by lighting also control the viewer's gaze, inducing him to concentrate on particular features of the image rather than others. Consequently, these signifiers are indexical. But if lighting is used to represent day and night and sometimes emanates from bulbs or lamps which provide part of the setting it can also generate iconic signifiers.

Apart from the cinematic devices described above which are characterized by a preponderance of indexical or iconic properties, every cinematic image is iconic. The image (signifier) enjoys so intimate a relationship to its signified that it may seem superfluous to distinguish between them.

2.1.5.1 Kinesics

Kinesics is the study of the system of facial expression and bodily gestures in non-linguistic form of visual communication. Each component of kinesics performs a variety of functions. For instance, movements of the face and body can give clues to a person's personality and emotional state. The face, in particular, signals a wide range of emotions such as fear, happiness, sadness, anger, surprise, interest and disgust with many of the expressions varying in meaning from culture to culture.

Some body and facial expressions that are used in a wide range of human contexts are present in the Yorùbá culture though they may be differently interpreted as defined by the culture.⁸ Many gestures and facial expressions, in the Yorùbá society are used to convey meaning. While the nodding of the head vertically, for instance, signifies approval, horizontal nodding means disapproval. Shrugging of the shoulders in the Yorùbá society is also an index of disdain or indifference while an open mouth signifies astonishment or surprise.

The film being a visual medium apart from speech employs kinesics for communicative purposes. In the film narrative, the face and body send signals as characters' interaction between characters is proceeding. For instance, patterns of eye contact shows who is talking to who, facial

expressions give out such meanings as puzzlement or disbelief and body postures convey a character's attitude namely, whether he is relaxed, interested or bored. Furthermore, body gestures used on ritual occasions such as kneeling, bowing, hand raising and so on are also employed in film narrative to convey meaning.

Our observation about kinesics in the film in general and the Yorùbá video film in particular reveals that it utilizes the close-up for dramatic effects. The use of close-up draws our attention to the details of the scene where there is a nuance of facial expression or a significant body movement or gesture.

2.1.6 Pictorial Communication

In film, meaning is achieved in pictures by means of sequencing of images (shots). Pictorial communication has different limitation from those inherent in linguistic communication. In pictorial communication, a picture may be misinterpreted if isolated or singled out. Any interpretation given to a singled-out shot or photograph is rather suggestive than saying the exact. On the other hand, some critics have argued that certain minimal inferences about the subject matter are possible in a singled out shot or photograph. For instance, it has been argued that when presented with a picture of a man who is running, we can quite reliably infer from the shot that the man is either

being pursued and consequently running out of danger or that he is pursuing something. Though, the interpretation might be true but the details are not presented. For instance, one would like to know : what actually is pursuing the man? What offence has he committed? Where is he running from? Where is he running to? What happened afterwards?

Though there may be implied narrative in single images, this is not to say that the viewer would be in a better position to acquire knowledge about the beliefs, intentions, choices, etc. of whoever or whatever is photographed in those single images than from those with narrative sequence. Filmmakers consciously and deliberately select shots which will effectively convey their intention in sequence. The totality of the shots, which are joined together through the editing devices to form a narrative sequence, gives a total meaning to the narrative. Meaning is therefore largely determined on the relationship of shots and by the context in which they are presented. Perhaps, Levaco's (1972 :106) opinion about how meaning is achieved through film shots encapsulates the issue of pictorial communication :

.... no image can be sensible in cinema unless it stands in some previously held relationship to something else, either affirmable within the parameters of a single take or confirmable between shots (in a sequence) by a similar

relationship established through montage. ... if in a film you see some sort of object and do not know its logical relationships to its surroundings, you cannot know precisely what it is nor in which area of the depth of field within the shot it belongs. In short, you cannot know its significance.

In this chapter, we have considered the two theories which we think are relevant to the present work. Aesthetics derived from consideration of works of art (literary or visual) has been examined. We have also discussed the semiotic theory. We think that since the film makes use of verbal and non-verbal systems in conveying meaning, then an application of the semiotic theory to film narrative will provide an intensity of treatment of film aesthetics.

In the following chapters, we shall apply, and/or adapt these theories as the material under study shall dictate.

NOTES

1. Musical art can be subsumed under the literary or the visual art.
2. See Olu Obafemi (1996 :63-64) for a more detailed analysis of Moses Olaiya Adejumo's language.
3. See Chapter 4.
4. Other semioticians have given other names to these terms. For instance while the signifier is also called 'signan' or 'sign vehicle', the signified is also referred to as 'signatum' or sign function'. But in this work for consistency we shall use 'signifier' and 'signified' which are Saussurean terms and which have been found widely acceptable.
5. Charles Sanders Pierce (1839-1914) was a philosopher and the American founder of semiotics. His ideas about semiotics are found in the eight volumes of his *Collected Papers*
6. Ogundeji (1988 :39) has described meto-symbolization as a process where the signifier substituted for the signified has a contagious relationship with the signified.
7. Olatunji (1985) further submits that statements about this belief

feature in such association as :

Dídùndídùn là á bálé olóyìn adùnkàn-àdùnkàn ni ti
kúkùndùnkú

It is all sweetness that one encounters in the house of the honey seller. Everlasting sweetness is the lot of the sweet potatoe.

8. The various facial expressions are blank-faced, raised brow, wide-eyed, wink, stare, rolled eyes, shifty eyes, glare, tongue in cheek, frown, pout, clenched teeth, lip biting and open mouth while body expressions are nodding, struggling, nudging, clenched fist, clapping shoving, pointing, wriggling, poking and grimacing.

CHAPTER THREE

TYOLOGY, THEME AND CHARACTERIZATION

3.0. INTRODUCTION

This chapter considers the typology, theme and characterization of the Yorùbá video films. Under typology, based on generic consideration, we have identified the folkloric, comic, crime, religious and love films. One common feature of the Yorùbá video films is their constant recourse to convey moral lessons and advice. Consequently, the films function as instrument of moral instruction. Since the role of the characters in the development of actions and/or incidents in a work of art is so vitally important, it is also necessary to have a look at how characters are depicted in the Yorùbá video films.

3.1 Typology

A consideration of Àlà mú (1991) and Adélékè's (1995) classification of the Yorùbá celluloid film reveals that five out of the different types identified by them can also be found in the Yorùbá videos film. They are: folkloric, comic, crime, religious and love films. For our discussion of these different classes of the Yorùbá video film, at least one of out the films that fall under each class will be used for our analysis.

3.1.1 Folkloric Films

Films like *Fópomóyò*, *Kòtò Ọrun*, *Èkùlé Ọrun* and *Èkùró Ọlójà* to mention a few, are films that draw freely from Yorùbá folklore. *Èkùró Ọlójà* for instance, derived its title from a sacred palm kernel used for rituals when installing a new king in Àròbájọ town. A new king (Alayé of Àròbájọ) was being sought for the town and the *ifa* oracle approved the candidature of two princes: Adélékàn and Ìbiladé. The first of the two candidates to present the *Èkùró Ọlójà* (the sacred palm kernel) is to be crowned the *Alayé*.

Meanwhile, Ibilade's former friend, Tégbè is now the custodian of the sacred palm kernel which was given to him by one of his farmhands, who found it in the bush after Alákijà had stolen it from Èlémònà's house and had thrown it away. Tegbe had caught her friend's wife red-handed with a lover. In order to cover her misdemeanour, she lied that Tegbe wanted to rape her. Ìbilade believed his wife's story. Tegbe left the town out of shame.

When Ìbilade later heard that Tegbe can help him fulfil his life ambition by giving him the sacred kernel in his possession, he sent emissaries to him. But Tegbe refused to accede to his request and this made Ìbilade plot to steal the object from his farm. When Tégbè sensed this development, he

exchanged the original kernel with a fake one. The hoodlums *Ìbilade* sent, set *Tégbè's* hut on fire and made away with the fake kernel. In order to punish *Ìbilade*, *Tegbe* later gave the original kernel to *Adélékàn* who was *Ìbilade's* rival. *Adélékàn* presented it to the kingmakers who crowned him as the *Alaye* of *Àrobajo*. The candidature of *Ìbilade* who had earlier presented the fake kernel was later disapproved.

One common characteristics of folkloric films is their depiction of the setting, incidents and situation of the *Yorùbá* traditional life, *Èkùrọ́ Ọlójà*, for instance, glamorises the rural landscape, the idyllic village life and the natural scenery of the *Yorùbá* traditional society.

The *Yorùbá* world view with their belief in magic is portrayed in *Yorùbá* folkloric films. The potency of the *Ọfọ́* (incantation) employed by *Alákijà* to cause *Èlémọ̀nà* to have a deep sleep before stealing the kernel shows that incantation is a verbal aspect of the magical art. When the people of *Àròbájọ* are faced with the dilemma of what interpretation to give to the strange birth of the baby boy who was born holding the *èkùrọ́ ọlójà*, they had to consult *ifá* for solution. *Ifá* in the *Yorùbá* belief is regarded as the custodian of all divine wisdom and the repository of all the myths and moral tenets of the other divinities.

The primary achievement of the producers of folkloric films lies in the way they have been able to use the Yorùbá oral tradition and folktale materials as a dimension of developed narrative. These films are significant in that they depict traditional Yorùbá life. The knowledge of the producers about Yorùbá traditional life and customs, combined with their creative ability gives vividness to the setting of these folkloric films.

3.1.2 Comic Films

Moses Ọláiyá Adéjùmọ (Bàbá Sàlá) is indisputably one of the most popular and commercially viable professional theatre practitioner in Nigeria. His films are based on comedy which he has deftly embraced to distinguish his productions from those of his contemporaries. The improbabilities of plot and characterization which are contained in his theatrical productions are tapped for humorous effect (Olú Ọbáfẹmi 1996 :55). Moses Ọlaiya's films are not only comic but satirical.

Scholars have tried to distinguish comedy from satire. Abrams (1981:167) for instance argues that while comedy evokes laughter mainly as an end in itself, satire 'derides', that is, uses laughter as a weapon and against a butt existing outside the work itself. The butt, Abrams further explains, may be an individual, a class, an institution, a nation or even the whole human

race. Though most times, Moses Adéjùmò's films are comic, the comic elements are only employed to ridicule the fatuous and hypocritical in the Nigerian society.

Ààrẹ̀ Àgbáyé, *Ọ̀run Móoru* and *Ána Góminà* are examples of Adéjùmò's video films that portray comic elements.

Ààrẹ̀ Àgbáyé, tells the story of Baba Sàlá, an ambitious man, who has become rich through juju means and not being satisfied, he wants to become a 'god' or the ruler of the world. His overambition ruins him and he ends up in the flames of hell.

In the film, Baba Sala mostly creates his comedies through costuming, distortion of normal procedures, gestures and mannerisms. For instance, he violates the Yorùbá dressing norms. He tucks in his 'bùbá' inside his 'kẹ̀h̄bẹ̀' and puts on an extra large wooden bow tie. The use of a bow tie (which is synonymous with the European dressing mode) on a Yorùbá traditional attire signifies culture conflict and may generate laughter.

Furthermore, there are in the society some laid down rules. Each profession, for instance, has its own particular ethics. It is a laid down procedure in the court of law that a judge or magistrate should listen to the submissions of both the plaintiff and the defendant before giving his

judgement. In *Áàrẹ̀ Ágbáyé*, Baba Sala deliberately defies these norms to generate laughter. As a magistrate in the film, infatuated by the beauty of a female plaintiff, he gives his ruling in favour of the lady by sentencing the male defendant to seven years imprisonment without listening to his submission.

In *Òrun Móoru*, humour is largely created through speech and other stage mannerisms such as movement, gesture and mime. Baba Sala's exaggeration of the various movements of the face in the scene where he encounters the fairies and gnomes creates laughter. He performs these facial movements to imitate the physical appearance and the disability of these supernatural elements.

3.1.3 Crime Films

There is a lot of crime in contemporary Nigerian society. Artists who are aware of the menace posed by it have tried to use their various media to present crime in order to expose it.

By 'crime' we mean those activities that violate the criminal laws of Nigeria. In the Yorùbá society, crime is precipitated by different factors such as poverty, lust for money, women and power, greed, jealousy, discontentment and so on. While crime is largely perpetrated in the Yorùbá

traditional society through the use of charms, nowadays various sophisticated weapons like firearms and explosives are used for assault. The remarkable change in moral values brought about by the adoption of foreign cultures has overshadowed the values upheld in the Yorùbá society.

There can be no crime film if the society is crime free. The violence witnessed in the Yorùbá film portrays the problems and experiences of life. In any human society, there is bound to be problems of interpersonal relationship which may result in violence. This is what is depicted in the films that are classified as crime.

The Hollywood can also be said to have contributed to the emergence of the crime film in Nigeria and in the Yorùbá society in particular. Crime has been one of the three themes that have been the preoccupation of the contemporary American film. Others are sex and race. In America, arguments about the impact of this genre are almost as numerous as those about sex. As film began to explore more realistically the various subcultures of the American society, crime became a natural part of that exploration. On the other hand, American studios at a period needed a new gimmick to attract the audience and the ability of film to graphically depict crime in all its forms made violence a natural phenomenon (Reynertson 1970 :22). Perhaps, this notion makes Adélékè (1995 :193) to conclude that what has motivated the

Yorùbá filmmakers to produce films which reflect excessive violence was their intention to sell emotions to the audience.

The contemporary crime scene in Nigeria coupled with the influx of American films dealing with crime can therefore be said to be the fertile ground for the emergence of the Yorùbá crime film. Video films like *Kòṣeégbé*, *Kánran The Killer*, *Èmí Kan 1000* and *Owo Blow* among others consciously and much more overtly present crime.

In *Owo Blow*, for instance, armed robbery is at the centre of crime. Social insecurity and fear on the part of the citizenry are manifested in the film where a robbery syndicate threatens the peace of the society. It is reflected in this film that social disorganisation, oppression and poverty are indices of crime growth in Nigeria.²

The plots of the films classified as crime deal with an attempt by a hero or a law enforcement agent who demonstrates psychological and physical attributes to unravel the activities of a gang terrorizing his town. In his bid, he exposes the criminals and becomes the focal point of our admiration.

3.1.4 Religious Films

The production of religious films is a new trend in the Yorùbá video film enterprise. Recently, some christian religious organizations now involve themselves in the production of films which depict the christian theology.³ The spiritual or emotional attitude of members of these religious organizations in their recognition of the power of God is brought to bear in their narration. Such films include *Ègún Ìpilẹ̀sẹ̀*, *Agbára Nlá*, *Idà Èṣù*, *Àsiṣe Nlá* and *Ogun Àtiléwá*.

Ogun Àtiléwá. for instance, reflects the supremacy of the power of God over that of Satan. It dramatizes the christian belief that the wicked shall not go unpunished.

In the film, Adewale employs a series of bizarre and supernatural forces to deal with his colleagues whom he considers as 'obstacles' to his inordinate ambition of becoming the Managing Director of his Company's London office. He gets rid of Bólú Gbólágeṣin, the incumbent Managing Director to create a vacuum. In spite of *ifá's* prognostication to the contrary, he loses the position to Máyòwá. Bent on getting the post, he again consults the *ifá* priest who helps him to afflict Mayowa with madness. Adéwálé thinks that his time has now come to have the post. The Chairman of the company, however, rules in

favour of another staff, Martins, a born again christian. Adéwálé's attempt to harm Martins backfires as God confirms His supremacy over Satan. In the process, Adéwálé runs mad.

All the religious films have a didactic slant. It lies in their condemnation of evil and reward for those who serve and trust in God.

3.1.5 Love Films

One essential feature of love films is that they are rooted in contemporary Yorùbá life. The subject of love in love films is handled either as a self – contained theme or in the context of marriage.

As Obiechinna (1973 :32) has rightly observed, in the African traditional society, though a male teenager does excite or show affection to a female teenager, but not through physical expression. Western civilization brought about by contact between Africa and the West has now altered the situation. Kissing, necking, hand-holding, cuddling and sex among others, not widely or openly known in the Yorùbá traditional society, are now indices of the state of being in love. This is what is portrayed in the Yorùbá love films.

In the world of the Yorùbá love film, a young man (usually the protagonist) is attracted strongly to a young woman. To make contact with the object of his excitement, the young man seizes any earliest opportunity to

make his intention known to the young woman. The acceptance of the young man's proposal enables them to proceed to strengthen the relationship. As the relationship progresses, physical, emotional, intellectual and psychological contacts are made. In other words, they come to care for each other in a deeply personal way. The situation might last as long as is convenient to the parties and might break up and the two drift apart again. The relationship might also mature into a permanent association where both parties decide to translate the love affair into marriage.

Yemí My Lover, Missing in love, For Better For Worse, Torí Ifé and *Ó Le Kú* are examples of Yorùbá love films. The contents of these films are based on contemporary romantic relationship between a male and a female teenager. One common phenomenon in these films is their portrayal of love as a basis for marriage.

3.2 Theme

The various and diverse theme of the Yorùbá Video films reflect their producers' intention to proffer information about the Yorùbá society and their relationship with that society. The moral concern of these producers provides us with a total view of that relationship. The attitudes and ideas of the

producers are shaped by their socio-cultural and political background which they in return relate in their words.

The plot of the Yorùbá video film is usually straightforward and reflects incidents which depict the reality of everyday life and experiences. We agree with Adeleke (1995 :156) that though the Yorùbá film has criticized institutions like marriage, politics, religion and the social strata, the family institution which is basic to all these other social institutions has been the most criticized. 'The gender and social role of the husband, wife, father, mother, child, brother, sister, in-laws' and so on, according to Adélékè have always been 'the focus of the Yorùbá film'. The family also constitutes a major theme in the Yorùbá video film.

The themes in the Yorùbá video film are carefully selected for treatment by the producers and are in consonance with the producers' creation of their characters. For the purpose of this study, three important and common themes have been selected for treatment. They are: jealousy, inheritance and lust for power, money and women. The last theme is more important because of its central concern to almost all the Yorùbá video films.

3.2.1 The Theme of Jealousy

Jealousy, especially among co-wives is one of the recurring themes in the Yorùbá video film. Films like *Adùn*, *Şaworoidę*, *Orogún Adédigba Ìkà Lomọ Ejò* and *Owú* among others dwell on this theme. Although, the theme is limited to just a part of the narrative in the first two films, it is the main theme in the last three films.

Jealousy has been identified as the factor responsible for unhealthy rivalry between co-wives. Its condemnation in the films is also seen as a condemnation of polygamy.

The actions of Tinúọlá and Àşàbí in *Şaworoidę* demonstrate co-wives' rivalry in a polygamous home especially among the wives of a king. The Yorùbá King (Ọba) by position is polygamous. He has a retinue of wives, some he inherits and some married by him. Lápité decides to marry the more beautiful Tinúọlá to mark his ascendancy to the throne of Jogbo town. His preference for Tinúọlá lies in Tinúọlá's beauty and moderate size in contrast to Àşàbí's big size :

Lápítẹ : Ta lolon? Àṣàbí? E e. Ta ni yí o
 a gbé irú àbàtiàlápà, gbàgbàtiòkò,
 ògidimòdẹ ùn lẹ sààfin?

Who is the king's wife? Asabi? Eh!
 who will take such dumsy, decrepit,
 shapeless woman to the palace?

When Tinúọlá moves into the modern palace with Lápítẹ, this does not go down well with Àṣàbí who feels cheated and incessantly goes to the palace to harass her co-wife. When the frequent quarrels become an embarrassment to the king, he takes sides with Tinúọlá and bans Àṣàbí from coming to the 'modern' palace.

At times jealousy can be innate, an essential characteristics of an individual. Human beings who exhibit such trait are usually possessive and suspicious. In *Owú*, Démiládé epitomizes jealousy. She suspects her husband and quarrels with him and any lady she sees with him. On one of such occasions, she quarrels with her husband's Secretary when she pays him an unscheduled visit and meets him discussing with his secretary. In consequence, her husband's Managing Director when he becomes tired of her actions, fires Délé, her husband. Dele then decides to travel abroad without

his wife and two daughters. In anger, Démiládé decides to bring her husband back. She employs the services of a juju man who enchants Délé to come back home.

When Délé arrived, Démiládé discovered that her husband had already married another woman abroad who also had a male child for him. Enraged with jealousy and hatred, she decided to attack her husband. In order to avoid her trouble and enjoy a temporary relief, Délé left the house for a hotel. But unfortunately, he was killed by armed robbers who had traced him to his hotel room. Because she could not bear the shock, Démiládé poisoned herself and her two children. The two girls died, but her brother-in-laws came to save her life. Her hope was finally dashed when Délé in his will made only his children as benefactors. Having killed her two innocent daughters who could have been more favoured in the will, the only boy by Délé's second wife consequently became the sole benefactor of his father's estate.

In Yorùbá video films that treat jealousy, it appears as if the producers see it as a female phenomenon. But this is not true. Men too have been found to be jealous. Envy, resentfulness, rivalry and so on are also present between the men folk. The mark of difference in the manifestation of jealousy between the male and the female folk is that while it is so much prominent amongst women, the men play it down.

3.2.2 The Theme of Inheritance

By and large, the principle governing inheritance among the Yorùbá in the contemporary society gives the wife of the deceased a right to her husband's estate. But many atimes, greedy family members of the deceased try to deny the widow this right by appropriating the estate to themselves. This attitude has been condemned by Yorùbá film producers vehemently.

In *Èbíkébí*, after the death of Yòní, members of his family attempt to take away from his widow her rights to her husband's property, but she does not agree. A few months after, she dies during childbirth but the baby survives. Àjàlá, a member of the family, want to take over the property and in his greed, he kills the other members of the family. He fails in his bid to also kill the baby girl. He dies in the process as the concoction he has prepared spills over him. Yòní's estate is later handed over to his daughter when she comes of age.

At times, inheritance has been found to be a motive for crime perpetration. Friends have killed one another, wives have murdered their husbands, siblings have assassinated one another to inherit properties. Such evil acts are also frowned upon by the film-makers and these they reflect in some of their films.

In *Òkò*, Jídé, a mechanic and a lover to Chief Ayòṣá's adulterous wife, influences the killing of the Chief so as to inherit his wife and estate. During one of their meetings, Mrs. Ayòṣá had confessed to Jídé that the refusal of her husband to give her enough money is affecting her ability to give him money :

Kódà owó tí mo fún ọ yí kì bá jù bẹ̀ẹ̀ lọ,
àmọ̀ kò fún mí lówó dáadáa mọ́.

Even this amount that I have just given to you could have been more but he has refused giving me enough money again.

When Jídé sensed that he could not get as much money from the adulterous wife as he wishes to, he promises Mrs Ayòṣá a love potion for her husband. But this is not to be as Jide has made up his mind to kill Chief Ayòṣá instead so as to eventually marry the wife and own her husband's estate.

To execute his plan, Jide consults a *juju* man, a friend of his who prepares a poisonous potion instead of a love potion for the Chief's wife with an instruction that she applies it to her husband's food. This act carried out by unsuspecting Mrs Ayòṣá leads to the death of her husband. But after the

death of Chief Ayḍolá, his wife becomes very unhappy with Jídé when she later realises his culpability in her husband's death. However, the two later die in mysterious circumstances.

3.2.3 Lusts: Power, Money and Women

Man's quest for power, money and women has often been the root of crime in the society. While he wants power so as to have the ability or official capacity to exercise control or authority or have great influence over others, he also needs money, resources and abundant riches. When a man achieves these, he wins the admiration of women. Man's uncontrolled passion or boundless enthusiasm for money, power and women has been found to lead to his destruction. Perhaps, this is why the Yorùbá film producers have found the expostulation of these themes so important in their works.

In *Şaworoidę*, Lápitę's lust for power and money leads to his untimely death in the hands of the soldiers led by Làgàta who seized power from him. With the help of Balógun, Lápitę had earlier schemed his way to become the king of Jogbo town. His rule is characterized by scandals, wickedness and misappropriation. Working in collaboration with the loggers headed by Làgbàyí, logs are exported for foreign exchange which they share among

themselves. Lápitẹ also extends the largesse to his traditional chiefs who he buys over. When the militant youths attempt to overthrow him, he seeks the support of the military. Ironically, the military who had helped him secure his position later overthrow and kill him.

In *Gbòhgbò Èsẹ̀*, the lust for money is mainly portrayed. The three different acts in the film present characters whose passion for money leads to grave consequences.

In the first act, Abis steals his father's building documents and sells the house without the consent of his father to fulfil his desire to travel abroad in search of greener pasture. The unsuspecting father, Chief Adé is later embarrassed and harassed by the new buyer. When the harassment and embarrassment become unbearable for him, Chief Adé commits suicide to cover his shame. Abis, who had travelled abroad without genuine documents is later repatriated. He returns home a pauper.

In the second act, Omítóògùn's wife abandons him because of his poverty for Chief Aji. In his bid to take full possession of the women, Chief Aji plants a dead child killed by the hoodlums he has hired inside the boot of Omítóògùn's taxi cab. Omítóògùn is later arrested by the Police acting on a tip-off. Omítóògùn is sentenced to fourteen years imprisonment for an offence he did not commit. But as fate would have it, he is to be later

released from prison after the hoodlums Chief Aji sent on another mission are arrested, and make some confessional statement which implicate the Chief. He is consequently imprisoned instead while Omítóògùn's wife regrets her action.

In Act Three Abísógun, the accountant of a company, colludes with the auditor to defraud the company. He later hires contract killers who murder the auditor so that he alone can have the money. He is later arrested and jailed. Meanwhile, his wife with whom he had kept the money runs away with the money. After serving his jail term, Abísógun traces his run away wife and murders her for her treachery and her inability to provide the money. Abísógun later on commits suicide.

The message the producer of this film intends to bring out can be found in the thematic song that closes it:

Kí ni gbòhgbò èsè? Owó! Owó ni
gbòhgbò èsè.

What is the root of evil? Money! Money
is the root of evil.

Chief Kanran (Honourable) in *Éèwọ* is a womanizer. He runs after any beautiful woman that comes his way to the extent that his passion for women becomes a subject of discussion in the neighbourhood. While in the

secondary school, he had put a girl in the family way and later abandons her before travelling abroad.

When he returns, he meets Fúnntọ during one of his escapades and later put her also in the family way. He plans to marry the girl but later finds out that she is the daughter the girl he had put in the family way in the Secondary School had for him. He has committed incest which is an abomination. He tries to commit suicide but he is prevented and has to live his remaining life in shame.

In conclusion, the Yorùbá video films portray realistic and critical issues in the contemporary Yorùbá society. The simmering problems that emanate from the themes considered above are critically examined and challenged by the producers who through their films see the need for social re-orientation and change.

3.3 CHARACTERIZATION

Structuralists such as Propp, Dundes, Todorov, etc. consider characterization as an aspect of the plot. Their consideration is rooted in the fact that the theme of any narration is acted out by the characters. The theme is always in consonance with the producers' creation of characters.

The general trend in literary tradition is the identification of a character by its overall function whether as a hero (protagonist) or a villain (antagonist). The role of the characters in the development of actions or incidents in a work of art is very important. Characters are recognized mainly by their behavioural and identificatory features which include their physical appearance, speech, costume, actions and reactions, social roles and qualities.

Under characterization, four groups of characters based on the traits exhibited by them have been identified. They are :

- i. characters with virtuous conduct
- ii. vicious characters
- iii. characters in love
- iv. comic characters.

3.3.1 Characters with Virtuous Conduct

The Yorùbá society is morally conscious. In the society, there are codes of behaviour handed down by the elders and supported by tradition and custom. One who keeps to this code of conduct is believed to be virtuous while one who is opposed to it is regarded as vicious. `Idòwú (1977 :146) lists some virtues in the Yorùbá society. These include : chastity, hospitality,

kindness, truthfulness, capacity to refrain from theft, respect for elders, gratitude, humility, etc.

One common feature of the Yorùbá video film is the constant recourse the producers make to convey effectively moral lessons and advice. In each of these films, moral lesson(s) are selected for treatment by the producers and these they have used in transforming their society positively.

In the works of the Yorùbá video film producers, some characters are readily perceived to be virtuous. Perhaps, the most illuminating technical device in the producers' art of characterization is their awareness that good behaviour with its reward is an effective tool in influencing the behaviour of their audience.

Kòṣeégbé, an adaptation of Ìṣòlá's dramatic text of the same title, presents the frightening state of smuggling and armed robbery in the society. The tripartite forces in the film namely, the custom officers, the police and the criminals are exposed. The corrupt situation in the Department of Customs and Excise which calls for urgent reforms is clear in the speech of Máko, the new Customs and Excise boss, at the beginning of the film:

A ti fi kún owó bodè lórí àwọn ẹ̀rù tó ní wọlé.
 A ti yọ Arówólò ní ipò onóbodè àgbà. ... Báyii
 a ti ṣetán láti gbógun ti iwà olè àti ti ọ̀dàlẹ̀.

We have increased the import duties. We have sacked Arowolo as the Custom Chief. ... Now we are ready to fight against armed robbery and treachery.

Máko is created as an uncompromising, straightforward and incorruptible Custom Chief. He fights corruption and its agents who are prominent personalities in the society. In his determined effort to put an end to these fraudulent practices, he faces two different blackmails plotted by the criminals. To complicate issues, his immediate assistants betray him by becoming accomplices to the criminals. However, with high dedication and relentless efforts, Mako, with the assistance of Tàlàbí, the head of the Secret Service outfit, mount a successful campaign against the activities of the criminals.

Máko is an introvert and a committed Custom Officer. He has no time for social functions and this is why it takes Sílífá some time to convince him to attend her 'birthday party' so as to carry out her plan to seduce him.

Máko is very witty and he demonstrates this in his dialogue with Gbélégbó as he brushes aside his moves to convince him to drop the operation he has launched against the criminals:

Gbélégbọ : Báwo lo ọ se fẹ ọ se ẹ tó fi jẹ pé ẹ ẹ le gé
Gbogbo itàkùn inú igbó tí ẹ ẹ fi ní pagi
kankan láa?

Máko : Tí a bá gé itàkùn, tí ọgbẹ bá bà róko, yó
mọ pé itàkùn tó lọ mọ òun, ló mọgbẹ báun.
Itàkùn tó dì móbì ni ò jóbì ọ sèsò re.

Gbélégbọ : Ọ̀gbọ̀n àwà mọ pé, láláí ọjú oró ni ò jẹ̀sẹ̀
ẹyẹ ọ tójú omi. N tawa hí sọ fún ọ ni pé, kó
o mọ ọ se ẹyí tó o bá lè se ńbẹ ni. Èyàn kan
ò lèse gbogbo ẹ tán.

Máko : Bàbá, ẹ ẹ ríran wò, àwà ọ fọ ibẹ mọ téniténí.

Gbélégbọ : How do you want to cut all the liana in the bush
Without wounding any tree?

Máko : If in the process of cutting the liana, the 'iroko'
tree (African teak/Chlorophora Excelsa) is hurt,
it will know that it is the liana which entangles it
that brings about the cut. The liana that entangles
the kolanut tree is the cause of its barrenness.

Gbélégbọ : But we know that forever the water lettuce will

not allow the feet of the bird to touch water.
Our advice to you is that you should do the one
you can do. Nobody can accomplish all the
enormous task.

Máko : Sir, you wait and see. We shall sanitise the
 place.

Máko's intelligence makes him survive the two blackmails plotted against him by his opponents. With the help of Tàlàbí he apprehends the culprits.

Taxi Driver emphasizes the fact that good character and not status is the most important factor in marriage.

In the film, Túndé, a taxi driver, wins the heart of Mojí Jacob, an accountant and the daughter of a Police Commissioner as a result of his honesty in returning the money which she had forgotten in his taxi cab. Túndé is further admired by Mojí for his feat in facilitating the arrest of some hoodlums who are responsible for kidnapping, killing and using human parts for money-making rituals. While Mojí's father supports his daughter's love for Túndé, her mother vehemently objects to the relationship. She wonders why her daughter, a graduate should marry a common taxi driver and an illiterate. In her bid to stop the relationship, she resorts to diabolical means consulting her fellow witches. This soon backfires and she publicly confesses all her

atrocities and devilish acts. She is consequently stoned to death. And thereafter, Mojí marries Túndé.

One important feature of this film, as of all other Afọláyan's films in which he plays the lead role, is their emphasis on character. The prevalent structure of Afọláyan's dramaturgy is his permanent identification with the good character. The plot of his films always centres on his adventure while pursuing a combination of personal and social aspirations against a hostile environment inhabited by evil men. He overcomes this after a variety of obstacles and gains as a result, self respect, the approval of the community and love of a desirable young woman. This kind of leitmotif is what Ekwuazi (1984 :236) has described as a feature of the American film.

The role of a good child in the family is also emphasized in *Taxi Driver*. The character of Yínká, the son of Túndé by his first marriage, is quite impressive. He is presented as an innocent and intelligent child. Each time the father returns from his business, he is always there to welcome him and ask him about how he has fared. On one of such occasions he asks:

Bàba mi, ẹ́ ẹ̀ tà lónìí? Ẹ̀lọ̀pàá ò mú u yin?

Ẹ́ mọ̀tò ò yonu? Kí lẹ̀ mú bọ̀ fún mi?

My father, hope you make some sales today. I

hope that the Police did not arrest you. Hope the vehicle did not give any trouble. What did you bring for me?

When his mother who had left his father because of his abject poverty refuses to come back in spite of several appeals, Yínká encourages his father by saying that:

Bàbá mi, tó bá ẹ̀ tì torí owó ni ìyá mí ò fi ní kó wálé
mọ́, bí n bá dàgbà n ó wá owó fún un yín. Àmọ́ n ò ní
jàlẹ̀ o. Ẹ́ ẹ́ gbọ́?

My father, if my mother refuses to come back home
Because you are poor, when I grow up I will give you
money. But I will not steal. Do you hear me?

Yinka's utterances throw considerable light on his character. From every point of view, an intelligent and considerate boy is presented. His behavioural traits are therefore so sensitively portrayed.

In *Òbúkọ́ Dúdú*, *Şiyanbọ́lá*, is presented as a true friend of Tẹ̀là. In the film, *Adẹ̀rùpọ̀kọ*, a security guard, had charmed Kúnlé, the son of Tẹ̀là, to commit incest with his father's wife. He has done this to avenge Kúnlé's advice to Tẹ̀là, (the Managing Director) to sack *Adẹ̀rùpọ̀kọ* for inefficiency.

When Tẹ̀là discovers that Mojí is pregnant, he sends her out of the house. When further enquiries show that Kúnlé is responsible, Tẹ̀là also sends him and his mother away.

All pleas and entreaties by Kúnlé's grandmother are turned down by his father. His grandmother as a last resort discloses to Şıyanbólá, Tẹ̀là's friend, the secret of how she has used her supernatural power to enrich Tẹ̀là and advises him to convince his friend to recall his wives and son or stand the risk of becoming poor again. She then warns Şıyanbólá not to disclose the secret to avoid calamity. But Şıyanbólá being a good friend, discloses this secret to Tẹ̀là to convince his obdurate friend to change his mind over his decision. Şıyanbólá goes mad for revealing the secret. It takes the intervention of an ifá-priest to heal him after Tẹ̀là had promised to take his wives and son back. Adẹ̀rùpọ̀kọ̀ is paid back in his own coin as he goes mad after Mojí acting on the instruction of an ifá priest had taken the type of he-goat he used for the charm to him.

In this film, Şıyanbólá is depicted as a true friend indeed. Despite his awareness of the danger of revealing the secret of his friend's wealth, he

displays a strength of character by resolving to damn the consequences and save his friend from trouble.

The characters so far discussed above are presented by the film producers as personifications of virtues. By so doing, the producers manifest through their characters the concept of good character which is basic for wholesome human relations.

3.3.2 Vicious Characters

The penchant of the Yorùbá video film producers for morality encourages their condemnation of social evils in all its ramifications. To achieve this, malevolent characters are usually punished for the various heinous offences committed by them.

In *Kòṣéégbé*, Arówólò, Málíkì and Tóíá represent the corrupt elites in the Nigerian society who employ illegal means such as smuggling and armed robbery to make money. Arówólò's attitude in particular is a reflection of the cankerworm that has so eaten deeply into the Nigerian Custom and Excise Department. His utterances at the beginning of the film portray him as one who trivializes corruption and sees it as something necessary to succeed in life:

À rí dọgbọ́n jayé, wọ́n lólè là rí jà. Ẹ́ owó oṣù tó

Jẹ? Ẹn, ẹn? Bí mo bá ran ẹnìkan lẹwọ tó sì fún mi lẹbùn, sé kò yẹ kí n gbà á? Ẹn, en? Wọ́n lólè nìyẹn. Èmi ò ní ba tẹ̀nìkan jẹ. Àmọ kẹ̀nìkan má gba oúnjẹ lẹnu tẹ̀mí o.

We are discreetly enjoying life, people accuse us of fraudulence. If I render help to someone and he offers me a gift, shouldn't I take it? Eh! People say that is stealing. I will not get anybody into trouble. And let nobody deprive me of my own 'food' (loot).

Arówólò was later sacked for corruption and arrested with Málíkì and Tólá for smuggling.

In *Àmin Ọrun*, Wọ́lé is presented as cruel and immoral. As a Student Union leader, he leads the students' riot against the College authorities. He throws a hot plate of beans at Rísí's face during the students' protest. He later apologises and Rísí falls in love with him. His rascally behaviour is further brought to light when he denies being responsible for Rísí's pregnancy. After Rísí had given birth to Ẹ̀nìtàn, Wọ́lé plans to kill Rísí and the baby. In the face of this problem, Tómi, his wife who has been medically confirmed unfit to have a baby as a result of the complications arising from an abortion

which Wọlé had performed on her while they were medical students, suggests that Ẹniitàn should be adopted. The adoption of Ẹniitàn sparks off chains of problems for Rísí who is later denied the maternity of her child. She eventually succeeds in reclaiming her child through the birth-mark which she and her daughter have in common. Wọlé's wife, Tómi, abandons him. He is also disfigured by the hoodlums employed by Senabu, Rísí's friend, to avenge the ill-treatment of Rísí.

Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ condemns treachery, greed and avarice. In the film, a clique, Sànyà and JP lobby a greedy traditional chief, Ọtún, to assist in a clandestine plan to sell the ancestral land of their town, Ajéígbé to an unsuspecting industrialist, Mr Johnson. Through the efforts of Ọtún, who distorts the history of the land, the clique wins the land case in court. But, as they start to enjoy the money made from the sale of the land, Sànyà and JP die mysteriously in quick succession. Though Ọtún makes frantic efforts to save his life, his return to Ajéígbé after his exile is characterized by disharmony and tussles which he creates in the once peaceful town in his bid to reclaim his former title of Ọtún. His discontentment leads to his mysterious death.

The three characters that are involved in the land deal are presented at the beginning of the film as insolvent. They plan to make money through illegal means. Sànyà's physical appearance portrays him as a lower class peasant. His speech at his birthday ceremony after getting his own share of the land deal reveals his former poverty state and the transformation which he now enjoys:

Ní ìwòyí èşín, bisikíiti pàmbolá-bolà la fi
şe é. Şùgbọn lóđún yíí, omi titún ti rú, eja
tuntun sì ti wọ inú rẹ.

Last year, the birthday was celebrated with
cabin biscuit. Now things have changed
drastically

Ajíbádé (JP) on the other hand is a court bailiff who finds it difficult to cater effectively for his family. Twice, we see his wife complaining about his inability to provide money for feeding.

Right from the beginning of the film, Ọtún is presented as a greedy chief. At the opening scene, in the company of Ọsì, he is seen demanding money from the family where he is sent by the king to correct the injustice in their choice of a family head. Later, when Ọsì demands his own share of the

money, he reluctantly gives him a very inconsequential amount. Ọ̀sì's comments here reveal Ọ̀tún's greed:

Ọ̀rò rẹ̀ ò jọ mí lójú

Ó n' bá ọ̀ lọ̀ nù u

I am not surprised at your attitude

It is typical of you.

The attitude of Ọ̀tún at the restaurant where the idea about the land business is sold to him by Sànyà and Aǰíbádé confirms his greed and gluttony. He eats and drinks voraciously and during the course of the meal, he pledges to support the deal.

This method of character delienation at the beginning of the narrative alerts us to the traits and outlook of the three characters. We are therefore, not really surprised at their involvement in the shady land deal.

The predominant theme of *Owo Blow* is crime (armed robbery). It is the story of a man caught in his own trap.

After Mr Owólabí has been wrongly jailed for trying to free the traders from the oppression of the Local Government Council where he works, his family begins to experience hardship. His son, Wọ́lé drops out of school

because the family cannot afford his fees. He later falls into bad company and eventually becomes the leader of a notorious gang of armed robbers. Though he later leaves the gang and embarks on series of philanthropic projects which endear him to the people, he is exposed by one of his old friends. He later commits suicide to avoid public ridicule.

In the film, Wólé is presented as an intelligent and well nurtured boy who later falls into bad company as a result of hard times. His resolve to help the family which is passing through hard times leads him to armed robbery. His tactfulness and ability endear him to other members of the gang who ask him to lead the group. For these rare qualities, he is held in high esteem so much so that when he offers to resign, the other members bluntly refused. His resignation is only accepted when he has carried out their wish to lead them to a major operation. After he departs, members of the gang are later arrested after an operation.

Wole's reflection on the news of the arrest of his former colleagues focuses on the implication of such arrest. First, he knows that he may be exposed. Second, he is aware that his reputation which he has built over the years after quitting armed robbery, is at stake. The action he takes to free himself from his alleged involvement in armed robbery still portrays him as a very tactful and intelligent character. He embarks on an image laundering

programme and he is able to win the heart of the people many of whom pledge their total support for him. When it becomes clear that the video clips of his wedding ceremony will expose him as having any relationship with the arrested robbers during the course of investigation, his revelation to his wife about editing the tapes and removing all the traits of the presence of his former colleagues at his wedding, further confirm his skill in concealing detection.

Perhaps, one important method of character delineation in *Owo Blow* is the use of nicknames.⁴ The notoriety of the criminals is impressed upon the audience through their various nicknames such as Owo Blow, Fatty, Jugnu and Lẹgo.

The discussion above may give the impression that it is only men who engage in crime. This is not so. Many evils committed by women also feature in Yorùbá video films. Films such as *Adùn*, *Ìkà Lọmọ Ejò* and *Orogún Adédigba* expose the various crimes committed by women who are enraged with jealousy. As discussed in 3.2.1 above, jealousy in the Yorùbá video films is often sparked off by the preferential treatment given by the husband to the newly married wife.

In *Adùn*, Chief Kanran, a wealthy man, refuses all the advice of his uncles and goes ahead to marry Adùn as a second wife. In spite of the

warmth and affection shown to her by her senior co-wife, Adùn plots to get rid of her and Àlàdé, her only son so that she alone can inherit the wealth of their husband. With this burning desire, she charms her senior wife who thereafter goes mad. She also used charms to get Àlàdé repatriated from abroad and imprisoned for dealing in hard drugs. Now, filled with an inordinate ambition to own all her husband's property, she again plots against her husband who is linked with dealing in hard drugs and sentenced to life imprisonment. However, succour comes for Àlàdé and his father through a radical lawyer who incidentally is the father of Àlàdé's fiancée and also a relation of the 'juju' man Adùn had consulted for her atrocities. A charm prepared for the lawyer by his uncle, the 'juju' man, makes him succeed in talking Adùn into releasing all the documents of Chief Kanran's property. Adùn goes mad after she has shown some resistance. Àlàdé and his father are later released. Àlàdé's mother is also healed by the 'juju' man.

In *Ìkà Lọmọ Ejò*, Oyèníkẹẹ epitomises an enemy within the gate. Her hypocrisy coupled with her supernatural power which is unknown to her husband and her senior co-wife are used to cause disaffection between her husband and co-wife. The co-wife shows her resentment because their husband wanted her because of her age to become the junior and regard the new wife as her senior. This decision begins a series of actions which cause

disaffection and puzzle in the family. Oyèníkèé discredits her senior co-wife many times by buying items on credit after changing into her image. The incessant humiliation of the family by the creditors makes their husband to send the senior wife who is believed to be insolvent, away.

Orogún Adédigba is an autobiography which present the life story of the producer, Oyin Adéjóbí. As the only son of the family favoured by destiny to be an heir apparent and a potential great man, his stepmother, as he claimed, decides to halt his ambition by impairing his movement. Though his stepmother dies later, he is confined to the wheelchair. His disability seriously affects his limitation in the film and drama business.

In the Yorùbá video film, vicious characters are also depicted through the use of the star-system. These characters are cast in similar roles in different films and they charm and astonish the audience by the sheer power and expressiveness of their acts (Àlà mú 1991 :45). Such actors therefore become permanently stuck to these stereo-typed roles. Examples of such vicious characters include 'Àgbàkò' (Charles Olumọ), 'Fádèyí Olóró' (Ọjó Arówófáfé), 'Ikú' (Ganiyu Bello), 'Baba No Regret' (Ọlá Ọmọ̀nìtàn) among others. The appellations are quivering as they evoke the spirit of fear. Metaphorically, they reflect the viciousness of the characters.

3.3.3

Characters in Love

By characters in love, we mean a male and a female character who display intense affection and desire for each other. But, here, we shall restrict our assessment of such characters to pre-marital love which is a common theme in the films classified as love.

In the contemporary Nigerian society, multiple relationship before marriage is a common phenomenon among teenagers. The implications of keeping one's eggs in one basket (i.e. the fear of dashing of hope in single relationship) has always been put forward as a reason for multiple relationship. This approach is employed by Àjàní in *Ó Le Kú*.

Apart from the reason given above, Àjàní's natural love for girls also accentuates his passion for multiple relationship. He likes 'fine things' and goes for them in their different shapes and sizes. For instance, Àṣàké is a school leaver, beautiful, fair in complexion, of medium height and robust. Lọlá, his second girlfriend, is an undergraduate, tall, slim, dark and equally beautiful. Šadé who fortuitously finds herself at the centre stage of the love

drama is Ajani's childhood acquaintance. She is of average height, slim and also beautiful.

Àjàní is a schemer, intelligent and sweet-tongued. He employs all these traits to cover his double-deal. When Àṣàké and Lọlá meet at a party he has thrown to rejoice at his ownership of a Volkswagen Beetle car, he is able to convince Lọlá that he has no relationship with Àṣàké. Lọlá's knowledge of Àṣàké's pregnancy for Àjàní later exposes him. And this put an end to their relationship. He loses Àṣàké also because Adélékè, Àṣàké's father discourages her from continuing with the relationship. As a result of this loss, Àjàní is disturbed emotionally. Just at the point of giving up, Ìjàlọlá's advice keeps him on. He later resolves to marry Şadé, the only available choice.

Àjàní is presented as a great poet. This is demonstrated in his composition of three different poems for each of his damsels. In the poems, he stresses the attributes of the girls and this always endears him to them. For instance, he describes Àṣàké's beauty and his love for her thus:

Kòkòrò tí n jẹfọ jàre ẹfọ.

Ìwọ̀n lewéko ọ́ dára mọ.

Àjàní tó n l'Àṣàké jàre Àṣàké.

Ìwòṅ lomidan-án sunwòṅ-ṅṅ mọ.

Ìgbín mi ti tẹnumọ gii rẹ.

Ojú méjì tí dùndún ni,

Ohùn kan ní í fi í fọ.

Àtẹmi, àtìwọ

Ẹmíí wa ti dọkan.

The insect that feeds on the vegetable plant is justified.

A plant's lushness should be moderate.

Àjàní that is running after Àṣàké is justified.

A young girl's beauty should be within measure.

My snail has stuck firmly to your tree.

The two faces that the 'dundun' drum has,

Bring forth one tune.

You and I,

Our lives have become one.

He also describes Lọlá as extremely beautiful endowed with impeccable character and wisdom:

Kí í ẹ̀ pé n ò rómìdán rí.

Àfọ̀jọ́ tí mo rí Lọ́lá fìrì,

Ni mo tó gbà pé 'ẹ̀ Ọ̀lọrun ò lopin.

- - - - -

Àtọ̀wọ́dà yàtò sàbùdà.

Àmùtòrunwá yàtò sí tafeporara.

Àní, Lọ́lá lẹ̀wà, ọ́ yàtò.

Lọ́lá lẹ̀wà, ọ́ yọ gedegbe.

Ká dúdú, ká tún máa dǎn.

Ká búrìn búrìn, ká dá gọ̀jọ-gọ̀jọ.

Ojú bí i t'ángéì

Abitan bí i itan afáraóyin

Bó o pọ́ o dǎa tó Lọ́lá

Ìwà rẹ̀ ò tó tí Lọlá

Bó o sì pọ̀ o níwà tó pọ̀

Ọgbón rẹ̀ ò le jinlẹ̀ tó tọ̀rẹ̀ẹ̀ mi.

It is not as if I've not seen a girl before

The day I saw Lọlá at a glance

Is when I believe that God's work is infinite

Artificiality differs from naturalness

Natural creativity is different from fabrication

I say Lọlá's beauty is different

Lọlá's beauty is striking

Having dark complexion that glitters

Eyes like those of an angel

Her thighs are like the honeycomb

If you claim to be as beautiful as Lọlá

Your character cannot be as good as Lọlá's

And if you say your character is impeccable

Kò sùn lẹ́jọ́ tó dá Ẹ́adé

Ẹ́adé rí wẹ̀kú, ó gúnrégé

Ó wá rí rọ̀gbọ̀dò

Ó ní dá mi lẹ́rùn

Ó rí yọ̀yọ̀yọ̀ bí ọ̀dú

Ọ̀dú orí ilẹ̀ tuntun

Ẹ́adé rágbọ̀n ìwà kẹ̀wà sí

If you wish beat me with the whip and not a staff

It is the dark-beauty that I am gazing at

That makes me trip on the showcase of the cloth-seller

I cannot do without glancing at the dark-beauty

I cannot do without watching the buttocks laced with beads

The perfect dental set cannot be gazed at in the market

Without tripping on the showcase of the cloth-seller

Four eyes are not enough to watch the spectacle
 They are not enough to watch the feast for the eyes
 The scene I am watching is that of my friend
 My friend, who is as gracious as a new day
 The one who is as meek as the dove
 One who is perfect without blemish
 It is as if the creator was not asleep
 He was not asleep the day he created Şade
 Şade's shape is regular, she is petite
 She is robust
 She whets my appetite
 She is as lush as the *odu*^f vegetable
 The *odu* that grows on a virgin land
 Şade's basket of character is full of beauty.

In the poems, Àjàní focuses on his perception of his 'beauty queens' employing various similes to describe their flawless beauty. Also, through his metaphors we perceive their quintessence and uniqueness. These poems are largely employed by Àjàní to flatter the unsuspecting ladies.

Àjàní's sense of humour is inimitable. The aptness and propriety of his humours are indices of his brightness and broadmindedness. When for instance, Àşàké complains to Àjàní at the 'Èrèbe' night about a boy and a girl

whom she feels are prone to snake bite while making love on the grass, Ajani's response is full of humour:

Ejò pàápàá máa ní bọ̀wọ̀ f'áwọ̀n tó bá ní múfèé.
Bó bá sì bù wọ̀n jẹ, wọ̀n á gbádùn dọrun ni.

The snake also respects people making love.
And if it bites them, they will enjoy till they
get to heaven.

Socially, Ajani is pleasant, friendly and affable. He is fond of the company of his friends; attending parties with them and sharing his problems with them. He is a member of the Pirate Confraternity who were visible during his wedding ceremony.

In *Amin Orun Risi's* character reflects the infatuation that is usually associated with teenagers' relationship. In spite of the humiliation she gets from Wole, she later submits to Wole's persuasion to have sex with him. She becomes an object of ridicule when Wole rejects the pregnancy. Wole's non-acceptance of the pregnancy is in accordance with the attitude of teenagers who find themselves in similar situation. The case of unwanted pregnancy today is a global concern. Various international bodies such as the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the United Nations Children Educational Fund

(UNICEF) among others have committed their resources to stem the tide of this unwholesome practice. While Rísí is unlucky, Àṣàké in *Ó Le Kú* is quite fortunate as Àjàní accepts being responsible for the pregnancy and proposes marriage.

Túndé's honesty is the foundation of the courtship he had with Mojí in *Taxi Driver*. Mojí falls in love with Túndé immediately he returns the money she had forgotten in his taxi cab. Mojí's love for Túndé is a clear demonstration of the popular saying: 'love is blind' as her status as an Accountant and as a daughter of a Commissioner of Police does not stop her love for Túndé, a stark illiterate and a taxi driver. Even when her mother opposes her decision, she insists. They eventually got married.

Characters in love are thrown into an ecstasy of love relationship. They have delightful experience when in love but break down emotionally when the love collapses.

3.3.4 **Comic Characters**

These characters provide humour through their speeches, modes of dressing or actions. They are created for the purpose of alleviating tension and are integral to the plot of the narration.

Apart from Moses Ọláiyá Adéjùmò (Bàba Sálá) whose theatre has been described as comic, there are some other comic characters who are always present in one Yorùbá video film or the other to provide humour. They include 'Alúwèḗ' (Sunday Ọmòbòláríé), 'Aláràn-án' (Muftau Ọládòkun), 'Ajírèbí' (Káyòdé Ọláṣḗhìndé), 'Mọladùn' (Mọnsurat Omidina), 'Bàba Sùwé' (Babátúndé Omídínà) among others. Each of these characters has a predominant humorous style that gives him a characteristic eccentricity of disposition. For instance, while 'Lúkúlúkú' is always close to tears at any slight opportunity, 'Ajírèbí' speaks uncouth English. On the other hand, 'Bàba Sùwé' is popular for his distortion of the Yorùbá proverb.

One common feature of the comic characters is their grotesqueness in terms of dressing which is created to delight the audience.

In this chapter, we have considered the types of Yorùbá video films namely, folkloric, comic, crime, religious and love. The themes of jealousy, inheritance, lust for power, money and women have also been discussed. The various themes are suggestive of the conformity of the film producers with established principles, rules and custom. Perhaps, the producers can best be described as instructors on moral ideas of their society as they portray through their works the Yorùbá view of moral excellence which they articulate

pungently. As for characterization, we have found out that the Yorùbá video film producers depict their characters by employing various identificatory and behavioural features.

In the Yorùbá video film, we see a dramatization of the Yorùbá worldview that believes in tradition and in addition try to mirror the Yorùbá society.

NOTES

1. Alàmú (1991) identifies four types of Yorùbá celluloid film. They are folkloric, historical, hoodlum and comic. Adélékè (1995) on the other hand listed nine. They are : crime, horror, cultural (mythological), historical, love/sex, political, religious, comic and tragic film.
2. See the plot of this film in 3.3.2.
3. So far, we have not come across video films on other faiths. Those that exist are christian in their theology. Some religious organizations that are involved in the production of christian films are El-Shaddai Ministry, Mount Zion Faith Ministry and Bethel Ministry.
4. Though nicknames are used for some other characters in other Yorùbá video films, its use is much more pronounced in *Owo Blow*. All the members of the armed robbery gang are known by their nicknames. In *Owo Blow*, nickname is used to hide the identity of the criminals.
5. Òdú (*Solanum Nodiflorum*) is a popular vegetable plant in Yorùbáland.

CHAPTER FOUR

NARRATIVE DEVICES

4.0 INTRODUCTION

The narrative devices fall under three broad categories. They are technical, linguistic and paralinguistic. The technical devices involve the cinematic techniques which have been used for effect. Linguistic devices encompass the stylistic features in the speech or dialogue of the film characters, while the paralinguistic devices portray the various domains of non-verbal expression which fall under the general heading of semiotics. Emphasis will be laid on the aesthetic properties of these devices.

4.1. Technical Devices

In film narrative, apart from dialogue, there are other methods of presenting the story. Other means of expression include movement of the camera, the angle of the camera, sound, editing and *misé-en-scène*.

In film, the narrator is not necessarily a biological person, not even a somehow identifiable agent like in the novel, but a symbolic

activity. Each shot in the film is an agent of narration. The concept of camera on the one hand, has been seen, in a wider sense, as closer to the role of the narrator. This is why it has been described as a 'construct of the spectator' and 'a hypothesis about space'. Deleto (1996) similarly opines that the camera defines the position of the invisible observer who is identified with the narrator:

The camera has often been used as the equivalent of the narrator in film . . . The camera would define the position of that invisible observer that could be identified with the narrator, a more identifiable agent which would indeed seem to be the origin of narration in a film. We could even extend the concept of camera to account for editing devices. This invisible but identifiable narrator would be able not only to present, in various ways, the space contained in the frame, but would change from one shot to another when it is necessary for the development of the narrative.

From the above, we can deduce that apart from literary techniques, the film with its peculiar nature as an audio-visual medium has technical devices which should be considered for its aesthetic evaluation. These technical devices, which at times co-exist to bring out the beauty in the narration, will now form the subject of our discussion.

4.1.1 **Camera Movement**

Among the more special cinema techniques is the camera movement. It is a device that concerns the movement of the camera in capturing an object. There are three different types of camera movement. They are panning, tilting and tracking.

4.1.1.1 **Panning**

A panning shot is one in which the camera is turned to either the left or right in a horizontal plane. Panning can be used to include in one shot a subject matter that is too 'spread out' or vast which is to be covered from a fixed viewpoint. Examples of such subject matters are

an expanse of land, forest or a war scene. Panning can also be utilised to establish clearly the relationship between two or more subjects.

In *Òbúkọ Dúdu*, a panning shot of the forest where Şıyanbólá lives after he has run mad is used to cover its (forest) spread. On projection, the length or expanse of the forest moves across the screen to establish Şıyanbólá's position. In the scene, the shot of the search party is presented as they comb the forest. When his hiding place is located, the camera shows the joyful smile of members of the search party and pans until Şıyanbólá, the object of their joy is brought into focus.

This device is prominent on moving objects especially vehicles in video films such as *Kòşéégbé*, *Àmìn Ọrun*, *Taxi Driver*, *Ìyá Ní Wúra* and *Ogun Àtiléwá* among others. In *Kòşéégbé* for instance, an impression of the speed of Máko's car is presented as he drives home from the office after he has been informed about the planned blackmail by his antagonists. This device is also employed in *Àmìn Ọrun* as Ẹnìtàn's wedding procession leaves the church for her family house.

4.1.1.2 Tilting

Tilting is the movement of the camera in a vertical direction. It is used to capture objects located above. Its use in the opening scene of *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀* is captivating. As the film unfolds, the images of some supernatural elements are presented and suddenly the camera tilts vertically to capture the moon thereby signifying that the spectacle we are about to watch takes place at night.

In *Ó Le Ku* also, tilting is utilised to present Àjàní's father as he appears in a dream to Àjàní's mother. To achieve this, the camera is tilted to present the image of Àjàní's father on the top of a cliff. The extremely long shot that accompanies this device makes his appearance look like a speck on the horizon.

4.1.1.3 Tracking

In tracking shots, the camera may be moved forward or backward. When it is moved forward, towards an object, as a dramatic device of directing the audience's attention to some significant detail of

the action, it is called track-in. When it moves away or withdraws from it, it is called track-back.

There are three types of track shots. They are the long shot (LS), the mid-shot (MS) and the close-up (CU). Out of these three types of track shots, the LS and the CU are mostly utilised for dramatic effects. Normal recordings are always done with MS. In the light of the above, only the LS and CU will be considered in our discussion of tracking shots.

4.1.1.3.1 Long Shot (LS)

The LS of the landscape of the Obáfẹmi Awólówò University, Ilé-Ifẹ which serves as the location for *Kòşẹégbé* is an experience in aesthetic adventure. The shot describes the setting of the story with its good road layout, beautiful quarters and lawns. The surrounding trees add beauty to the environment.

At times LS is used to open a film and informs us about its location. *Taxi Driver*, for instance, opens with a LS of the Lagos City and its characteristic striking landscape dominated by flyovers, tower-

like buildings and the lagoon. The city appears to be a favourite location for contemporary film-makers because of its dramatic pictorial qualities.

In *Ó Le Kú*, a long elevated shot of the old Ibadàn city with its characteristic rusty roof tops opens the film. The sentence 'Níbàdàn La Wà Tá a Ti Ní Jayé' (We are at Ibadan where we enjoy life) on the screen and its accompanied drum sound which serves as a parody of an old jingle that opens the news programme of the old Nigeria Broadcasting Corporation (NBC) Ibadan, now Federal Radio Corporation of Nigeria, Ibadan gives us a hint that the location of the film is Ibadan and that the story happens in the recent past. The striking landscape of the University of Ibadan campus captured in LS supplies the pictorial qualities of the film. A shot of the University gate, surrounded by beautiful lawns and the matriculating students at the beginning of the film informs us that the actions or events we are about to watch happen within the walls of the institution. The luxuriant flowers, trees and gardens presented in LS in the various scenes where Àjàní renders his love verses to his damsels all add glamour to the quality of the film.

Furthermore, the various LS of the halls of residence give us the clue about the location of the scene we are about to watch. For instance, each time the events in the film are to take place in Àjàní or Lọlá's room in the halls of residence, a LS of the hall is first presented to provide the hint of the location of the action. Each location in *Ó Le Kú* is chosen with careful consideration for the setting in the novel and much of the inspiration in the film seems to derive its reality from this choice¹.

LS is mostly used to capture a considerable circumference of scenes in the video films we have considered above. It also serves as a tool for exterior shooting.

4.1.1.3.2. Close-Up

Close-up (CU) is indispensable for film narration. It is more prominent in films and serves many purposes. Firstly, it gives details of a particular situation. Secondly, it helps to open a window to the interior preoccupation of a character. Thirdly, it intensifies the participation of the audience in achieving a total situation and lastly, it brings into focus various facial activities of characters. Apart from these

functions, other devices, most especially soliloquy or interior monologue utilise CU for their dramatic effects.

CU is effectively used in *Àmìn Ọrun*. A close-up of Rísí after Wọlé (O'Jay) had proposed friendship to her reveals her infatuation for him in spite of her friend's (Sènábù) warning. The smile and happiness on Risi's face suggest her interest in Wọlé. On the other hand, however, a close-up shot of Wọlé when attacked by the contract killers sent by Sènábu to avenge his ill – treatment of Rísí reveals his trepidation and anguish. A chosen detail of his reaction to this action through a close-up helps to establish his psychological state in a dramatic way.

In *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀*, close-up is artistically employed to illustrate eloquently the sundry details of the vistas of the scene where Ọtún's nightmares are presented. The fear of Ọtun is revealed after dreaming that the ghosts of Ajíbádé (JP) and Sànyà are pursuing him. When the ghosts are about to seize him in the dream, he wakes up suddenly from sleep with a shrill. The palpitation of his heart is presented with the aid of a close-up to reveal his anguish at the most critical moment.

A more comprehensible analysis of Tẹ̀là's interior preoccupation and the various emotions of his wives come into focus in *Òbúkọ́ Dúdú* when Tẹ̀là discloses his knowledge of his junior wife's pregnancy. While Tẹ̀là's mood shows extreme disappointment in Mojí's infidelity, that of the senior wife reveals her consternation for her co-wife's unsavoury behaviour. A further close-up on Mojí, the culprit, suggests the turmoil going on in her mind.

CU in *Ó Le Kú* is skilfully used to create an indepth analysis of the characters and designates evidently something of importance to the narration. The CU of Àjàní and Àṣàké as they sit in the dark at the 'Èrẹ̀bẹ̀' night discussing is to impress upon us their inner condition as regards Àjàní's confession of his love for Àṣàké and her scepticism about Àjàní's proposal. Their reactions to this discussion are observed as a CU shot of the two lovers is brought into focus.

Apart from revealing emotions, a CU shot of a character may be utilised for the purpose of the audience's comprehension of an important speech made by such character. This is what the producer

tries to achieve in *Ó Le Kú* by presenting the CU shots of Àjàní each time he renders his love verses for each of his lovers.

4.1.2 Camera Angle

Camera angles are compensatory as they bridge the audience's physical distance from the action and approximate real life situations. The high and low angles, which are the two possibilities, are cleverly utilised in some Yorùba video films under our consideration for aesthetic effects.

In *Ó Le Kú*, the arrival of Àjàní at his house, shot through the space between the two branches of a tree, and from a high angle is very artistic and novel. The audience fascinatingly watch this spectacle from the rear of a tree and through the space between its branches. The shot of Dòtun also, as he goes out of Lọlá's house and Lọlá's coming in is taken from a vantage position. From an elevated position, the shot is taken inside the house bringing into focus the entrance for

us to watch the coincidental meeting of Dòtun and Lọlá by the door. Lọlá's unsavoury attitude to Dòtun is also captured from this position.

In *Àmìn Ọrun*, a low-angle shot coupled with a close-up is employed to make Tómi's mother image large and overbearing on the screen while at the balcony giving instruction to Ajírèbi, her gate-keeper to lock out Wọlé.

In *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ* (1) and *Ó Le Kú* (1), the aerial shots of Abéòkúta and Ìbàdàn cities respectively are taken to give hints about the locations of the films. In the shots, the rusty roof tops of the two historic towns are brought into focus to reveal their ancientness.

4.1.3 **Sound**

We have already identified three types of sound in Yorùbá video films, namely, sound proper, dialogue and music (see 2.1.2.). Apart from dialogue which will be treated under linguistic devices, our focus here will be on sound proper and music.

4.1.3.1 Sound Proper

Sound proper is any auditory material apart from music and speech recorded for motion pictures. It includes imitative sounds, as of thunder, car, birds or an explosion. Generally, sound proper in motion pictures reinforces the pictorial communication. When they do so, they induce us to watch closely the mood of the action on the screen.

In *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀*, the horrific sound of the supernaturals opens the film. The darkness from where it emanates from, signifies the Yoruba belief that supernaturals abide in the dark and in the forest. A close-up on one of these weird elements as they file out to consume the sacrifices offered them further confirms our assumption.

In the events that follow, the ululation of the birds introduces us to the source of the sound as we later see the birds perching on a tree in a virgin land which Sànyà tries to convince Mr Johnson to purchase for the industry he is trying to set up.

A sound can become symbolic of certain character or an object. The character or object is first introduced with the aid of such sound and as the film progresses, it becomes a permanent identificatory mark.

For instance, in *Taxi Driver*, the sound of Tundé's taxi cab signifies its presence. The sound becomes synonymous with the taxi for each time we hear it, we expect the emergence of the cab.

In the Yorùba video film, there are other sounds that are puzzling and ominous. These sounds are functionally employed to introduce dangerous situations and create suspense. Whenever they are used, they overwhelm our consciousness and arouse our feelings.

Òtun's nightmares in *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀* are always introduced by a puzzling sound. The constant use of the sound familiarises us with his dreams which arouse feelings of intense fear, horror and distress. Once the sound is played, we expect to see Òtún being pursued by the ghosts of Sànyà and JP.

Death in *Ọrun Móoru* is introduced with a deafening 'whoosh-whoosh' sound. As Bàba Sàlá breaks the second gourd that he has been instructed by the river goddess to keep, this heart-breaking sound is introduced. As it dies down, the image of death appears on the screen towering over the audience.

4.1.3.2 Music

All lyrics, songs and tunes vocally and/or instrumentally produced fall under music.

Music in the Yorùbá video films performs three major functions. Firstly, it comments on the actions on the screen. Secondly, it entertains and thirdly, it reiterates the theme(s) of the story. Music that falls under this last category is culturally denotative and constructive. It also has didactic values as the moral lesson it tries to impart is either direct or implied.

The songs in *Kòṣeégbe* are topical. They contribute to the psychological advancement of the action and the intensification of the climax. The recurrent background music: *Ó ṣe é gbé nà? Kòṣeégbe'* (Can it (task) be accomplished? It cannot) serves as the nucleus of the film. It suggests the dimension or enormity of the task Máko, the protagonist has set for himself. Whenever the music is relayed, it advances or corroborates the event it accompanies and as we listen to it, we see Máko in one difficulty or another and we are left with

pessimism or optimism about his bid to surmount the problem(s). In the same film also, the song 'Alákàn yíí rọra' (This crab, beware) employed by Mako's antagonists is to warn him to take things easy in dealing with them or be ready for confrontation:

Alákàn yíí rọra!

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

Alákàn yíí rọra!

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

Ìwọ ká, èmí ká!

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

Tèmi ẹ lè dèpè

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

Èpè kan ò pahun!

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

Pónpóladiḡ ní wọ̀nkúwọ

Bó dìjà, bó dítà

Èmi ò ní sá!

This crab, beware!

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

This crab, beware!

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

You pluck, I pluck!

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

How can mine become a curse

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

No curse can harm the tortoise

Kín-ìn-rín-jin-gbin

The crooked sticks have been bound together as cudgels

If it turns to a fight, if it becomes rowdy

I will not run.

The songs in *Àmìn Ọrun* are both thematic and commentative.

They restate certain needs, tendencies or meanings of the picture they accompany. In addition to intimating the audience with the nature of the story, the songs also assume the cinematic function of underscoring discreetly some of their implications.

The music exemplified below underscores the difficulty and perplexity of life such as the one that confronted Rí sí. It reminds us that some of the problems confronting man in life are caused by evil

doers who of course do not go unpunished. As we listen to this music intermittently, our mind is prepared for the inevitable end of Wọlé:

Làásìgbò! Làásìgbò ayé
 B'Élédùmarè bá dákẹ́ dájọ́
 A jẹ pé bóyá aṣebi á jẹgba
 Aṣebi ò ní lọ láìjẹgba
 Làásìgbò! Làásìgbò ayé

Trouble! Trouble of life
 If God silently passes judgement
 It means the evil doer may be punished
 The wicked will not go unpunished
 Trouble! Trouble of life.

The song employed for the scene where Rísí breaks the news of her pregnancy to Wọlé's bewilderment comments on Wọlé's action and its expectant result:

Orí ọkẹrẹ́ konko láwo.
 Bá a wí fọmọ ẹni,
 Yiyẹ ló yẹ kó gbọ.

Ori òkéré konko láwo.

The head of the squirrel is big in the plate.

If a child is warned,

He should take heed.

The head of the squirrel is big in the plate.

Wọlé's misdeed and obstinacy are likened to the proverbial disobedient squirrel who, despite several warnings from its mother, goes to the farm in search of food and ends up in the farmer's pot.

The song that opens *Òbúkọ Dúdú* is also thematic and provides information about the nature and content of its plot:

Òbúkọ dúdú ni baba e dáràn nílé ọlá.

Òbúkọ dúdú ni wọn lò, tó tún gbẹsan.

Èké ò léyìn, ire ni ẹ jẹ á mọ ọ ẹ.

Mọ ẹ kà o.

Ọré dákun mọ mọ yájú mọ.

Ọré dákun dábò mọ ẹbi.

Èdùmàrè ní bẹ lókè.

Tí ó gbẹsan ohun gbogbo.

It is the black he-goat that the old man used to cause trouble in a rich man's house.

It is the black he-goat that was used in revenge.

Hypocrisy is not beneficial, let us do good.

Do not be wicked.

Friend, please do not be insolent again.

Friend, please I beg you, do not be wicked.

The Almighty God dwells above who will avenge all ungodliness.

In the film, Adẹ̀rùpọ̀kọ̀ had been sacked on Kúnlé's advice to his father.

Adẹ̀rùpọ̀kọ̀ then uses a black he-goat to charm Kúnlé to misbehave

through having an affair with Mojí, his father's wife. His father, Tẹ̀là

soon discovers that Mojí is pregnant for Kúnlé. The two miscreants are

banished but their suffering ends when Mojí acting on the instruction of

an ifá priest takes to Adẹ̀rùpọ̀kọ̀ the type of he-goat he had used for the

charm. In the process, Adẹ̀rùpọ̀kọ̀ becomes mad. The song therefore

summarises the storyline and points the moral.

The songs in *Ìyá Ni Wúrà* are both thematic and entertaining.

The thematic song advances the plot of the narrative :

Ìyá o ni wúrà ọmọ láyé.

Níjọ rírí jẹ,

Níjọ àìrí jẹ,

Níjọ rírí mu,

Níjọ àìrí mu,

Ìyá mi mo şè rántí rẹ.

Mother is gold to the child.

When there is food to eat,

When there is none to eat,

When there is water to drink,

When there is none to drink,

My mother, I remember you.

The lyrics of the song rendered by Kẹhìndé who has been separated from his mother and twin brother since childhood are based on the title of the film. The import of the song is the agony of missing his caring mother.

The second song in the film is used by Kẹ̀hìndé to entertain the children who are inmates of the orphanage where he had lived and trained as a musician. He had been invited to perform so as to enliven the spirit of these children:

Èyin ọmọdẹ, ẹ gbọkàn lólúwa.

Gbọkàn lé Ọlórún ọbá ọga ògo.

Òun lọba tó dá ẹ.

Òun lọba.

Èyin ọmọdẹ ẹ gbọkàn lólúwà.

Children, trust in the Lord.

Trust in the Lord, the Almighty.

He is the God who creates you.

He is the glorious king.

You children, trust in the Lord.

Ó Le Kú, perhaps, is the only Yorùbá video film that employs quite a lot of commentative music which not only induces the audience, but invites them to enjoy amusing analogies which have all the traits of a literary aperçu.² Most of the time, in the film, use is made of songs on

disc whose themes are relevant to some occasions like birthday, wedding, etc. For instance, tracks like Ebenezer Obey's 'Happy Birthday' and 'Ètò Ìgbéyàwó' are played to suit the birthday and wedding ceremonies in the film. Most of the time, the pictures in the film are reinforced by the message of the songs that accompany them. The configuration of visuals determine the selection of the song intended to reflect their mood and meanings. Apart from being commentative, these tracks are employed in *Ó Le Ku* to depict the period of setting.

There are instances where Yorùbá traditional musical ensembles are used for instrumentation in the Yorùbá video film. In this case, the instruments are applied in the performance of some actions. For instance, in films like *Èkùró Olójà*, *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀*, *Òrìṣà* among others, the ushering in of the Kábiyèsí is preceded by the use of instruments in the dundun ensemble.³

In *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀*, the fast tempo bata sound is used at the height of confrontation. The sound introduces the climactic clash between Ọtún and members of Ajíbádé's family at Ajíbádé's funeral.

The sound adds potency to Ọtún's movement and heightens his frenzy as he moves to forestall the burial ceremony.

4.1.4 Lighting

In this study, we have found Adélékè's definition of the functions of lighting in films invaluable.⁴ He has said that lighting in films provides four basic functions. First, it highlights the theme(s) in a film. Second, it differentiates between day and night. Third, it gives scenes realistic and expressive effect and fourth, it creates compositional effect by evolving a pictorial balance among the different objects in the scene.

Lighting in *Kòṣéégbé* and *Àmìn Ọrun* is used for chiaroscuro effects. The condition of Sílífá's living room in anticipation of Máko's arrival and the interrogation room where Professor Kásúmù is questioned for impropriety are pertinent examples respectively. Light and shade in these scenes are so arranged for pictorial representation.

Apart from the producers' handling of character and plot which sustains the audience's interest, *Ó Le Kú*, *Kòṣéégbé*, *Àmìn Ọrun* and

Owo Blow among others, have been noted for their luxuriant and opulent images of the characters and objects through consistent expressionistic lighting. Struck by the reality of the film images which appeal to their sensitivity, the audience cannot help reacting to them as they would to nature. In *Ó Le Kú*, for instance, the use of expressionistic lighting in presenting the University of Ibadan tower at the opening of the film is an experiment in artistic excellence. With a blue background, the tower, illuminated through light, glows in its white colour. The portrait shot of Arówòlò in scene three of *Kòṣéégbe* also establishes its aesthetic quality. A most quintessentially absorptive posture of Arówòlò in a cool blue-violet background is presented through the use of expressionistic lighting. The blue hues of his dress glow in the surrounding penumbra as if it contains its own source of illumination.

Darkness or night in Yorùbá video films is depicted through the use of shade or obscurity and this is achieved during production by the interception of rays or the diminishing of light. Contrastingly, a shot of the rising sun and the brightness of light introduce a new day. In 77

Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀, for instance, the scene where the spirits appear at night and the commencement of work on Mr Johnson's site at the beginning of a new day which immediately follow the night spectacle are contrastive.

4.1.5 **Interior Monologue and Simultaneous Montage**

In films, interior monologue is usually accompanied by simultaneous montage to depict the dimension of the character's mental preoccupation. While interior monologue is the technique that reproduces the course and rhythm of consciousness as it occurs in a character's mind (Abrams 1981 :187), simultaneous montage involves the showing of shots simultaneously one on top of the other. One of the effects of simultaneous montage is its reflection of how connections between objects or events could be induced by optical juxtaposition.

In *Kòşéégbé*, a confused and depressed Máko is brought into focus as he opens the envelope that contains the photographs of his illicit love affair with Sílífá. In this confused state, the producer undertakes to capture the spectrum and flow of his mental process by

imposing on Máko's image the events that had happened in Sílífá's house.

The reflections or thoughts of Òtun after the king had given his consent to Ajíbádé's family to bury him in *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ* are also imposed on his image. Òtún's posture reflects a man whose perception mingles with conscious and half-conscious thoughts, memories, expectations and feelings. The shot of his encounter with the ifá priest and the latter's warning about the consequences of burying Ajíbádé's corpse are brought into focus. The priest had earlier warned him that the only thing that can prevent his death is that Ajíbádé's corpse should not be buried.

In her moment of utmost despair, Rísí's flow of thought about the pains, agonies and suffering she received in the hands of Wolé is presented in *Àmìn Ọrun*. The effect of this is to heighten our anger at Wolé for his unwholesome attitude to Rísí. Visualising these incidents as they occur from Rísí's thoughts has resonance effect. It provokes in the audience kinaesthetic response.

In interior monologue, it is the character's thought that is brought into focus through the use of superimposition or simultaneous montage. One function of interior monologue is that it helps the audience to have a good perception of the inner mind of the character(s) as it gives them hint(s) about the character's reflection and his psychological depth.

4.1.6 **Artificial Lyricism/Optical Trickery**

This device involves a contrived concatenation of several individual shots to present certain events that could have been difficult to act out. When professionally handled, it would seem as if the audience is faced with a physical reality of such events.

In *Òrun Móoru*, for example, artificial lyricism is employed to present death. As Bàba Sàlá breaks the second gourd in anticipation of stupendous wealth, an apparition moves out from the gourd. As it moves out from the frame, it turns to a weird figure clad in black apparel holding a cudgel. This is a mental image of death in the Yorùbá cultural milieu.

Two important overwhelming events in *Àmìn Ọrun* are presented with the aid of artificial lyricism. The first is the presentation of the battered image of Rísí soaked in her own blood when hit by a vehicle and the other is Wọlé's face soaked in his own blood after he had been beaten up by hoodlums.

Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀ relies on the same trick to put across hints about the supernatural. Its recourse to this device in presenting the ghosts of Ajíbáde and Sànyà pursuing and dragging Ọtún is designed to bring out the character of the supernatural elements.

This device is also employed in *Òbúkọ Dúdú* to demonstrate the supernatural prowess of Tẹ̀là's mother-in-law. Şıyanbólá and the woman disappear to emerge later in the forest where the latter had taken him to show him the secret behind Tẹ̀là's wealth.

In *Ìyá Ni Wúra*, Kẹ̀hìndé's miraculous escape from his attackers who had been contracted by 'Chairman' (Léré Pàimọ) to kill him is achieved through artificial lyricism. At the point of being struck with a rod, he is lifted to the top of a nearby car after the shout of halleluyah.

This gimmick is utilised to demonstrate the power of God and this makes his attackers take to their heels.

In conclusion, it has been observed that this device is very handy in films that centre on a culture which believes in the co-existence of the supernatural and the natural.

4.1.7 **Flashback/Cutback**

The filmic time is subject to the producer's discretion who may expand or condense it. The flashback or cutback is a narrative device that is usually employed to expand the filmic time for it recalls past experiences or incidents. It relays a scene which has already taken place in the past with the purpose of helping the audience to understand the story better.

In *Kòṣeégbě*, Máko's insolence to an importer which was narrated by Dọlá to Málíkì, Arówólò and co is presented as a flashback. Àjẹpé's story about the unknown visitor sent by Málíkì and co to bribe him and Máko is also presented through this device.

A flashback is also used to interrupt the narrative in *Òbúkọ́ Dúdú* in order to recall and offer a vivid and visual description of how Tẹ̀lẹ̀'á's mother-in-law used her supernatural power to enrich him. This spectacle provides more information about Tẹ̀lẹ̀'á's background for our proper assessment of him in the unfolding events. Furthermore, this device throws more light on the mystery surrounding Tẹ̀lẹ̀'á's wealth.

The story of Kẹ̀hìndé's separation from his mother and twin brother is unfolded in *Ìyá Ní Wúrà* after the happy re-union of the trio. With this, Kẹ̀hìndé is opportuned to have a first hand information about the reason for the unfortunate event.

In flashback, the audience is able to visualise retroactively a past event which adds value to the development of the story. The function of this device is that it is used to interrupt a narrative in order to portray or recount an incident or scene from the past for a comprehension of the total story.

4.1.8

Dream Device

Mariam et. al. (1963 :253) defines dream as a series of thoughts, images or emotions occurring during sleep and a visionary creation of the imagination. This device is employed by artists to establish the pungency of certain issues in the minds of their characters. At times, dream could serve as premonition about certain future events. This means that what will happen in the future is revealed to the character through the dream.

The purpose of dream in *Ọrun Móoru* is to explore the workings of the mind of a poor man to such an extent that Bàbá Sàlá, the poor man, even though he is poor still has his life to thank God for.

In *Ó Le Kú* also, the dream explores the mind of Àjàní's mother over her anxiety about her son's marriage. On the other hand, the song in Àjàní's dream establishes his dilemma on the choice of a partner. The song in the dream is a clear manifestation of Àjàní who is in a quandary as to what he should do:

Ebi n pa mí, mo gbé su léná.

Òungbẹ n gbẹ mí, mo gbágbè dódò.

Kí n tó dé'lé ẹran ti fişu jẹ.

Kí ni n ó wa jẹ?

Kí ni n ó wa jẹ?

Kí ni n ó wa jẹ?

Àfi gààrí Alábẹkẹ.

I was hungry and I put yam on fire.

I was thirsty and I took the gourd to the stream.

Before I returned home, the goat has eaten all the yam.

What will I eat?

What will I eat?

What will I eat?

Unless the 'gaari' of Àbẹkẹ.

The song is an analogy of how in his quest to satisfy his desires, Àjàní encounters bigger tasks. The rhetorical questions are tantamount to mental challenge and stress, uncertainty or anxiety over reaching a decision.

Dream in *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ* serves a premonitory purpose. Ọtún in his dream is chased by Sànyà and Ajibádé's ghosts. Through the dream, he is alerted to an impending danger. To forestall this, he

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consults the Ifá priest who establishes the cause of the problem and offers him a temporary solution.

From the instances above, we may conclude that dream seems to explore the mind or the psyche of the character. Most times, dreams are products of psychological influences and owing to their indeterminacy, films that dwell on them may arise from the agitated inner environment. The dream images may recreate or mobilise the audience previously repressed fears or induce the spectators to revel on a prospective wish-fulfilment.

4.1.9 Time Management

While flashback expands the filmic time, time management condenses it. There are two methods of depicting time management in the Yorùbá video film. The first is through the indication of dates or time on the screen while the second is presented by showing the image of a younger person who immediately metamorphosed into an older person.

Films that make use of the first method include *Àmìn Ọ̀run* and *Owo Blow*. In *Àmìn Ọ̀run*, the audience is propelled into future events on three different occasions. After Wọ̀lé and Rísí had sexual intercourse, we are launched into seeing Rísí expecting Wọ̀lé's baby 'four months later'. Immediately after Wọ̀lé's denial of being responsible for the pregnancy, we are propelled into seeing Wọ̀lé as a qualified medical doctor 'four years later'. As soon as Wọ̀lé and Tómi, his wife, left for abroad with Ẹ̀niitàn, we see them back in Nigeria 'after twenty years'. This device also occurs extensively in *Owo Blow* where it is applied on five occasions. As in *Àmìn Ọ̀run*, inscriptions of these periods are always provided on the screen. For instance, 'after six months' of Mr Owólabí's imprisonment, problems set into his family as Wọ̀lé, his brilliant son drops out of school because of his mother's inability to pay his Junior Secondary School Examination fees. Apart from this, it becomes impossible for the family to get its basic needs. After losing Chima his friend, who had accommodated him under the bridge, we are launched into the events that happened 'three days later' when Wọ̀lé

meets Jéjé, his old school friend. Later in the film, we are propelled to see Wólé 'after many years' as the leader of a gang of armed robbers. 'After two years' that Wólé had left the gang, two of its members are caught while carrying out an operation. The arrival of Jéjé 'a week' after Wólé had won the case of his alleged involvement in armed robbery is the climax to the denouement of the story as Jéjé innocuously provides the information needed by the Investigating Police Officer (IPO) to nail Wólé.

The second type of time management, however, is adopted in *Ìyá Ni Wúrà*. The method is rather stylish or skilful as the backs of teenage Táíwò and Kẹ̀hìndé are first presented to the audience and as they turn to face the camera, a blur changes their images to a young lawyer and a young musician respectively.

By employing time management, the producers condense the history of their protagonists and present to us their compendia that are relevant to their (producers') plot.

4.1.10 **Suspense**

Suspense is the anxiety or apprehension resulting from an uncertain, undecided or mysterious situation. According to Abrams (1981 :138) suspense:

arouses expectations in the audience or reader about the future course of events, and how characters will respond to events. An anxious uncertainty about what is going to happen, especially to those characters whose qualities are such that we have established a bond of sympathy with them, is known as suspense.

Suspense is created right from the time conflict is introduced into a narrative until its resolution. Apart from this, the various events in a plot also create anxiety or apprehension. Dawson (1970 :30) similarly submits that:

all works of art are fully grasped through the perception of the interrelatedness of their parts, and in drama the relation between parts is characteristically one of tension.

The underlying continuous tension, is that between the situation at any given moment and the complete action. Suspense is one of the commonest devices in Yorùbá video films. It pervades their various plots. A few examples will be given to lend credence to this view

In *Àmìn Òrun*, the treatment of suspense towards the end of the film is quite fascinating. With the decision of Rísí to attend Èniitàn's wedding and prove her filial ties, various questions trouble the mind – how is she going to achieve this? What will be the implication of her action? Will she succeed? Will she fail? From here the plot moves rapidly towards the climax. Rísí's accident further provokes kinaesthetic response in us. Respite, however, comes later when we discover that she did not die afterall. The conflict is later resolved and harmony achieved as mother and child later reunite after several years of separation.

Our second example is from *Taxi Driver*. In the film, Túndé's curiosity leads him to a secluded place where he discovers the activities of a gang that specialises in the use of human beings for money-making rituals. As he discreetly observes their operation from his hiding place,

a member of the gang gets the instinct that they are being watched. As he tries to find out and approaches the spot where Tundé is hiding, the spectator becomes apprehensive and thinks of the implication of his arrest. His anxiety is doused when the member of the gang misses the spot thinly.

The use of puzzling and ominous sound is quite evident in the presentation of suspense in Yorùbá video films. Such a sound is used to introduce dangerous situations and create suspense. When it is used, the sound arouses feelings of intense fear, horror and distress in the audience (See 4.1.3.1).

One hallmark of the use of suspense in the Yorùbá video film is the discreet knowledge of the producers on how long to maintain it without becoming unbearable or tedious, and how it can be broken with maximum effect.

By this device, the producers always re-establish our knowledge of the convention that, come what may, the hero or heroine must survive. This suggests why atimes we usually prepare for the possibility

of surprise and the probability of the protagonist's success despite the difficult or dangerous situation facing him.

4.1.11 Limitations

So far, we have considered the technical production devices employed in Yorùbá video films. Of all these techniques, it seems as if artificial lyricism or optical trickery (especially in the handling of the supernatural) and the synchronization of image with sound have not been perfected in the production of Yorùbá video films.

In *Ọrun Móoru*, for instance, the technique used in presenting Babá Sàlá's adventure in the supernatural world is flawed. In the scene where Babá Sàlá encounters the water spirits, his photograph is superimposed on the artificial world of the spirits. Presenting dummies as water spirits and as real figures raises a moot problem. Although, the water spirits are staged and manipulated so skilfully that they evoke the illusion of being real, the artificiality of the setting of the spirit world invalidates this reality. The magic of presentation wears off easily as the spectators soon recognise it as trick and disparage it accordingly.

Arising from the above, we may therefore conclude that perhaps, owing to lack of technical expertise, the Yorùbá video film producers are yet to work out more authentic form of presenting the world of the supernaturals.

In some of the Yorùbá video film also, the sound and the picture, at times, do not synchronise. For instance, the background thematic music 'Alákàn yǐi rọra' (This crab, beware) in *Kòṣeégbé* does not synchronise with the rendition of the lyrics by Málíkì and Arówólò. The rendition of the characters, though it is calculated to trap us into believing that they themselves render the song, breaks down because a slight shift of the camera makes us realise abruptly that the song is recorded and relayed through a record player.

Similarly, in *Òbúkọ Dúdú*, the relay of the recorded incantation which is also rendered by Mojí does not synchronise. The sound and Mojí's voice are not properly arranged for parallel occurrence.

The presentation of local setting as foreign is another issue that suggests that the Yorùbá video film industry still has a long way to go. It has become increasingly difficult to shoot films having foreign setting

in their original environment. Rather than visiting the country to shoot the film, such as what obtains in Hollywood films, they (producers) resort to creating artificial location to present the illusion of the reality that the scene(s) in the films actually take place in foreign countries.⁵ A case in point is *Ogun Àtílẹwá* where images of the London city and the tower of London are presented through editing devices to open the scene where Máýòwá resumes in the London office of his company as the Managing Director. In the same vein, Goodluck's mere boarding of a plane that moves on the tarmac is intended to indicate his foreign musical trip in *Ìyá Ni Wúrà*.

Perhaps, finance is responsible for some of these flaws. Finance has been the bane of the development of the film industry in Nigeria. Producers need a huge amount of money to produce their films and ensure that their quality is up to Hollywood standard. The general economic recession in Nigeria has made film funding a mirage and this has virtually crippled film production.

4.2 THE YORÙBÁ VIDEO FILM AS TEXT : LINGUISTIC DEVICES

We have looked at what make a story a film story. Now, we are going to look at the video film as text with a consideration of the linguistic description of the text.

Language has the unique role of capturing the breadth of human thought and endeavour. It expresses world views and ways of life of the people who own it. The most widely recognised function of language is that it is used for communication purposes. It is employed to communicate our ideas, exchange facts or opinions. The use of language is often referred to as 'referential', 'prepositional' or 'ideational'. Since language is the primary medium of communication among characters in the Yorùba video films, it should therefore be the primary object of linguistic study.

4.2.1 Prologue and Epilogue

While prologue is the lines introducing a play, epilogue is a short addition or concluding section at the end of a literary work, often dealing with the future of its character(s).

prologue is used in *Àmìn Ọrun, Tí Olúwa Ní Ilẹ̀* and *Ogun Àtílẹ̀wá* among others while *Kòṣeégbé* perhaps is the only video film that utilises both prologue and epilogue.

Kòṣeégbé opens with a prologue which gives the audience an insight into the nature of what they are about to see. The prologue provides some hints of intention :

Taa ló le tún lẹ̀ yí ẹ̀?

Olóòótọ̀ ò lẹ̀ní

Aṣẹbi ò lónìbẹ̀rù.

Who will reform this country?

The honest is not welcome.

The dishonest fears no one.

This device makes the audience eager to see the events of these conflicting remarks. The film also ends with an epilogue which talks about the aftermath of the arrest of Mako's opponent and what happened to Mako thereafter:

Mako ò ku o.

Àwon aṣebi ló lọ sewọn.

Ehoro máa sáré nìso.

Ajá n bọ lẹyin.

Mako is not dead.

It is the wicked ones that have gone to jail.

Hare! Continue to run,

The dog is after you.

In *Àmìn Òrun*, the prologue says what we are about to see is 'a true life story' while in *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀*, the title of the film is derived from a biblical reference which serves as its prologue :

Ti Olúwa ni ilẹ̀ àti ẹkun rẹ.

Ayé àti àwọ̀n tí ó tẹ̀dọ̀ sínú rẹ

The earth is the Lord's and the fullness thereof

The world and those who dwell therein

(Psalm 24 :1 RSV)

Similarly, the prologue in *Ogun Àtíléwá* is taken from a biblical reference which gives us a hint about the nature of the film.

Àti gégé bí wọn ti kò láti ni ìmò
 Ọlórún, Ọlórún ti fi wọn fún iyè ríra
 láti ẹ ohun tí kò tọ.

And even as they did not like to retain God in their knowledge, God gave them over to a reprobate mind, to do those things which are not right (Romans 1 Vs 28 NIV).

As pointed out earlier, prologue is employed by the Yorùbá video film producers to give an insight into the nature of their films. The epilogue on the other hand, gives us hint about the future of the character(s) in the films.

4.2.2 Soliloquy

Soliloquy is the act of talking to oneself, silently or loudly. This device according to Abrams (1981 :180) denotes the convention by

which a character, alone on the stage, utters his thoughts aloud. One of the functions of soliloquy is that it is used to convey directly to the audience information about a character's motives, intentions and state of mind.

In *Kòṣeégbé*, Máko on two occasions soliloquises on his precarious situation. When he is informed about Sálú's arrest for possessing indian hemp, he demonstrates a distressful state by putting his hands on his head. His monologue conveys his state of mind:

Orí mi ẹ̀lẹ̀dàá mi. Irú u kí wá nìyí? Lásìkò tíṣẹ̀
wà lówọ́ mi, ni Sálù tún lọ dáràn wálé. Ha!
Ara ohun tí ì jẹ̀ sẹ̀ o ẹ̀eṣe rẹ̀ é o. Má jẹ̀ á gbọ́
gbogbo, kì ì jẹ̀sẹ̀ ọ̀ lọ déédé.

My God! My creator! What nonsense is this that at a timewhen I have many commitments, Salu has committed a serious offence. Ah! This is one of those things that make one's wish unfulfilled. Secret things make one's work unprogressive.

A confused and depressed Máko is also brought into focus as he opens the envelope that contains the photographs of his illicit love affair with Sálífa. In this confused state, he soliloquizes through a prose that is laced with interrogatives and exclamatory remarks:

Yéè! Mo gbé! kín nìyí? Fótò èmi àti Sílifá!
 Nìhòhò! Á à! Á à! Á à! Irú u kín nìyí
 Ọlórún? Irú u kín lèyí? Şebí mo gba
 kámèrà yẹn lójó yẹn lẹhùn ún? Níbo ni
 eléyí ti wá? Kín ni mo şe yíi? Báwo ni
 mo şe gò tó báyíi? Yéèèè!

Yea! I am finished! What is this? My photographs with Sílifá! Nude! Ah! Ah! Ah! God, what nonsense is this? What type of a thing is this? But I seized that camera that day. What is the source of this? What is this that I have done? Why was I so stupid? Yea!

The use of soliloquy here gives a good picture of the inner state of Máko. He is scared of the implications of his actions.

Soliloquy is presented in a more dramatic form in *Àmìn Ọrun*. As Rísí hears the announcement of Ẹniitàn's wedding programme on the radio, her reaction is captured in a close-up : surprised and confused. While ruminating over the news, another close-up shot of Ẹniitàn's photograph hanging on the wall comes into focus to disclose her object of thought. The succession of shots of Ẹniitàn is simply designed to intimate us with the subject matter of Rísí's thoughts. Suddenly, like a robot, she leaves her seat and moves slowly to where the photograph is hung. She removes it and with a full concentration on it, she retreats slowly to her seat before presenting her agony in a soliloquy:

Eniitàn! Ẹniitàn mi Àjìkẹ́. Ọmọ Àjùmòbì ò kan
 tàánú. Ẹniitàn, o fẹ́ sẹ̀gbeyàwó, lójú ayé mi, ẹni
 ẹlẹni dẹ́ fẹ́ gbà ẹ́ è mi ẹ́. Ẹniitan Àjìkẹ́, èmi ni
 mo bí ẹ́. Èmi ni ìyá ẹ́. Lójú ayé mi, ẹlòmíi á jókòó
 fọmó tí mo bí.

Eniitan! my Ẹniitàn, Àjike. The daughter of Àjùmòbí ò kan tàánú. Ẹniitan, you want to wed. In my life time, another person wants to usurp my responsibilities. Eniitan, Àjike, I gave birth to you. I am your mother. In my life time, another person will stand as a mother to my daughter.

This device is employed to present to us the indescribable sadness of Rísí as reflected in the despair behind her monologue.

Àjàní's soliloquy immediately after his dream in *Ó Le Kú* is a manifestation of his predicament over his choice of a wife. He broods over the dream :

Ha! Àlá ni m̀d̀ ǹ l`á ni. Àlá ọ̀san, k̀ò yémi o.
 Ọ̀lọ̀run ni ǹ fi ǹnkan p̀úp̀ọ̀ pam̀ọ̀ f̀édàá. Ẹ́ ...?
 Àbí...? Ó dá a ... Ta wá ló yẹ kí ǹ f̀ẹ́ báyíi?
 Hún-un!

Ah! I have been dreaming. Day dreaming. I cannot understand. It is God that hides so

many things from man. Do ...? Or...? It's okay.
Who now do I marry?

The broken flow of thought in Àjani's mind describes his dilemma on the issue of choice.

When the Managing Director position in the London office of his Company continues to elude Adéwálé in *Ogun Àtílẹwá* despite his use of supernatural powers and the assurances of the 'jùjú' man, he reveals his thoughts in a monologue:

Kí ló dé tí wọ̀n ní láti tún gbé Mr. Máyòwá lọ jẹ MD London office? Wọ̀n tún wá fi Mr. Martins jẹ MD Lagos office. Kí ló dé? Kí ló dé? Kí ló dé? Lẹ̀yìn gbogbo ètùtù tí mo ẹ̀ lọ̀dọ̀ bàbá yẹ̀n. Kí ló dé?

Why again did they make Mr Mayowa the MD of the London office? And again make Mr. Martins the MD of Lagos office Why? Why? Why? After all the sacrifices the juju man told me to make. Why?

The use of 'why' interjectionally by Adéwálé expresses his puzzle and surprise about not being favoured for the London position in spite of spending a huge sum of money on 'jùju'.

As earlier pointed out, it is the protagonist's thoughts that are focused in most cases when soliloquy is used. One function of this device is that it helps the audience to have a good perception of the inner mind of the character(s) as it gives them hints about the character's reflection and a peep into the psychological depth of the character.

4.2.3 Use of Mass Media

The use of mass media (electronic and print) is evident in Yorùbá video films. This device reduces the length of a story and provides information that is crucial to the narration.

In *Ó Le Kú*, a television broadcast, for instance, informs Àṣàké and her parents about Àjàní's marriage. The information came as a news item. The language of the news item presents to us the images of the wedding ceremony.

Ayeye Ìgbéyàwó

Gongó sọ ní ìlú Ìbàdàn lónii, sẹ̀gẹ̀dẹ̀ sẹ̀, akutukú ku, pépéyẹ̀ sì pamọ̀ níbi ayeye Ìgbéyàwó tí wọn ẹ̀ ní ilé ìsìn nílá àwọn ẹ̀lẹ̀sìn Kírìstì ní Yunifásitì tí Ìbàdàn. Ìgbéyàwó nàà wáyé láàrin ọ̀dọ̀mọ̀kúnrin amọ̀bíọ̀jọ̀ kan tí orúkọ rẹ̀ ní jẹ̀ Àjàní ọ̀mọ̀ Ajámásàn-án àti omidan ẹ̀lẹ̀yinjúegẹ̀ kan tí orúkọ rẹ̀ ní jẹ̀ Sádé, ọ̀mọ̀ gbajúmọ̀ olówó o ní tí gbogbo ènìyàn mọ̀ sí Ajénifújà. Bí iyàwó tí n rẹ̀rìn in músè bẹ̀ẹ̀ ní ọ̀kọ̀ rẹ̀ nàà ní bẹ̀yín kẹ̀ tí àwọn méjèèjì sì ní fi ẹ̀nu ko ra wọn lẹ̀nu lóòrẹ̀kóòrẹ̀. Nígba tí ayeye nàà dé góngó, àwọn ọ̀rẹ̀ Àjàní tí wọn jọ̀ wà nínu ẹ̀gbẹ̀ kan tí wọn ní pẹ̀ ní Páréètì fi ẹ̀yẹ̀ dá tọ̀kọ̀taya nàà sí. Wọn wọ̀ aṣọ̀ ẹ̀gbẹ̀ wọn, wọn sì ní rìn kiri, wọn dúró wámú, wọn sì fi orí idà wọn kọ̀ ara wọn, kí àwọn tọ̀kọ̀taya nàà lè gba abẹ̀ àwọn idà wọn yí kọ̀já. A sàdúrà fún tọ̀kọ̀taya nàà pé, ẹ̀yìn iyàwó kò ní mọ̀ ẹ̀ní. Iyàwó yóò bí ọ̀sàn, iyàwó yóò bí ọ̀ro o. Àmín o.

Wedding Ceremony

Ibadan town was enlivened today when a wedding ceremony took place at the University of Ibadan Chapel. The holy solemnisation was between a fair complexion young man, Àjàní the son of Ajámásan-án and a bright-eyed damsel, Şadé the daughter of that prominent wealthy man popularly known as Chief Ajénifújà. As the bride was full of smiles, so also was the groom. They kissed each other intermittently. When the ceremony got to its peak, members of the Pirate Confraternity of which the groom is a member honoured the couple. Dressed in their confraternity's uniform, they displayed. In pairs they stood, raising their swords for the couple to pass under. We pray for the couple that they will bear fruits and multiply. Amen.

The actions in the ceremony through the use of imagery are presented in a way that it is easier for the listener to visualize and have a mental picture of the marriage event. A clip of the marriage event that accompanied the broadcast on the television makes it more vivid.

Similarly, from a newspaper report and from a radio broadcast (press review), Wólé in *Owo Blow* gets the information about the arrest and the killing of some members of his former armed robbery gang. The radio press review presents it thus:

Àwọ̀n ọ̀lọ̀pàá ti dárúkọ̀ àwọ̀n olè tí wọ̀n mú ní ọ̀jọ̀rú tó kọ́já. Nínú ìwé ìròyìn *Lagos Gist* ni a ti rí i kǎ pé ọ̀kan nínú àwọ̀n olè nàà a má a jẹ̀ Jugnu Ofege, èkejì a sì máa jẹ̀ Fatai Ajèròmí. Ìròyìn nàà tẹ̀síwájú pé àwọ̀n tí ó kù nínú ẹ̀gbẹ̀ adigunjalè yíì ni ó ti fi ara gbọta tí wọ̀n sì ti dí ẹ̀ni ànà. Fún ẹ̀kúnrẹ̀rẹ̀ àlàyé, ẹ̀ wo ọ̀jú ewé kẹta *Lagos Gist*.

The police have given the names of the armed robbers that were arrested last Wednesday. From the *Lagos Gist* newspaper, we read that one of the armed robbers is called Jugnu Ofege while the other is known as Fatai Ajeromi. The report further says that the remaining members of the gang have been

shot dead by the police. For full details, see page three of the *Lagos Gist*.

Another information concerning the alleged involvement of Wólé in the operations of the gang is also presented in a newspaper report with the caption 'Owo Blow Mentioned in Robbery Operation'.

The Yoruba film producers resort to the use of mass media in presenting vital information which generally adds value to the development of their plots.

4.2.4 Slang

Trask (1999 :279) has defined slang as 'an informal and often ephemeral linguistic form'. He further succinctly describes the expression :

Slang is an informal but colourful words and expressions. Slang expression are usually introduced by the members of a particular social group; they may remain the property of that group and serve as a badge of group identity. The majority of slang forms are transient : they are used for a few months or

a few years, and then they pass out of use, to be replaced by even newer slang terms.

Slang is characteristically associated with informal registers and presents an alternative lexis of a colloquial form. In the English language, slang initially originated from sex, money, liquor, drugs and parts of the body. It was after some time that a good ration of blasphemy, scatology and euphemism were also included. Below are examples of the slang forms of the five domains mentioned earlier:

Sex	Money (wealth)	Liquor	Drugs	Parts of the body
Bang	Pot of dough	Booze	Freak	Chassis frame } the body
Fuck	Bundle	Juice	Junk	Apple Grapes } female breast
Rub-a-dub	Pile	Jump steady	Cokey	Bald headed cock rod trouser snake } penis
Do the do	Wad	Hard stuff	Snow bird	Brush Bush Garden } Pubic hair
Grind	Roll in money	Moonshine	Weedhead	Cunt Pussy Honey pot Dead end street } vagina
Jack up Mount	Stinking Stuffy	White lady Blob	dope	

Similarly, in the Yorùbá language, slang originated from these domains mentioned above. Thus we have:

Sex → fífó, là mólè, ìbásùn

Money → kúdí, égo (adopted from the meaning of money in the Igbo language), Iṣu.

Drug → oṣà, gbáná, kùkúyè, òpá-iyonu (Indian hemp)

Female breast → òroṅbó, oṣàn, kèngbe wàrà, ṣìkìṣìkì

Because of its uncouth nature, majority in the Yoruba society see slang as dirty and indecent. They see it as the property of the touts and as a language of the irresponsible and uneducated.

Eric Patridge in Crystal (1995 :53) also, observes that, among other things, slang is used 'to show that one belongs' and 'to exclude others'. This group-identifying function of slang provides the basis for its use in Yorùbá video films. In the films, slang serves as the property of urchins (area boys), hoodlums and contract killers. This expression is employed to mark social or linguistic identity of these groups. For

reason of social identity, members of these groups seem to be linguistically different.

In *Owo Blow*, the dexterity in the use of slang is striking. Some examples will suffice.

When Wólé narrates his pathetic story of how he became a wanderer to Jeje, his old school mate and an urchin, the latter replies him in a prose laced with slangs:

Story ẹ yíí wà pathetic gan an. Biography ẹ, tí wọn bá maá kọ ọ sínú ìwé, ìwé á gan, ó má a kun ni. Ha! But at the same time, bemi ẹ wà yí, mi ò lè ní mi ò mò ẹ ní. Mà á dẹ help ẹ. *Ọmọ*, èmi a settle awọn boys. Mà á mú ẹ wọ *company*. O ẹ́ ẹ́ à rí wa lẹ̀ẹkan. Nígba tí à n *jàṣẹ́ mọ́ra*. Area Boys, èrè to pé, men. *PLC* ni. Tó o bá ti wọ *company*, tó o bá bèrẹ̀ iṣẹ́, wà á má a *ṣeṣu*. Wà á *ṣeṣu* e, ìwọ gan wà á padà sílé fine, láì *jọjà*. Because èmi tó n wò yíí, *ọjà*, *gbáná*, cocaine, heroine, nńkan tí mò n fi owó temi *jẹ* nìyẹn. My advice to you ni wì pe to bá

dàbí pe o ti wọ company, ọmọ! Ma try ẹ o. Kò nì sòwò tó pé rárá. Wà á ti gbẹ tán kó o tó mọ nnkan tó sẹlẹ. Ọmọ máa fine.

Your story is very pathetic. If one should write your autobiography, it will be very voluminous. Ah! But at the same time, as I am, I cannot claim that I do not know you. I will help you. Boy, I will settle the boys. I will make sure you are employed in the Company. You saw us too the other time when we were seriously working. Area boys, a rewarding venture. It is PLC. if you are employed in the Company, if you start work you will be making money. You will be making your money and you too will return home happy without indulging in drugs. Because, me that you are looking at hard drugs such as cocaine, heroine are what I use my money for. My advice to you is that if you join the Company, boy don't try it. It is not rewarding at all. You must have become so dry (lose weight) before you know what is happening. Boy! Go on enjoying yourself.

After Wọlé has joined the 'Company', the leader of the group one day observes his laickadaisic attitude and scolds him :

Ọmọ àlẹ̀ ní ẹ̀. Kí ló ẹ̀ ẹ̀? Wèrè yẹ̀n ò tán lára ẹ̀ ní. A! má rò pé o ti ní *stay* o. Agídí ní wọ̀n fí gbà ẹ̀ sínú ẹ̀gbẹ̀ wa yíí o. Kò yẹ̀e ní? À ń *şışe ajě* ò ní rẹ̀rìn ín. Kí ló fa laughter? Kí ló fa laughing fun ẹ̀?

You are a bastard. What is wrong with you? The madness traits are still in you. Ah! Do not feel you have been employed permanently. We employed you into this group controversially. Can't you understand? We are working for money, you are laughing. What is the cause of your laughter? What causes your laughter?

Slang is also utilised in the scene where Wọlé and Ajírẹ̀bí clash in Àmìn Ọ̀run. Wọlé had gone to look for Tómi, his wife in his mother-in-law's house after she had abandoned him but Ajírẹ̀bí, the security man,

acting on instruction refuses to allow Wọlé in. The following dialogue ensued:

Wọlé: Kí, kí, kí ló n ń ẹ yín? E dẹ fẹ̀ tìlẹ̀kùn mọ mi lójú.

Ajírẹbi: Ẹ́yín gbójú yín síbi ilẹ̀kùn ni ì.

Wọlé: A a! kí ló n ẹ yín báyií?

Şé kì í ẹ pé ẹ mu igbó láààrò yíi?

Ajírẹbi : A! doctor, ó ju ẹnu yín lọ ò, Ọlórún. Tí ò bá ẹ pé ẹ jẹ ẹni tí mo mọ ni, mà á rọọsi yín, ẹ ẹ fídí jálẹ̀.

Wọlé: Ẹ má sọ bẹ̀ẹ̀ mọ. Ẹ wò ó èèyàn kàn ti cool down ni. Şé ẹ rí èmi tí ẹ n wò yíi, èmi ni *bàbá aluta* nígbà tí èniyàn sì n ẹ aluta. Şé ẹ understand. So, ẹ má ba mi try nonsense.

Ajírẹbi : Ẹ ẹ ní wèrè. Kí ló n ẹ yín? Tí ẹ bá ní wèrè, ẹ ẹ *lápótí èşù* ...

Wọlé: Apári ọmọ Yákúbà

Ajírẹbi : Tíẹ náà fẹ̀ ẹ dé, ọmọ kílóòbù.

Wolé: What?, what?, what is wrong with you? You want to slam the door on my face?

Ajirébi: It's you that put your face near the door.

Wolé: Ah! Ah! What is wrong with you? I hope you have not taken indian hemp this morning.

Ajirébi : Ah! Doctor, this is too big for your mouth. If not because you are someone that I know, I would have rushed you and you will fall.

Wolé: Don't say that again. Look, one has only cool down. Me that you are looking at, I led students' riots when I was in school. Do you understand? So don't try any nonsense with me.

Ajirébi: You don't have any trace of madness and if you do, you don't devil's instruments ...

Wolé: Bald man, the son of Yàkubà.

Ajirébi: Yours will soon come, club man.

From the evidences above, we can deduce that slang is a colloquial departure from the standard Yorùba usage. It is often imaginative, vivid and ingenious in its construction. Its presence in Yorùbá video films is an evidence of the vitality of the Yorùbá language and language at play.

In spite of the negative attitude many have towards the use of this linguistic form, we believe that slang is an effective means of communication in the Yorùbá society today. Slang introduces new concepts and new expression which are indices of language development. The English language today is rich in vocabulary because it has always freely admitted new words. Quite a number of English slang can now be found in the standard form.

In the Yorùbá society today, slang, though originated from a smaller group, has become one of the commonest means of communication among different classes of people. Because it is more picturesque, idiomatic, vivid and humorous, it has eventually catches the fancy of the general public and used at times in place of standard form.

Slang can be upgraded to the standard form where they will contribute to the richness of the Yorùbá language. Like more standard

usage, slang develops over the years, responding in kind to the vagaries and development of the society in which it is created and used.

4.2.5 Code-Mixing

Ìṣòlá (1996) has described code mixing in the Yorùba film as an anathema. He condemns the frivolity of Yoruba screenplay writers in making use of half-English and half-Yorùba for dialogue and posits that Yorùbá film-makers should be language reformers instead of being lazy and irresponsible in holding up to what is in essence a disease of imitation. Though, Ìṣòlá believes that the video is 'vulnerable and can be subjected to all kinds of vulgarising pressure' he still feels that 'cheap profit and cultural decadence are veritable adversaries a producer should contend with'.

Empirical research has established that code-mixing is a characteristic of language use in bilingual or multilingual communities such as Nigeria.⁶ This is a linguistic phenomenon that Nigerian speech communities have not been able to escape from. Every 'educated' Nigerian is essentially a bilingual, communicating with its kith and kin in

his mother tongue and with fellow Nigerians of other linguistic groups in English. Since films portray the society, it then follows that it may reflect this societal phenomenon. Contemporary films reflect contemporary issues and it is only natural that the norms and practices of the society they imitate may be reflected.

Moreover, the speech of characters, at times, reflects their roles. The utterances of a non-literate character, for instance, may be rich in unadulterated Yorùbá and figurative expressions while those of a literate character may skilfully portray the actual sociolinguistic contemporary behaviour.

There are few Yorùbá video films that are devoid of code-mixing. They include *Èkùlé Ọrun*, *Fópomóyò*, *Kòşéégbé* and *Ó Le Kú*. Apart from these films and some few others, most of the speech in others are presented in half-Yorùbá and half-English.

Code-mixing in Yorùbá films are of two types. They are lexical intrusion and phrasal switches. While lexical intrusion involves the imposition of words from another language into a speech, phrasal switches, on the other hand, involves the interference of phrases from

another language on the discourse. We shall go ahead to give examples of each type as they occur in Yorùbá video films.

a. **Lexical Intrusion**

In Àmìn Ọrun, Wọlé, a Medical Doctor employs code-mixing to narrate to his in-laws and Ẹniitàn how he and Tómi, his wife find out that Ríísí did not die after all after they return from abroad :

Ó n lọ bá Tòkunbò ní *school* wọn. Ó n lọ
disturb ẹ. Ìgbà yẹn la fi *realise* pé kò kú

She was going to see Tòkunbò in her school.
 She was disturbing her. That was how we
 realised that she did not die.

Similarly, in *Owo Blow*, when Mr Owólabí's family visits him in prison, his speech to Wọlé, his son is intruded with English lexicons:

Gbogbo ǹnkan tí mi ò lè ẹ nígbà tí mo wà
 ǹlé, o ti n ẹ bí bàbá fún *family*. Mo wá n

gbàdùrà pé, gbogbo ǹnkan tó o bá ǹ dáwólé,
school ẹ ni, business ni, á prosper ni

All I could not do when I was at home, you are now acting as the head of the family. I am now praying that, all you lay your hands on, whether it is your education or business will prosper.

In *Ìyá Ni Wúrà*, also, Ẹkùn, Goodluck's bodyguard, code-mixes while seeking the consent of his master before allowing Justice Nelson who comes on a visit into the compound:

King bàbá, ó ní Judge loun. Ẹ fún mi ní order.

King, he said he is a Judge. Give me an order.

b. **Phrasal Switching**

Phrases from two languages may succeed each other in apparently random order. This is a common feature in some of the contemporary Yoruba video films.

In *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀*, for instance, the 'kábiyesi's' speech while welcoming Mr Johnson, the industrialist to his palace contains phrasal switching:

Nice meeting you ... sit down. Em! We want people like you, *kẹ ẹ wálé, kẹ ẹ wá* develop *ilú yii*. *Ìgbà témi wà ní London, wọ́n* send to me ni to come and take up this assignment and mi o hesitate to do so.

It is nice meeting you ... sit down. Eh! We want people like you to come home and develop this town. I was sent for in London to come and take up this assignment and I did not hesitate to do so.

The dialogue between *Wọ́lé* and *Mopé* in *Owo Blow* when the former accuses the sister of tarnishing the image of the family because of her infidelity reflects phrasal switching:

Wọ́lé: *Ẹ má* destroy image family *yii, àntí* mi.

Mopé: K'emi ma destroy image family. Şé o mọ ǹnkan tó ò ní sọ Wọlé. Hẹn! Şé o rò pé inú mi dùn sí gbogbo ǹnkan tó ní şẹlẹ̀ ni. Mummy sick, iwọ náà mọ pé wọn ní high blood pressure. Oúnjẹ kò sí nílẹ̀ ... Àwọn ìbejì need owo common entrance. Inú mi ò dùn si. Mi ò lè jókòó, kí n máa wo everybody kí wọn starve to death.

Wolé : My auntie, don't destroy the image of this family.

Mopé: That I should not destroy the image of the family? Wọlé, do you really mean what you are saying? Do you feel I am happy about all that is happening? Mummy is sick. You know she is hypertensive. There is no food at home.... The twins need their common entrance fees. I am not happy about the situation. I can't just sit back watching everybody starve to death.

Mayowá's response to the preaching of Mr and Mrs Martins about Christ in *Ogun Àtiléwá* is also laced with this urban linguistic variety:

Làì ní Jésu yìi, ilé mi tòrò. I have peace, good children ... Láì ní Jésu yìi, I got promotion. Without having this Jesus, ilé mi dára.

Without accepting this Jesus, I have a peaceful home. I have peace, good children ... Without this Jesus, I was promoted. Without having this Jesus, my home is serene.

Though, bilingualism can be an asset for national development in that it can promote intra-group understanding and national unity, it is, however, our view that there must be conscious and vigorous effort to stem the tide of code-mixing which favours the domination of the English language over Nigerian languages. Since language is a definitive factor in cultural identification, the hope of renewal for Yorùbá culture according to Ìṣòlá (1996 :139) 'lies in the active promotion of its language in every available medium'.

4.2.6 Yorùbá Traditional Oral Materials

This section contains discussions on the Yorùbá traditional oral materials that are present in the Yorùbá video film. The objective is to characterise each of the verbal art, what distinguishes one type from the other and the degree to which they occur in the Yorùbá video film. The traditional oral materials that are present in the Yorùbá video film are: incantation, *iwúre* and *ifá* divination poetry. We shall now go ahead to discuss each of these categories.

4.2.6.1 Incantation (Ofo)

According to Olatúnjì (1984 :139), *ofo* is cultic and mystical in its expectation. *Ofo* is the verbal aspect of magic. It is used by man to subject both the natural and supernatural worlds to his will. Other aspects of magic are the use of charms and rites.

Ìṣòlá (1996 :124) has identified three functions of *ofo*. First, it is used as a supplicatory argument to back up one's request made to the deity. Second, it serves as a source of power to force one's will on an

unwilling target and lastly, it is a means of acquiring power to overwhelm one's adversary in heated and confrontational exchanges.

The use of *ofò* pervades the Yorùba video film. Out of the 30 Yorùbá video films used as specimen for this study, there are 20 (67%) of them where we have this poetic genre. The reason for this is not far fetched. Incantation is an aspect of Yorùba life. In an attempt to control the physical and metaphysical world around them in their day-to-day activities, the Yorùbá use incantation. This is why it is so pervasive in the Yorùba video films.

In *Òbúkọ Dúdú*, for instance, Mojí is advised by the *ifá* priest to perform a rite before confronting Adérùpọkọ to avenge the latter's misdeed to her. She performs the rite using the *ofò* as an accompaniment to the sacrifice :

Igbó jújú òhun lorúkọ tí à n pe ikú.

Ọ̀nà jùjù òhun lorúkọ tí à n pe ààrùn.

Adétúká lorúkọ tí à n pe èfú.n

Adèrìnàkà òhun lorúkọ tí à n pe èsù ọ̀dàrà.

̀̀N jẹ́ ó wá ẹ̀fùfùlẹ̀lẹ̀,

Dábi padà sọ̀nìbì.

Ẹ̀fùfùlẹ̀lẹ̀.

Adẹ̀rùpọ̀kọ̀ ló bá n'perí mi ní bì,

Ẹ̀fùfùlẹ̀lẹ̀.

Dábi padà sọ̀nìbì,

Ẹ̀fùfùlẹ̀lẹ̀.

Torí pé kí ni?

Àdiitú làá dirú.

Àdiitú làá diyò

Tónirú bá dirú kalẹ̀,

Ọ̀lọ̀bẹ̀ ní í tú u.

Àgbéjùsilẹ̀ lọ̀mọ̀dé gbégi eléèrà.

Tá a bá mọ̀pòlọ̀ tí ò jọ kọ̀nẹ̀kọ̀,

À á gbé e jù sílẹ̀ ní ò.

Gbogbo ẹ̀yin tí ẹ̀ bá wà nídii ọ̀rọ̀ mi pátápátá,

Ẹ̀ gbé mi jù sílẹ̀.

Kẹ̀ ẹ̀ jẹ́ n má a bágbesi ayé mi lọ.

Bàbá ọ̀dẹ̀ ní í perí mi níbì,

À ẹ̀sàà dábi padà sọ̀nìbì,

Ẹ̀fùfùlẹ̀lẹ̀.

Igbó dúdú (the black jungle) is the name we call death.

Ọ̀nà jùju (the dread footpath) is the name we call affliction.

Adétúká (He that scatters people) is the name we call spell.

Adérìnaká (He that wonders about) is the name we call Èṣù

Ọ̀dàrà (the trickster god).

Now it is the turn of the ferocious gale,

Send evil back to the evil doer,

The ferocious gale.

If it is Adérùpọ̀kọ̀ that is behind my misfortune,

The ferocious gale.

Send evil back to the evil doer,

The ferocious gale.

Because of what?

The locust seed is untied (set free) from the wrapper.

The salt is untied (set free) from the wrapper.

If the seller of the locust seed wraps it,

It is the cook that unties it.

A child drops an ant infested wood abruptly.

If we catch a toad that does not resemble the frog,

It is dropped abruptly.

All that are behind my misfortune,

Set me free.

Let me continue to live my life.
 If it is the security man that is behind my misfortune,
 Send evil back to the evil doer,
 The ferocious gale.

With this *ofọ* and rite, *Mojí* succeeds in her revenge mission.

In *Èkùró Ọlọjà* also, *Alákijà* steals the 'èkùró ọlọjà' from *Ẹlẹmọ̀nà* by forcing his will on him employing incantations which make *Ẹlẹmọ̀nà* falls into a deep slumber:

Òkú ọdún mèta ìí rójú bárayé wíjọ.

Àgbinsínú legbin ín gbin.

Àkùnsínú lẹkùn ún kùn.

Ẹmú ò gbọdọ mú ni tì lágbẹde.

À sùn fọnfọn ni tífọn.

Oorun níí gba tọwọ ọmọdé.

Oorun níí gba tọwọ àgbà.

Gbogbo ẹyin tẹ ẹ wà nínú ilé yíí,

Ké ẹ sùn.

Ké ẹ sun àsùn piyè.

A three year old corpse cannot argue a case with the living.

It is within itself that the kob antelope grunts.

It is within itself that the leopard grumbles.

Spincers cannot fail to hold the iron piece in the smithy.

A deep sleep is the lot of the *ifon*.

It is sleep that takes something from the hand of the child.

It is sleep that takes something from the hand of the adult.

All the people in this house,

You should sleep.

You should sleep a deep sleep.

Incantation is distinguishable from other poetic genres by its mystical and metaphysical expectations. In incantation, the potency of the spoken word gives strength to the magic.

4.2.6.2 **Iwure**

The address of a prayer to a deity or other subject of worship for a person is referred to as *iwure*. Usually in Yorùbáland, *iwure* expresses blessings from the elderly to the younger ones. The blessing may touch on a number of desires or wishes such as wealth, peace, love, good

health and other good things of life. *Ìwúre* can be used for precatative and invocative purposes.

Ìwúre occurs in some Yorùbá video films such as *Owo Blow*, *Bàbá Àgbà*, *Èkùró Ọlójà* and *Ó Le Kú*. Among these films, it is much more pronounced in *Ó Le Kú*.

In *Ó Le Kú*, when Àjàní visits his uncle in Lagos after his final degree examination to collect the Volkswagen car the latter had promised him, the uncle after the presentation of the car thereafter blesses him:

Ọlọrun ó fun ọ lókun.

Pírí ló mọ ọ sùn.

Pírí ló mọ ọ jí.

Pírí ló sì mọ ọ dídè.

Torí pé pírí lologó jí.

A ì bá ọkùn ẹyẹ lóri ìtẹ.

Yí ó da fún ọ.

Yí ó da fún ọ.

God will give you strength.
 Soundly shall you sleep.
 Soundly shall you wake.
 Soundly shall you rise.
 Because the pin-tailed whydah⁷ wakes soundly.
 No one sees a sick bird on the nest.
 It will be well with you.
 It will be well with you.

In the same film, Bòdè, Àjàní's elder brother also blesses Şadé whom he meets in Àjàní's house:

Arábìnrin, yí ó dáa fún ọ.
 O ó jèrè.
 O ó jèrè òkíkí baba ajé.
 O ó jẹ tọlá ginnìginnì aşọ òde iràgà.
 O ó jẹ tàkònkótán ohun ọrọ ibẹ.
 O ó máa şégun lóùn ún.
 O ó máa şégun lósi.
 O ó máa bi àwọn ọtá lulẹ láàrin agbo.
 Àya wọn ló máa gbà kọjá.
 Ìwọ ló lékè àwọn ọtá rẹ.

Lady, it will be well with you.

You will be blessed.

You will be blessed with fame, the father of wealth.

You will be blessed with beautiful clothes from iraga metropolis.

You will be blessed with inexhaustible wealth.

You will be victorious to your right.

You will be victorious to your left.

You will be victorious over your enemies in gatherings

You will match on their chests.

You will be victorious over your enemies.

Similarly, in *Owo Blow* when Wọlé presents a cash gift to the Chairman of the Drivers' Union, the latter shows his appreciation in return through blessing:

O ẹ́ a dúpẹ́ o.

Ojú ò ní tì ọ́.

O ò ní ẹ́ é tì o.

Iwájú, iwájú báyíi lẹ́pá ẹ̀bìtì í ré sí.

Iwájú lo ó mọ ọ lọ.

Wà á sẹ́gun òtá.

Wà á rẹ̀yìn odi.

Ojú ò ní tì ọ́.

Thank you very much.

Disgrace shall not be your portion.

You will succeed.

It is to the front that the trap trips.

You will always move forward (progress).

You will be victorious over your enemies.

You will subdue your adversaries.

You will not be put to shame.

4.2.6.3 Ifa Divination Poetry (Ẹ̀sẹ̀ Ifá)

In the Yorùba traditional society, the *ifá* priest is usually consulted on issues that bother on the lives of people, present and future. Whenever decision is to be taken and there are several options, the *ifá* is consulted. *Ifá*, therefore becomes 'the source of order and the bridge to make order achievable within the physical realm' (Okome 1997 :30).

As the mouthpiece of other divinities, *ifá* is the repository of all the myths and moral tenets of them all. This is why when *ifá* speaks

through the priest, its literary corpus offers us through the use of analogy, images and symbols what to do to be at peace with God, the supernatural powers and mankind.

In video films like *Èkùrò Olójà*, *Ó Le Kú* and *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀*, *ifá* is consulted for solution to crises or problems.

In *Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀*, for instance, Ọ̀tún consults the *ifá* priest to find out the cause of Sànyà and Ajíbádé's death and what could be done to forestall such calamity in Ajêigbe town. The vehicle for the communication of *ifá*'s message is through narration:

Ọ̀kànràn wọ̀nrin onilẹ̀ ló làre.

Àjẹ̀jì ò mọ̀sẹ̀ ilẹ̀.

Èjọ̀ níláńlá ní í ọ̀ba lórópo.

Àrùwẹ̀ nílá ọ̀sẹ̀ láàfin ọ̀ba.

Oówo níláńlá so àwọn àgbà lẹ̀nu.

Àwọn ló dífá fún Ọ̀rúnmìlà.

Ifá ní lọ sí ibi àjò tó funfun bí ọ̀jọ̀.

Yóó gbẹ̀gbẹ̀édógún ọ̀dún lẹ̀hùn-ún.

Nígbà tí Ọ̀rúnmìlà dé,

Wọ̀n l'Ọ̀rúnmìlà ò nilẹ̀ mọ̀.

Ọrúnmilà ní ta ló nilẹ?

Wọn lóòṣà ni.

Ọrúnmilà ní kí wọn lọ rẹ é p'Òòṣà wá.

Wọn p'Òòṣàlá dé,

Ọrúnmilà bí í léèrè,

Òòṣàlá kú sórí ilẹ.

Wọn sin in sórí ilẹ,

Ó ní ki wọn p'Ọṣun wá.

Wọn p'Ọṣun wá sórí ilẹ,

Ọrúnmilà bí í léèrè,

Ọṣun kú sórí ilẹ.

Ọkànràn wọnrín, the owner of the land is justified.

The stranger knows nothing about the land.

A big problem puzzles the king.

Bereavement takes place in the palace of the king.

Big boils afflict the mouth of the elders.

Ifà divination is performed for Ọrúnmilà.

Ifá is embarking on an immaculate journey.

He will be away for three thousand years.

When he returns,

He is told that he is no more the owner of the land.

Ọ̀rúnmìlà asked them who the owner of the land is
They said it is Ọ̀òṣálá.

Ọ̀rúnmìlà asked them to invite Ọ̀òṣálá.

He is invited.

Ọ̀rúnmìlà asked him.,

Ọ̀òṣálá died on the land.

He is buried on the land.

He asked them to invite Ọ̀sun.

They invited Ọ̀sun to the land.

Ọ̀runmìlà asked her.

Ọ̀sun died on the land.

As implied in the ifa verse above, two gods died because they illegally acquired Ọ̀rúnmìlà's land. The events in the *ẹ̀ṣẹ ifà* above is an analogy of the message of the ifà priest to Ọ̀tún :

Ó dèèyàn méjì tó kú lóri ọ̀rọ̀ tẹ ẹ bá wá yíí o.
Ènikẹ̀ta ó ku o, nítorí wọn talẹ ni. Àkúfà sị ni.

Two people have died on this matter that you have come to investigate. The third person will also die because they sold a land. And it is a chain death.

In this section, we have identified the various linguistic patterns used in the Yorùbá video film. We have looked at the speech in the film texts and have used their contents and the context in which they occur to categorise them. Now, we are going to discuss the non-verbal form of communication that are present in the Yorùba video film.

4.3 Paralinguistic Devices

As already discussed in 2.1.5.1, by paralinguistic devices, we mean the use of body language (kinesics) as non-verbal mode of communication. In the Yorùbá video film, some body and facial expressions are used to convey meaning.

In *Taxi Driver*, for instance, the winking by the leader of the syndicate who use human beings for money-making rituals to his 'boys' signifies that the little boy who has just been kidnapped should be killed.

Similarly, in the scene where Rí sí is involved in a motor accident in *Àmìn Ọrun*, the posture of the eye witnesses suggests that something terrible has happened. The witnesses are first seen carrying their hands

on their heads with their mouth wide open before the camera focuses on Rísi soaked in her own blood.

There are instances where the face of the characters in the Yorùbá video films also signals a wide range of emotions. The mien of Babá Sàlá in *Ọrun Móoru* when death appears to kill him, for instance, portrays fear. The countenance of Wọlé in *Owo Blow* after hearing about the emergence of Jéjé, his old friend and the latter's innocuous confession that links him with armed robbery signifies sadness and regret.

On the other hand, in *Ó Le Kú*, in the scenes where Àjàní renders his love verses to his damsels, the facial expression and the state of mind of the girls show that they are happy, full of desire and long for Àjàní.

As pointed out earlier in Chapter three, various facial expressions such as raised brows, wide eye, winking, winking, rolled eyes, clenched teeth, toothy smile and pouting are used by Bàbá Sàlá in *Ọrun Móoru* to generate laughter and imitate the physical appearance and nature of

the fairies and gnomes which he encounters during his search for wealth.

In this chapter, we have considered the various narrative techniques which have been used in the Yorùbá video film for effect. They fall largely under three broad categories namely technical, linguistic (speech) and paralinguistic (non-verbal). These devices create a gamut of effects which are pivotal or central to the success of the message which the producers intend.

NOTES

1. *Ó Le Kú* is an adaptation of Akínwùmí Ìṣòlára's novel of the same title.
2. In the film, fourteen tracks are identified. Twelve of them are composed by Ebenezer Obey while two are those of Yusuf Olatúnjí. They are:

Ebenezer Obey

- i) Èní rí ǹnkan he
- ii) Maá muí láye ǹbi
- iii) Ọ̀rọ̀ mi kọ̀ rára
- iv) Board members
- v) Gbogbo bá a ti ǹ ẹ
- vi) Ọ̀lọ̀ mi jẹ́ ká jọ̀ yọ̀
- vii) Happy Birthday
- viii) Gbọ̀ ẹ̀bẹ̀ mi
- ix) Èdùmàré sọ̀rọ̀ mi dayọ̀
- x) Ètò Ìgbéyàwó
- xi) Àimàsìkò
- xii) Lady Paulina

Yusuf Olatunji

xiii) Ó yẹ ká ní fura

xiv) Àṣá n bẹ̀yẹ̀lé ẹ̀rẹ̀

These tracks are also listed in the video film.

3. By making use of these musical ensembles, the producers try to re-enact the Yorùba traditional method of ushering in a king into the palace.
4. See Adélékè (1995 :5)
5. Hollywood films such as *Going Bananas*, *The gods Must Be Crazy* and *Amos and Andy* are films that were shot in different parts of East and South Africa.
6. Code-mixing has been one of the subjects of research by linguists. Scholars such as Adéníran (1977), Ahukanna (1990) and Oyètádé (1992) have conducted critical investigation on this linguistic behaviour. They all agree that code-mixing characterises the speech behaviour of bilinguals and that it owes its development to language contact. The general belief of linguists about this phenomenon is that the languages in contact are complementary in the sense that they are more or less equally mix to facilitate communication. Code-mixing has also generated a lot of discussions amongst 'purists' who feel that this practice is a sign of deficiency in one of the languages in contact.

7. The pin-tailed whydah is a bird that has fast, direct and undulating flight. It walks daintily. The striking characteristics of this bird make the Yorùbá to refer to it especially when talking about good health.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this study, we have discussed the aesthetics of the Yorùba video film particularly as it is manifested in the various devices employed by the Yorùbá video film producers in their works. The study has shown that the Yorùba video film applies various techniques which can help us to define their aesthetics.

The various narrative techniques which fall largely under three broad categories namely technical, linguistic (the film as text) and paralinguistic (non-verbal) have been found to create a gamut of effects which are pivotal to the success of the message which the producers intend.

The application and/or adaptation of the aesthetic and the semiotic theories, which are the two theories employed for this study are considered most useful for this study. The various arguments of the two different schools of aestheticians, that is, the naturalists and the artists on aesthetic response to and perception of natural objects and

works of art, which are crucial to our analysis have been considered. While the naturalists hold the view that human imagination should be liberated from nature and that art is the creation of a new world and not the expression or reproduction of that world, the artists on the other hand hold that the distinguishing feature of excellence in the arts is something not to be found in nature. Based on these arguments of the two schools, we have been able to deduce that creativity, which is an essential ingredient of aesthetics is present in both natural and artistic objects.

One of the achievements of this study is its identification of the criteria for aesthetic evaluation and judgement. The 'serious content' view which maintains that to consider a work of art as great, human materials such as factual truth, religious belief, moral, social and political rightness must be present in such work is one of the criteria for aesthetic evaluation. In our own view, we have been able to point out that the greatness of art should not only be considered in terms of something resulting from its use aesthetically. Rather there should be a meaningful distinction between 'serious content' contributing great art

and 'serious content' making for great art. Other criteria for aesthetic judgement which have been considered in this work include originality, language style (which has always been referred to as the natural starting place for aesthetic study), and other narrative techniques such as interior monologue, dream device, suspense, flashback, etc. Other technical devices that are peculiar to the film medium which include the camera movement, camera angle, sound, lighting, etc. have also been considered for our aesthetic appraisal of the Yorùbá video film. Video film making has been described as the conscious manipulation of these cinematic devices. Instances where these devices are employed for special effects in the video films have been given to admire the dexterity at which the Yorùba video film producers have mastered the film art. Many of the films that fall within our scope have been noted for their luxuriant and opulent images of characters and objects through the use of these devices.

In this study, we have been able to identify the major reasons why the Yorùbá theatre practitioners embraced the video film after its inception. The video film medium offers them an alternative to the

inhibitions of the stage as they are thrilled by the power of the medium that is greatly increased by technical innovations and scientific discoveries, to open up new, hitherto unsuspected dimension of reality. Another reason is that the video film medium avails them the opportunity to record their works for posterity.

A useful contribution to the advancement of knowledge on the typology of Yorùbá video films has been made in this study. Using their contents and themes as criteria, we have been able to identify five types of Yorùbá video films. They are: folkloric, crime, religious, comic and love films. The contents and themes of some of these films have been discussed to reveal how they fall under each of these categories.

The various and diverse themes of the Yorùbá video film producers give us information about their moral concern and their relationship with their society. These themes are acted out and they are usually in consonance with the producers' creation of their characters. The producers' ideology and their method of characterisation have been revealed. The various themes are suggestive of the conformity of the producers with established principles

and rules as they elicit the Yorùbá worldview of moral excellence. Also, the characters in the Yorùbá video film are exposed by the producers through the employment of various identificatory and behavioural features which include their social roles, external appearance, qualities, traits, costume, actions and reactions. The Yorùba video film as an audio-visual medium has been utilised by the producers to create an indepth analysis of the characters. The various emotions, moods, gestures, mental preoccupations and gaits of these characters are revealed by the camera and provide source of information about them.

A further achievement of this work is its discussion of two of the film techniques which have not been perfected by the Yorùbá video film producers. These techniques are artificial lyricism or optical trickery and the synchronisation of image with sound. These flaws are noticeable in video films such as *Ọrun Móoru*, *Ọbúko Dúdú* and *Kòṣeégbé*.

This work has broken new grounds in the study of the Yorùba video film. It is the first work that has looked into both the technical and literary dimensions of the medium. Definitely, it will be a source

material for research on the Yorùba video film art. However, the Yorùbá video film, being a relatively young medium, still has a lot to benefit from scholarly explorations. A study of the aesthetics of the Yorùbá video film cannot provide an exhaustive work on the medium. There are still vast areas that call for further research. Since this work is a general consideration of the aesthetics of the Yorùbá video film further research can consider individual critical attention of the producers in order to provide a more detailed analysis of their works. Approaches such as sociology and style can also be considered as areas for further research.

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ANNEX 1

YORÙBÁ VIDEO FILMS SELECTED FOR THIS STUDY

1. Koṣeégbé
2. Àmìn Ọrun
3. Tí Olúwa Ni Ilẹ̀ I – III
4. Ọbúkọ Dúú
5. Ọrun Móoru
6. Ìyá Ni Wúra
7. Taxi Driver
8. Ó le kú I and II
9. Owo Blow I – III
10. Ogun Àtiléwá
11. Èèkùlé Ọrun
12. Fọpomọyọ
13. Èkùrọ Ọlọjà
14. Orogún Adédigba
15. Agbára Nlá I – III
16. Kánran The Killer
17. Şaworo Idẹ
18. Èmí Kan ₦1000

19. Òkò
20. Èbíkébí
21. Owú
22. Gbòngbò Èsè
23. Adùn I – II
24. Àsírí Nlá I – II
25. Ìkà Lomọ Ejò I – II
26. Ègún Ìpilẹṣẹ
27. Abéré Alhaja
28. Iyàwó Alhaji
29. Yemí My Lover
30. Èewọ

ANNEX 2

B. CATALOGUE OF YORÙBÁ VIDEO FILMS (VIDEOGRAPHY)

S/n	Title of the film	Producer	Year of Production
1.	Igi Da	Kòlá Olatúndé	1990
2.	Ajá Dúdu 1 and 2	Ọsọ Dáramọlá	1990
3.	Ode Ọsán	Ọsọ Dáramọlá	1991
4.	Ọta Ọlorun	Èbun Oloyeédé	1991
5.	Fọpomọyọ	Jimọ Aliu	1992
6.	Koto Ọrun	Yẹkinni Ajiléye	1992
7.	Ha! Èniyan	Sẹgun Rasco	1992
8.	Ajagunmàlẹ	Wemímọ Films	1992
9.	Itunú	Gbénga Adewusi	1992
10.	Orogun Ọrun	T. A. Balogun	1993
11.	Só Daa Bẹẹ?	Èbun Oloyeédé	1993
12.	Ninú Ikòkò	Suntab Films	1993
13.	Aşewo To Re Meka	Adẹbayọ Salami	1993

14.	Ọkọ Yoyo	Fẹsọ Oyewole	1993
15.	Aṣiri Nlá 1 and 2	Jídé Kosokó	1993
16.	Bọbọ Driver	Fola Films	1993
17.	Senior Girls	Fẹsọ Oyewole	1993
18.	Legal Wife	Suntab Films	1993
19.	Èhin Okú	Adeyemi Afqlayan	1993
20.	Ogun	Ajala Films	1994
21.	Owo Idan	(Moshood Abiola (Prof. Peller)	1994
22.	Ofa Oro	Yekinni Ajilaye	1994
23.	Ipo Ola	Lanre Abbey	1994
24.	Ere Gele	Taiwo Hassan (Ogogo)	1994
25.	Oluweri	(Moshood Abiola (Prof. Peller)	1994
26.	Bukola Omo Daddy 1-2	Aigbeni (D'Rovans)	1994
27.	Ilu Le	Adebayo Salami	1994
28.	Agbo Meji	Ola Makinwa	1994
29.	Adasi	Mrs. Olarewaju	1994

30.	Express Man	Wemimọ Films	1994
31.	Òkò	Adébáyọ Salámì	1994
32.	Diamond	Moses Olaiya Adéjùmọ	1994
33.	Ìrù Èşin	Èbùn Olóyede	1994
34.	Ododó Èyẹ	Wemimọ Films	1994
35.	Orò Kànkà	Delé Odùlé	1995
36.	Idunnu	Muyideen Aromirẹ	1995
37.	Orogún Adédigba	Oyin Adéjóbí	1995
38.	Ahọn	Péjú Ogunmọlá	1995
39.	Ti Olúwa Ni Ilẹ 1-3	Kareem Adépọju	1995/96
40.	Ipade	Love Olu	1995
41.	Nnkan Mi Ni	Adeyemi Afọláyán	1995
42.	Etekéte 1- 2	Jímọ Aliu	1995/96
43.	Ipade Ayọ	Léré Páimọ	1995
44.	Amin Orun	Tunde Hundeyin (Dudu)	1995
45.	Lakunle Alagbe	Delé Odùlé	1995

46.	Yétúndé Ayaba	M. O. Atóbátéjé	1995
47.	Moriamọ	Múyíwa Adépoju	1995
48.	About to Wed	Yinka Quadri	1995
49.	The Twins	Muyideen Aromiré	1995
50.	Moréniké Alágolo	Déle Odulé	1995
51.	Omọ Elépo	Jídé Kòsókó	1995
52.	Yemi My Lover 1-2	Yemí Ayébò	1995
53.	Láidé The House Girl 1-2	Muyideen Arómiré	1995
54.	Omọ Elépà	Kólá Oloótú	1995
55.	Londoner	Ọjọ Jolu	1995
56.	Agbara Nlá 1-4	Mount Zion Faith Ministry Intl.	1995
57.	Kanran The Killer	Remmy Toffy	1995
58.	Èwoléwo	Biyi Adé	1995
59.	Ta Ni Ki N Fé?	Muka Ray	1995
60.	Agba Wolii	Kayodé Oyebodé	1995
61.	Iya Ife	Oluwayemi Jayeola	1995

62.	Ọmọ Oòdua	Yẹkinni Ajiléye	1995
63.	Ọfin Fọju	Tayé Arógunmátidi	1995
64.	Ọrọ Ajọso	Akeem Adébayo	1995
65.	Èjẹ Okiki	Wálẹ Ilẹbiyi	1995
66.	Májẹmu	Rasak Ajao	1995
67.	Ìabakẹ 1 -2	Tóyin Afoláyan/Bàbá Ọlá Original	1995
68.	Pakute	Tóyin Afolábi	1995
69.	Ta Ni Wẹrẹ?	Comrade Ashaolu	1995
70.	Igbekun	Fẹmi Bright	1995
71.	Opéyemí	Ọga Williams	1995
72.	Edunjobi	Yinka Quadri	1995
73.	Ayọ The Queen	Muyideen Arómirẹ	1995
74.	Gbémisọlá	Adébayo Salami	1995
75.	Jẹnsimi	Sunday Soyinká	1995
76.	Ile Alayọ	Alhaji Kamala	1995
77.	Majiyagbe	Lady Smart	1996

78.	Jókotadé	Şola Şobowále	1996
79.	Ayé Yẹ Wọn Tán	Abíodún Abbey	1996
80.	Lakiribótó	Thompson	1996
81.	Ọrọ Mi Dayọ	Alhaji Wàabì Komina Alah	1996
82.	Nnkàn Onínkan	Modúpẹ Johnson	1996
83.	Èmi Kan ₦1,000	Salaudeen Yusuff	1996
84.	Bóorepò	Yẹmisi Jayeola	1996
85.	Ọmọnyí	Fẹmi Ọgúnrọgba	1996
86.	Tẹmidire	Adébimpe Bada	1996
87.	Bankẹ	Tóyin Adẹgbola	1996
88.	Iyawó Alhaji	Jídẹ Kosókọ	1996
89.	Lady Gay	Ayọ Akínbọla	1996
90.	Rọmọkẹ Adunbárin	Adẹbayọ Salami	1996
91.	Ọbẹ Ayé	Gengil	1996
92.	Ojú Orón	Yẹmi Ọgungbe	1996
93.	Irawọ	Alhaji Ọdẹrinlọ	1996

94.	Eja Aarọ	Yomi Ogunmola	1996
95.	Asiri Ola	Benjamin Oluwole	1996
96.	Ina Omọ	Rasak Ajao	1996
97.	Adetoun	Bisi Badejo	1996
98.	Asiri Iya Eko	Wale Awojobi	1996
99.	Tinúadé	Mrs. Idowu Philips	1996
100.	Oko Aarọ	Junfako Productions	1996
101.	Opó Olórún	Adéyemi Afolayan	1996
102.	Agbo Odaju	Oyedele Video Production	1996
103.	Ta Ni ki N Pa?	Adéfemi Awofe	1996
104.	Lady Terror	Toyin Afolayan	1996
105.	Koseetú	Lere Paimo	1996
106.	Erú Wèrè	Fatai Adetayo	1996
107.	Ija Agba Meji 1 & 2	Peju Ogunmola	1996/2000
108.	Ayedun	Babatunde Omidina	1996
109.	Iwa Omọ	Rasak Ajao	1996

110.	Èkún Ayò	Abdullahi Rasak	1996
111.	Èta Òkò	Jídé Kosókò	1996
112.	For Better For Worse	Gbénga Adéwùsì	1996
113.	Tèmiyèmi	Akeem Adébáyò	1996
114.	Ere Ije	Akeem Adébáyò	1996
115.	Desperate Woman	Solá Awóléyè	1996
116.	Ojò Ayò	Adégòkè Àina	1996
117.	Tèmiladé Alápepe	Jimò Salau	1996
118.	Iya Àgbà	Mufutau Oládòkun	1996
119.	Májègò	Leo Manik Ògúnymí	1996
120.	Oriyomí 1- 2	S. I. Òla	1996
121.	Irekoja	Yòmí Adékoyà	1996
122.	Èran Iya	Dèjì Adenugà	1996
123.	Èbùn Oluwa	Yèmi Fàròunbí	1996
124.	Omo Omi	Olori Adéola	1996
125.	Adáramásunlé	Fèsò Oyèwólé	1996

126.	Imùlẹ̀ Ifẹ̀	Bìmpẹ̀ Adẹkọ́lá (Iretí)	1996
127.	Ènu Òrófó	Rasaq Àràṣán	1996
128.	Ìtanna Ọ̀lá	Şesan Àdió	1996
129.	Battle To Finish	Láńrewájú Ọ̀dẹ́ajo	1996
130.	Èbuté	Èbùn Oloyede	1996
131.	Sisi London	Muyideed Aromirẹ̀	1996
132.	Èjẹ̀ Ọ̀run	Dìran Adéogun	1996
133.	Ànikẹ̀ Ọ̀gò	Bọ́lá Obot	1996
134.	Èjẹ̀ Ifẹ̀	Kabiru Salami	1996
135.	Ìşile	Ládùn Ọ̀jorá	1996
136.	Lábe Ọ̀run	Muyideen Aromirẹ̀	1996
137.	Yemí in the Moon	Yemí Ayọ̀bọ	1996
138.	Ọ̀kọ Mummy	Tafa Bakare	1996
139.	Èdan 1- 2	Adélajá Ogunde	1996
140.	Kí Ló Kán? 1 - 2	Èbùn Oloyede	1996
141.	Àwọ̀n Àgbà	Dauda Adẹyẹmọ	1996

142.	Gbemisola 1-2.	Adébayo Salami	1996
143.	Danfo Driver	Kola Olootu	1996
144.	Ìdè Èṣù 1-4	Mount Zion Faith Ministry Intl.	1996
145.	Àsiri Mi	Jumoke Osin	1996
146.	Koseegbe	Tunde Kelani (Mainframe)	1996
147.	Ayo Ni Mo Fe	Tunde Kelani (Mainframe)	1996
148.	Omolade	Jide Kosoko	1996
149.	Ogun Oru	Ade Lawanson	1996
150.	Ìdè 1 and 2	Yekinni Ajileye	1996
151.	Boluwa Ba Fe	Wemimo	1996
152.	Baba Agba	Dele Odule	1996
153.	Dr. Brown	Olú Omójola	1996
154.	Ojú Tuntun	Dash Waves	1996
155.	The Virgin	Muyideen Aromire	1996
156.	Owo Asepò	Oyewole Olowomojuore	1996
157.	Ayokayo	Muyideen Aromire	1996

158.	Awakọ	Afẹlele Films	1996
159.	Iyawo Alarède	Gbénga Adéwùsì	1996
160.	Eewọ	Gbénga Adéwùsì	1996
161.	Ajeji	Gbénga Adéwùsì	1996
162.	Ìwọ Ni	Gbénga Adéwùsì	1996
163.	Inira Obinrin	?	1996
164.	Ọṣẹ Ifá	Aliu Jamiu	1996
165.	Golden Cage	?	1996
166.	Ọmọ	Adẹṣina Arákangúdu	
167.	Eni Ọmọ Sin	?	1996
168.	Àrokàn	?	1996
169.	Ọṣunwọn Ayé	?	1996
170.	Adẹṣewà	Ọladiipọ Motion Picture	1996
171.	Temi Ni	?	1996
172.	Ọmọwọn	?	1996
173.	Inira Ọmọ	Muyideen Arómiré	1996
174.	Ọmọ Èkùn		

175.	Gbẹsan	?	1996
176.	Ọpọn Ayé	Yekini Ajiléye	1996
177.	Èẹ kùlẹ Ọrun	Yekini Ajiléye	1996
178.	Èbíkẹbí	Alimak Film Production	1996
179.	Òkò	Awada Kẹrikeri	1996
180.	Etí Iboji	?	1996
181.	Adákẹdajọ	Mustapha Bakare	1996
182.	Tosibẹ	Sunday Films	1996
183.	Ajé	?	1996
184.	Ọrọ Ọmọ	Alasco Films	1996
185.	Èhin Ọkunkun	?	1996
186.	Àkànda	?	1996
187.	Ìyà Di Meji	?	1996
188.	Àgbẹkẹlẹ	Èbun Oloyede	1996
189.	Yemí Tuńráyọ	Yemí Ayébo	1996
190.	Mákan	?	1996

191.	Tori Abo	?	1996
192.	Èkùn	?	1996
193.	Owo Èṣù	Akin Ògúngbè	1996
194.	Olú Èsan	?	1996
195.	Èjẹ̀ Ọ̀dọ̀	Samson Jayéolá	1996
196.	Ajùmọ̀bí	?	1996
197.	Ìpadabọ̀ Abija	Yekinni Ajiléyẹ̀	1996
198.	Oríkunkun	?	?
199.	Ọ̀kọ̀ Ijamba	Mustapha Bakare	?
200.	Ta Ló Pa Chief?	Fatai Tẹmọ̀la	1996
201.	Epọ̀n Agbò	?	1996
202.	Abortion	Muyideen Aromire	1996
203.	The Big Guns	Dauda Adéyẹmí	1996
204.	48 Hours	Fatai Tẹníọ̀lá	1996
205.	Ta ló Lomọ̀	Adémọ̀lá	1996
206.	Ọ̀mọ̀ Elẹ́fọ̀ọ̀	Muka Ray Èyiwùmi	1996

207.	Onibúṛẹ	Gbénga Adéwùsì	1996
208.	Second Wife	Muyideen Aromire	1996
209.	Maradona	Gbenga Adewusi	1996
210.	Ọmọkẹyẹ	Bọsẹ Sàngókẹyẹ	1996
211.	Ìràwọ Mi	?	1996
212.	Ire Mi	?	1996
213.	Missing in Love	Èbun Olóyèdé	1996
214.	Express Man	Kàmoṛu Saba	1996
215.	Lucky Boy	Şẹsan Àdió	?
216.	Bus Conductor	Mustapha Bakare	1996
217.	Street Love	?	?
218.	Aşẹ Oro	Sunday Films	1996
219.	Adégbẹsan	Akeem Ajala	1996
220.	Bọseyẹkóri	Akeem Ajala	1996
221.	Ore Ọfẹ	Músili Salau	1996
222.	Ọláníyọnu	?	?
223.	Iyanu Nlá	?	?

224.	Ipá Idá	Nojimu Inango	?
225.	IyáỌkọ Mi	?	?
226.	Iwọ Kọ	?	?
227.	Adun 1-2	Muyideen Arómiré	1996
228.	Àpótí Ajé	Samson Film	1996
229.	Wúraọlá	Majekodunmi Production	1996
230.	Love '96	Sunday Osai	1996
231.	Ọ̀sikòyemí	Wemimọ Films	1996
232.	Iyawó Ọgá	?	1996
233.	8 Years	Taiwo Akinadé	
234.	Gbòngbò Èsẹ̀	Ọlasco Film Production	1997
235.	Ọ̀búkọ Dúdú	Baba Wánde	1997
236.	Owo Blow 1-3	First Call Production	1997/98
237.	Ó Le Kú 1-2	Tundé Kelani (Mainframe)	1997/98
238.	Ana Gómíná	Báyọwá Films International	1997
239.	Èwá Ọwuro	Wolad Film Production	1997
240.	Alájọbí	Aanú Oluwa Film Production	1997

241.	Ajò	Larry Communication	1997
242.	Igi Olúgbìn	Alasco Videos	1997
243.	Ajé	Consolidated Pictures	1997
244.	Ìpinnu Mi	Tenifab Motion Pictures	1997
245.	Àkẹ̀tẹ̀	Wings Movies	1997
246.	Aṣeni	Sara Pictures	1997
247.	Èkùró Olojá	Oyin Adéjọbí	1997
248.	Ọ̀pá Afọ́jú	Baba Wánde Film Production	1997
249.	Ogun Àtiléwá	Mount Zion Faith Ministry Int'l	1997
250.	Ologbe Larere	?	1997
251.	Owú	Yínká Fowóra	1997
252.	Ǹnkan Ob̀inrin 1-2	?	1997
253.	Awófele	?	1997
254.	Ija Aye	?	1997
255.	Aṣise	?	1997
256.	Giangageiya Oláiyá		

257.	Bóripé	?	1997
258.	Tánká	?	1997
259.	Aşiri Rábiatu	?	1997
260.	Dúró	Lazek Pictures	1998
261.	Ayé Obinrin	Legend Films	1998
262.	Ogbé Okàn	Ogogo Film Production	1998
263.	Iya Ibeji Eléran Igbé	Ogogo Film Production	1998
264.	Ìkà Lomọ Ejò 1 -2	Bàbá Wandé Film Production	1998
265.	Ìbèrè Opin Ayé	Mount Zion Faith Ministry Int'l	1998
266.	Aşişe Nlá	Mount Zion Faith Ministry Int'l	1998
267.	Atupá	Orìşabunmi Film Production	1998
268.	Alabá Onireşì	Kóredé Film Production	1998
269.	Èbuté	Oláiyá Film Company	1998
270.	Tori Ifé	Kaltoy Entertainment	1998
271.	Adéshina	Buk Dam Fad Production	1998
272.	Kányinsọlá	Olá Original Production	1998

273.	Ọ́lọ́run Ní	Alimak Film Production	1998
274.	Ó Léwu	Jimoh Aliu	1998
275.	Oṣu Mésan	Ànjòfẹ́ Film	1998
276.	Ilẹ̀kùn Àańú	Das Motion Picture	1998
277.	Afẹ́fẹ́	Máyòwá Films	1998
278.	Ìwà Obìnrin	Àrìyọ́ Osu Ventures	1998
279.	Ọwọ́ Ẹkún	Ade Mich Film Production	1998
280.	Ọlájìrẹ	Adio Film	1998
281.	Aginjù Ayé	Olúwalówí Venture	1998
282.	Ènìà Dúdú	Ogo Olúwa Kìitan Trading Coy.	1998
283.	Ojúlọ́gẹ	Aiyédùn Motion Pictures	1998
284.	Ègun Ìpilẹ̀sẹ́	El-Shaddai Drama Ministries	1998
285.	Mojoyin	Ijaduade Films	1999
286.	Ọpá Àjọbí	Wumyet Film Production	1999
287.	Ayé Kù síbì Kan	Yemi Adégunju Films	1999
288.	Gbòńgbò Ìkorò	Love Fellowship Drama Ministry	1999

289.	Orisun	Latter House World-Wide Ministry	1999
290.	Jesu Kristi Ti Nasareti	Femoye Video Production	1999
291.	Olugbala Gba Mi	Evom Production	1999
292.	Abiye Lomo Mi	Yab Films	1999
293.	Afe fe Aye	Ayomiku Pictures	1999
294.	Ajumobi	Olasco Films	1999
295.	Agogo Ogbon	Lady Pictures	1999
296.	Akobi	Corporate Pictures	1999
297.	Saworo Ide	Mainframe Production	1999
298.	Oyeronke	Adesqueen Films	1999
299.	Iya Orogun	?	1999
300.	Oshodi Oke	?	1999
301.	Adesile	?	1999
302.	Olúwanísolá	La Ganini Movie International	1999
303.	Agan Ale	Matthew Tomoye Video Production	1999
304.	O N Fo Loke	Rasco Films	1999
305.	Atubotan	Wemimọ Films	1999

306.	Adéyemí	Muka Ray Ejiwumi	1999
307.	Pelumi 1- 2	Flem Film Production	1999
308.	Aṣwó Kano	Ṣolá Ṣobowaké	1999
309.	Olusanjò	Aloy Production International	1999
310.	Ibugbè Ayò	Mao Films	1999
311.	Ayọku	Babatunde Omidina (Baba Suwe)	1999
312.	Ilé Olá	Ayò Olúyemí (Olasco)	1999
313.	Borítifé	Adébáyò Salami	1999
314.	Òriṣà	Adùkẹ́ Adéyemí	1999
315.	Ayelaagbè	Bioku Films	1999
316.	Ó N Fo Loke	Afro America and Rasco Film	1999
317.	Aṣiri Iya Eko	Olaso Film	1999
318.	Ewúro	?	1999
319.	Èbun	Funke Soroye Ogunmola	1999
320.	Aàrò Mèta	Adeníyí Ademókoyá (Ajewólé)	1999
321.	Subuolá	T & D Film Production	1999
322.	Ṣoló Mákíndé	Korede Film Production	1999

323.	Oláoruran	?	1999
324.	Mopelolá	?	1999
325.	Igbámládogí	Tq̄ba Opalẹyẹ	2000
326.	Adẹrẹ Alhaja	Maga Vision	2000
327.	Olá Abata	?	2000
328.	Ojú Agbami	Alimak Film Production	2000
329.	Ologbò Dúdú	Kolá Olootú	2000
330.	Amòokun Şèkà	V- Bee Media Network	2000
331.	Obálami	Amoye Film Company	2000
332.	Ojọ Esan	Mercy Film Production	2000
333.	Òwo Maału	Al_Bak Film Company	2000
334.	Arowolo	Kóredé Film Company	2000
335.	Idamu Otunba	Adébáyọ Salami	2000
336.	Opólumero	?	2000
337.	Iyá Olóbì	Raolab Film Production	2000
338.	Alápá Kan	Latons Video Ventures	2000
339.	Àbẹnì Oní Pangbẹ		

340.	Bùsáyò	Corporate Pictures	2000
341.	Tòmíwá	?	2000
342.	Sàanu Olu		2000
343.	Afolábí	Century Films	2000
344.	Olórùn Lúgò	?	2000
345.	Mamá Ò Ní Gbà	Faproms Promotion	2000
346.	Ọwọ́ Ènì	Yómí King Production	2000
347.	Iyabò Òlolo	Cal Ban Film Production	2000
348.	Òdodo Ọrò	Isolak Venture	2000
349.	Ènì Afẹ́	Zactis Production	2000
350.	Àşẹ Ọkà	Ọláoyè Venture	2000
351.	Ìbajẹ́ Ọjọ́ Kan	Ras-ad Films	2000
352.	Èrù Jẹ́jẹ́	A. A. Ajibolá Films	2000
353.	Ohun Ojuri	Tenifab Motion Pictures	2000
354.	Aşiwájú	Badjern Films International	2000
355.	Babá N Gbẹ́jọ́	Fowórà Films	2000

356.	Aláaṣírí	Lakog Film Production	2000
357.	Igbó Dúdú	Látúndé Films	2000
358.	Ìbalé	Gemini Films	2000
359.	Abọrẹ	Muka Ray Films	2000
360.	Ẹyẹ Ayé	Olasco Films	2000
361.	Ìkòrè	Itu Baruka Production	2000